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Table of Contents

(Files in PDF format)

1.	Pius ten Hacken, Renáta Panocová & Laura Giacomini Editorial DOI: 10.33542/JTI2025-2-1	2
2.	Mahmoud Afrouz Proposing a Tentative Revision Hypothesis for Sacred Texts: The Holy Qur'an's English Translation and Revision in Focus DOI: 10.33542/JTI2025-2-2	3
3.	Aseel Zibin, Renad Al-Momani, Areej Allawzi & Dina Salman Translating LOVE and BELOVED Metaphors: A Cogno-Cultural Analysis of <i>La Sombra del Viento</i> by Carlos Ruiz Zafón and its Arabic Translation DOI: 10.33542/JTI2025-2-3	20
4.	Roberto Martínez Mateo Multimodal Translation and Ideological Representation in Picture Books: A Case Study of <i>King and King</i> DOI: 10.33542/JTI2025-2-4	41
5.	Eivor Jordà Mathiasen Feminist Translation Strategies Revisited DOI: 10.33542/JTI2025-2-5	66
6.	Rachel E. Herring & Anne Catherine Gieshoff Exploring Curricular Aspects of Dialogue Interpreter Training: A Report on Two Surveys DOI: 10.33542/JTI2025-2-6	83
7.	Małgorzata Kodura Aspects of Creativity in AI-Powered Polish-to-English Literary Translation DOI: 10.33542/JTI2025-2-7	112

Editorial

From its start, the *SKASE Journal of Translation and Interpretation* has been a Diamond Open Access journal. This means that neither the readers nor the authors pay for its services. As a consequence, we cannot afford fees for reviewers or payments to the editors for the services to the journal. We are grateful to our universities for their support. The Pavol Jozef Šafárik University in Košice hosts the journal website as well as the email address and offers technical support. The University of Innsbruck pays for a student assistant giving editorial support. In addition, the Slovak Association for the Study of English provides the funding for assigning a doi to each article published in our journal.

In order to maintain a high standard of quality for the articles we publish, we have to appeal to reviewers. Like many other journals, also many that charge for subscriptions, we do not pay for reviews. We hope that they find the opportunity to read about potentially interesting ideas at an early stage and the feeling to make an essential contribution to the development of the field a sufficient reward for the efforts. Once a year, in the July issue, we publish a list of names with the colleagues who helped us by reviewing a paper we received. On request the journal can also issue a certificate.

We are grateful to the reviewers who support our journal and we are continuously looking for ways to make their efforts more meaningful and less burdensome. Last year we introduced a review form. This year, we piloted a preliminary evaluation step. All submissions are first evaluated by one of the editors. The results are discussed in an editorial meeting. Papers for which we judge that they would be unlikely to be accepted are rejected at this stage. Other papers go through our usual peer review process. In this way, the quality of the papers received by reviewers should be better. For authors, the additional step should not lead to a longer processing period. For papers rejected at this stage, the advantage is that they get an earlier decision.

In the twelve months ending 30 November, we received 87 manuscripts for our regular issues. Of these, 40 were not sent out for review and two were withdrawn. The others are in different stages of the reviewing process. In addition, we published a special issue on empirical translation and interpreting studies in September. It was guest-edited by Silvana Deilen and Ekatarina Lapshinova-Koltunski. For special issues, our policy is that they appear in addition to the two regular issues we produce in June and in December.

In this issue, you will find six articles. We hope you will enjoy reading them. We invite authors to submit their manuscripts through the journal's email address and we invite scholars willing to review manuscripts to contact us.

The editors

Pius ten Hacken

Renáta Panocová

Laura Giacomini

E-mail: skase-jti@upjs.sk

Proposing a Tentative Revision Hypothesis for Sacred Texts: The Holy Qur'an's English Translation and Revision in Focus

Mahmoud Afrouz, University of Isfahan

Abstract

The present study analyzes a translation of the Holy Qur'an and its revision to take a step towards formulating a tentative revision hypothesis. Muhammad Ali's (1917) translation and its edited version by Aziz (2010) are the corpus of the study. The major principle of the revision hypothesis was found to be that the translation of a sacred-text is less target-oriented than its edited-version. This revision hypothesis is not formulated in absolute terms. Other researchers can test the validity of its principles by focusing on specific genres (i.e. religious texts, children's literature, etc.).

Keywords: *the Holy Qur'an; sacred texts; the revision hypothesis; Maulana Muhammad Ali (1917); Zahid Aziz (2010)*

1. Introduction

The passage of time may cause cultures, languages and translations to experience some changes. In the case of translations, such change sometimes appears in the form of a revised (self-)edition of the translation or the production of (re)translations by other translators. Retranslation refers to the process of translating a source text (ST) that has previously been rendered into the same target language (TL). Retranslation, as a product, “denotes a second or later translation of a single ST into the same” TL (Koskinen & Paloposki 2010: 294). Accordingly, retranslators are those who produce retranslations.

Although retranslations may sometimes “respond to a lack in the initial translation,” they “exist not because earlier translations are defective but because they are the necessary condition for the survival of the canonical source text” (Massardier-Kenney 2015: 73–81). On the basis of Berman's Retranslation Hypothesis, “later translations tend to be closer to the source text” (Chesterman 2004: 8). Editors are those who just edit a target-text, and self-editors denote those translators who commit self-retranslations.

While “corpus-based studies of translation use published texts as the basis for their corpus” (Bisiada 2018: 1), almost all of them just concentrate on the original translations or their edited versions. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no study has yet been conducted to compare the original translation with its edited version to propose or even pave the way for formulating a tentative hypothesis for the revised editions. The current study aims at analyzing a translation and edition of a sacred text: the Holy Qur'an. The corpus is introduced comprehensively in the methodology section.

Edited versions (or revisions) of published translations always appear after the original translation. They share this feature with retranslations. The question that may arise here is whether revisions and retranslations share the same hypothesis or not? In other words, do we need to formulate a separate hypothesis for revisions? Can we confidently assert that revised versions are closer to the STs (i.e. are more ST oriented) than the original translations (as is the case for retranslations)? The present paper aims to find answers to these questions.

2. Literature review

In Section 2.1, previous works on the Holy Qur'an's translations are reviewed. In the two sections after that, some studies on the issue of the retranslation hypothesis and revision hypothesis (RH) are reviewed.

2.1. Previous works on the Holy Qur'an's translations

Al-Salem (2008) analyzed procedures employed in rendering metonymies in five English translations of the Holy Qur'an: Pickthall (1930/1992), Arberry (1955/1996), Al-Hilali and Khan (1996), Ghali (1998) and Bewley and Bewley (1999). He found the following methods used by translators: "translation into a metaphor;" "translation into the same metonymy;" "translation into the same metonymy with the intended meaning in parentheses;" "reduction of metonymy to its sense only;" "assuming that there isn't a metonymy," and "translation into another metonymy" (196). The findings indicated that translators showed great tendencies towards rendering Arabic metonymical expressions into the same metonymy in English. All translators were chosen from the 20th century. The researcher could have selected a number of translations carried out in the 19th and the 21st century to investigate whether the time span really affects the type of strategies selected by translators and the overall tendencies of translators towards the target- or the source-language. If Al-Salem (2008) had done so, he could have also tested the RH in the context of religious texts.

Pirnajmuddin & Zamani's (2012) study investigated English translations of Qur'anic culture-bound terms by Al-Hilali and Muhsin Khan (1995), Shakir (1980), Arberry (1955), Yusuf Ali (1934), and Pickthall (1930). Concentrating solely on "[p]ractical laws of religion (Furū al-Dīn)," they found that "literal translation" is the most frequent and the most proper procedure in rendering culture-bound terms (CBTs) (71). The researchers could have examined the general tendencies of the retranslators and tested the RH.

Naseri and Shiravi Khoozani's (2015) paper focused on four Persian translations of the Qur'an by Moezzi (1993), Sharany (1995), Dehlavi (1996) and Mesbah-zadeh (2001). The researchers concentrated on a set of criteria for comparing the translations: "accuracy" of equivalents, "consistency and cohesion," "eloquence," the morphological and stylistic issues, etc. (137). Based on their findings, once the first two translations (i.e. Moezzi 1993 and Sharany 1995) are compared, it would be revealed that the later one is slightly more source-oriented, and, when the translations of Dehlavi (1996) and Mesbah-zadeh (2001) are compared, it would be found that the later translation is more source-oriented than the earlier rendition. Therefore, as far as the RH is concerned, Naseri and Shiravi Khoozani's (2015) paper neither confirms nor disproves the hypothesis.

Mohammadi and Valavi's (2019) paper examined metonymies in three ancient translations of the Holy Qur'an by Tabari (13th century), Meybodi (15th century) and Abul-Futouh Razi (15th century). The researchers found that "Tabari and Abul-Futouh Razi" mainly used "literal translation," while "Meybodi has had the most content-wise translation in rendering metonymy" (17). If Tabari's translation is merely compared with Meybodi's, it can be pointed out that the RH is disproved since the earlier translation was more source-oriented than the later one. However, the study could have obtained more conclusive results in terms of the RH if more recent (re-)translations had been also taken into consideration.

2.2. Previous works on the retranslation hypothesis

Paloposki & Koskinen (2004) took the retranslation hypothesis into consideration and compared “its claims with data from Finnish first translations and retranslations” (27). Based on their findings, “while there are numerous (re)translations that fit in the RH schema, there also exist several counter-examples where the schema is turned the other way round, and also cases where the whole issue of domestication/assimilation versus foreignization/source-text orientation is irrelevant” (36). Paloposki & Koskinen (2004: 36) contended that there were “no inherent qualities in the process of retranslating that would dictate a move from domesticating strategies towards more foreignizing strategies”. The researcher, finally, pointed out that they did not find enough support for the RH.

El Damanhoury (2015) analyzed three Japanese translations of the Holy Quran and tested the applicability of the RH in this respect. Translators included Izutsu (1964), Mita (1972) and Nakata (2014). Based on the results of her study, Izutsu employed foreignizing strategies in 60%, Mita in 62% and Nakata in 70% of the cases (56-59). The earliest translation (by Izutsu in 1964) was found by the researcher to be “the most domesticating” one, “followed by Mita (1972) and lastly Nakata (2014)” (56–59). The findings of El Damanhoury’s (2015) study were in line with the basic principles of the RH.

Kitanovska-Kimovska (2017) attempted to test the RH by analyzing three Macedonian translations of Shakespeare’s *Hamlet*. The study was on the basis of a comparison between the source text (ST) and the target texts (TTs) by Shopov (1960), Gjuzel (1989), and Mihajlovski (2008) “in terms of the number of lexical inventions, i.e. the number of words derived through the processes of conversion and compounding” (201). The earliest translations, both direct and indirect one, were found to be more “target-oriented, while the second direct translation” was “more source-oriented” (210). The researcher confirmed the RH in her study.

Oyali’s (2018) study investigated the validity of the RH “in representations of certain Biblical concepts in the translations of the Bible into Igbo” and his findings proved that “most of the borrowings in the first translation are de-borrowed in the retranslations” (84). Analyzing five translations of the Bible, he finally concluded that “the opposite” of the retranslation hypothesis “is true” in this case since “later translations” were found to be “more target culture oriented than earlier translations” (97).

The findings of El Damanhoury’s (2015) thesis and Oyali’s (2018) paper were in sharp contrast: one confirmed the RH and the other totally disproved it. It should, however, be noticed that while the genre of the two studies was the same (i.e. sacred texts), the corpora studied by the two researchers were not the same. Moreover, the source- and the target-languages were not the same in the two works. Overall, such factors might play a role in (dis)proving the RH. Prospective researchers can work on such an issue, but what is significant for us, in the present study, is that there are at least a few works dealing with the issue of the retranslation hypothesis in religious texts. But no one, as far as the researchers know, has yet attempted to take a step towards formulating the RH. Therefore, the present study is conducted to fill the research gap.

2.3. Previous works on revision hypothesis

All works conducted so far have generally focused on translations of the Holy Qur'an and almost none of them took the issue of edited versions into account. Only the study carried out by Afrouz (2021) straightforwardly dealt with RH. But it needs to be clarified that his work focused on "self-revision". Afrouz (2021) found that subsequent revisions made by a translator were more accurate and more natural than the first translation produced by the same translator. However, Afrouz's (2021) paper concentrated on self-revisions and modern Persian literature, but the current study worked on a translation of the Holy Qur'an as a classical Arabic literary-religious text and its revision (made by a person other than translator himself). Such a study has never been conducted by any other researcher.

From among numerous English translations of the Holy Qur'an by individual translators (e.g. Sale 1734; Muhammad Ali 1917; Pickthall 1930; Yusuf Ali 1934; Arberry 1955; Shakir 1980; Irving 1985; Nikayin 2000; Saffarzadeh 2001; Abdel-Haleem 2005; Starkovsky 2005) or groups of translators (e.g. Yuksel et al. 2007; Royal Aal al-Bayt Institute for Islamic Thought 2008; The Monotheist Group 2012), only the one by Muhammad Ali (1917) was selected because it was revised by Zahid Aziz in 2010.

3. Method

The current study is analytical-comparative qualitative research exploring the potential relationship between religious translations and their edited versions. The sacred literary text selected in this study is the Muslims' greatest religious Book the Holy Qur'an, originally translated by Muhammad Ali (1917/1951) and edited by Aziz (2010). The following steps were taken to carry out the study:

1. It was attempted to find a sacred literary text with its original translation and its latest revision.
2. The translated version was linguistically compared with its revised version to detect the changes applied by the reviser.
3. The features of the revised version were analyzed.
4. On the basis of the findings and data analysis, a tentative hypothesis concerning revised versions of sacred texts was suggested.

4. Results and discussion

The issue of RH is first discussed in terms of classical literary texts and then is dealt with in the context of sacred literary texts. The most conspicuous changes applied by the editor was the exclusion of the ST which reduced the number of pages from 1388 to 923—a 20 percent reduction in hardcopy versions. It may make the edited version appear much handier and reader friendly. Moreover, while the electronic version of the original translation is about 80 megabytes, the edited version is less than four megabytes. Although both of these changes may, at first sight, seem superficial, they can potentially influence the accessibility of the edited version to the TT audience.

Other changes applied by Aziz are discussed here by referring to some tangible evidence from the corpus. It is noteworthy that the changes mentioned here were majorly found to be consistent throughout the whole revision.

1. Replacing the second person singular form *thou* and *thee* by *you*:

ST	صِرَاطَ الَّذِينَ أَنْعَمْتَ عَلَيْهِمْ غَيْرِ الْمَغْضُوبِ عَلَيْهِمْ وَلَا الضَّالِّينَ {الفاطحة/7}
TT	The path of those upon whom Thou hast bestowed favours, Not those upon whom wrath is brought down, nor those who go astray. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 6–7)
RTT	The path of those upon whom You have bestowed favours, Not those upon whom wrath is brought down, nor those who go astray. (Aziz 2010: 1)

As can be seen, the subject pronoun *Thou* is changed into *You*. This modernization has also occurred in alteration of *hast* as *have*. Consider the following instance which contains further changes:

2. Modernizing antiquated endings to English verbs:

ST	قَالُوا سُبْحَانَكَ لَا عِلْمَ لَنَا إِلَّا مَا عَلَّمْتَنَا إِنَّكَ أَنْتَ الْعَلِيمُ الْحَكِيمُ {البقرة/32}
TT	They said: Glory be to Thee! we have no knowledge but that which Thou hast taught us; surely Thou art the Knowing, the Wise. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 24)
RTT	They said: Glory be to You! we have no knowledge but what You have taught us. Surely You are the Knowing, the Wise. (Aziz 2010: 9)

Besides modernizing the pronouns *Thee* and *Thou*, the (auxiliary) verbs have also experienced such a change: *hast* vs. *has*; *art* vs. *are*. In the same line, the more traditional construction *that which...* is replaced by *what....* Additionally, the sentences which had been partially separated by a semicolon are now totally separated by a period. It may presumably imply that the revised version shows stronger tendency towards simplification via separating complex sentences. Further evidence of such changes will be presented as follows:

3. Replacing the second person singular form *thy* by *your*:

ST	وَإِذْ قَالَ رَبُّكَ لِلْمَلَائِكَةِ إِنِّي جَاعِلٌ فِي الْأَرْضِ خَلِيفَةً قَالُوا أَتَجْعَلُ فِيهَا مَنْ يُفْسِدُ فِيهَا وَيَسْفِكُ الدِّمَاءَ وَنَحْنُ نُسَبِّحُ بِحَمْدِكَ وَنُقَدِّسُ لَكَ قَالَ إِنِّي أَعْلَمُ مَا لَا تَعْلَمُونَ {البقرة/30}
TT	And when <i>your</i> Lord said to the angels, I am going to place in the <i>earth</i> one who shall rule (in it), they said: What! Wilt Thou place in it such as make mischief in it and shed blood, and we celebrate Thy praise and extol Thy holiness. He said: Surely I know what you do not know. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 23)
RTT	And when <i>your</i> Lord said to the angels, I am going to place a ruler in the earth, they said: Will You place in it such as make mischief in it and shed blood? And we celebrate Your praise and extol Your holiness. He said: Surely I know what you do not know. (Aziz 2010: 8–9)

Muhammad Ali has been inconsistent in using the archaic forms like *thou/thee* and *thy*. As the instance above clearly demonstrates, both *your* and *thy* are present in his translation, while in the edited version by Aziz, just a single form is used: *your*. Therefore, whereas expressions like *Wilt Thou*, *Thy praise*, and *Thy holiness* are modernized, *your Lord* is left unchanged since it had been modernized in the original translation. It seems that Muhammad

Ali has only used archaic forms to refer to God. Whatever the case may be, his behavior can be considered as a sort of stylistic inconsistency.

Furthermore, the sentences separated by a comma (i.e. ...*shed blood*, and *we...*) are now totally separated by a question mark (i.e. ...*shed blood?* and *we...*). It shows the meticulousness and diligence of the editor in the accurate use of punctuation marks. This would promote the readability and fluency of the TT. In the same line, Aziz has replaced the long and rather complex clause *to place in the earth one who shall rule (in it)* by *to place a ruler in the earth*. Aziz has also removed the unnecessary term *What!* to observe the brevity of his revised edition.

Take the last part of the above verse into consideration: *Surely I know what you do not know*. Interestingly, Muhammad Ali in his 1951's edition has employed structures like *they see not* and *you know not* while he has used simpler constructions such as *they do not see* and *you do not know* in his original 1917's version. Aziz (2010), as could evidently be seen, has restored the original translation's style.

4. Replacing more traditional phrases by modern ones:

ST	وَالَّذِينَ يُؤْمِنُونَ بِمَا أُنزِلَ إِلَيْكَ وَمَا أُنزِلَ مِنْ قَبْلِكَ وَبِالْآخِرَةِ هُمْ يُوقِنُونَ {البقرة/4}
TT	And who believe in that which has been revealed to <i>you</i> and what was revealed before <i>you</i> , and they are sure of the hereafter. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 13)
RTT	And who believe in what has been revealed to <i>you</i> and what was revealed before <i>you</i> , and of the Hereafter they are sure. (Aziz 2010: 4)

As was explained in previous instances, the phrase *that which* is replaced by *what*. There were other alterations in the revised version. Firstly, the *Hereafter*, as a religious-bound term, is capitalized by the editor to distinguish it from ordinary terms. Secondly, in rendering the Arabic clause *بِالْآخِرَةِ هُمْ يُوقِنُونَ* /*bel ākherate hom jūqenūn*/, the original translation's word-order is more target-oriented than the edited version. The edited version follows the Arabic word-order and is, therefore, structurally more source-oriented. It should, nonetheless, be remembered that this event has been an exception, and in other cases, the edited version has been much more target-oriented than the original translation.

5. Replacing more formal and difficult lexical items by everyday words:

ST	أَتَأْمُرُونَ النَّاسَ بِالْبِرِّ وَتَنْسَوْنَ أَنْفُسَكُمْ وَأَنْتُمْ تَتْلُونَ الْكِتَابَ أَفَلَا تَعْقِلُونَ {البقرة/44}
TT	What! do you enjoin men to be good and neglect your own souls while you read the Book? Have you then no sense? (Muhammad Ali 1917: 29)
RTT	Do you tell people to be good and neglect your own souls while you read the Book? Have you then no sense? (Aziz 2010: 12)

In the above instance, the difficult word *enjoin* in the original translation is replaced by everyday verb *tell*. Other changes in the revised version include:

- Removal of the word *What!*—which is used typically by Muhammad Ali wherever the Arabic item *أ* /*a*/ is used at the beginning of a sentence to make interrogative constructions
- Replacement of the word *men* with *people*—which may display the tendency of the editor to employ more neutral gender-free words

- Breaking up longer sentences into shorter independent sentences to boost the flow of constructions (usually by replacing comma, colon or semicolon with question mark, exclamation mark, period, etc.)

6. Avoiding prolixity and showing more tendencies towards brevity:

ST	وَاتَّقُوا يَوْمًا لَا تَجْزِي نَفْسٌ عَنْ نَفْسٍ شَيْئًا وَلَا يُقْبَلُ مِنْهَا شَفَاعَةٌ وَلَا يُؤْخَذُ مِنْهَا عَدْلٌ وَلَا هُمْ يُنصَرُونَ {البقرة/48}
TT	And be on your guard against a day when one soul shall not avail another in the least, neither shall intercession on its behalf be accepted, nor shall any compensation be taken from it, nor shall they be helped. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 30)
RTT	And guard yourselves against a day when no soul will avail another in the least, neither will intercession be accepted on its behalf, nor will compensation be taken from it, nor will they be helped. (Aziz 2010: 12)

Other changes in the revised version include replacing the less frequently used modal *shall* by *will* and changing the word order (i.e. *on its behalf*) to promote the flow of the sentence.

7. Replacing complex constructions by more simplified ones:

ST	فَمِنْهُمْ مَنْ آمَنَ بِهِ وَمِنْهُمْ مَنْ صَدَّ عَنْهُ وَكَفَىٰ بِجَهَنَّمَ سَعِيرًا {النساء/55}
TT	So of them is he who believes in him, and of them is he who turns away from him, and hell is sufficient to burn. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 217)
RTT	So some of them believe in him, and some of them turn away from him. And Hell is sufficient to burn. (Aziz 2010: 117–18)

The expression *منهم من* /*menhom man*/, originally rendered as *of them is he who*, is simplified as *some of them*. Moreover, the last clause in the Arabic text, being a dependent segment in the original translation, is broken up as an independent sentence in the edited version. The religious-bound term *Hell* is also capitalized.

8. Replacing literary (and old-fashioned) words by more everyday (modern) ones:

ST	قَالَ هِيَ رَأَوْنَتِي عَنْ نَفْسِي وَشَهِدَ شَاهِدٌ مِّنْ أَهْلِهَا إِنْ كَانَ قَمِيصُهُ قُدًّا مِنْ قَبْلِ فَصَدَقَتْ وَهُوَ مِنَ الْكَاذِبِينَ {يوسف/26} وَإِنْ كَانَ قَمِيصُهُ قُدًّا مِنْ دُبُرٍ فَكَذَبَتْ وَهُوَ مِنَ الصَّادِقِينَ {يوسف/27}
TT	He said: She sought to make me yield (to her); and a witness of her own family bore witness: If his shirt is rent from front, she speaks the truth and he is one of the liars. And if his shirt is rent from behind, she tells a lie and he is one of the truthful. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 482)
RTT	He said: She sought to seduce me. And a witness of her own family bore witness: If his shirt is torn in front, she speaks the truth and he is a liar. And if his shirt is torn from behind, she tells a lie and he is truthful. (Aziz 2010: 289)

The word *rend* in Muhammad Ali's translation is a literary old-fashioned verb. It is replaced with *tear* in Aziz's revision. Prolixity in expressions like *make me yield (to her)*, *one of the liars* and *one of the truthful* are respectively replaced with *seduce*, *a liar*, and *truthful*. It should be reminded that the original translation is closer to the ST since, for instance, the two parallel-structured expressions *هُوَ مِنَ الْكَاذِبِينَ* /*howa menal kazebīn*/ and *هُوَ مِنَ الصَّادِقِينَ* /*howa menal ṣādeqīn*/ are literally rendered in the original translation as *he is one of the liars* and *he is one of the truthful*, respectively, while they were condensed in the edited version as *he is a liar* and *he is truthful*, respectively.

9. Replacing literary constructions with everyday ones:

ST	وَقَالُوا قُلُوبُنَا غُلْفٌ بَلْ لَعَنَهُمُ اللَّهُ بِكُفْرِهِمْ فَقَلِيلًا مَّا يُؤْمِنُونَ {البقرة/88}
TT	And they say: Our hearts are securely <i>covered</i> . Nay, Allah has cursed them on account of their unbelief; so little it is that they believe. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 47)
RTT	And they say: Our hearts are securely covered. No, Allah has cursed them on account of their unbelief; so it is little that they believe. (Aziz 2010: 20)

Sometimes changing some lexical items and word-order can result in the change of literary style into normal one. Take, for instance, the alteration of *Nay* and *little it is* into *No* and *it is little*, respectively. It should also be remembered that although Muhammad Ali (1917) has typically rendered the word *بَلْ/bal/* as *nay*, he has not been consistent and, in some verses, the same word *بَلْ/bal/* had been translated as *yet*, *rather*, or *but*.

10. Observing the (more creative and accurate) use of punctuation marks:

ST	قَالُوا إِنَّمَا أَنْتَ مِنَ الْمُسَحَّرِينَ {الشعراء/153} مَا أَنْتَ إِلَّا بَشَرٌ مِّثْلُنَا فَأْتِ بَآيَةٍ إِنْ كُنْتَ مِنَ الصَّادِقِينَ {الشعراء/154}
TT	They said: <i>You are</i> only of the deluded ones: <i>You are</i> naught but a mortal like ourselves: so bring a sign if <i>you are</i> one of the truthful. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 736)
RTT	They said: You are only a deluded person. <i>You are</i> nothing but a mortal like ourselves—so bring a sign if <i>you are</i> truthful. (Aziz 2010: 463)

While three successive colons are used in the translation, the editor has replaced two of them with a period and a dash. Aziz has accurately used a full stop at the end of the first verse, while Muhammad Ali had employed a colon. Furthermore, the expressions *مِنَ الْمُسَحَّرِينَ/menal mosaharīn/* and *مِنَ الصَّادِقِينَ/menal šādeqīn/* are again rendered literally by Muhammad Ali as *of the deluded ones* and *of the truthful*, respectively, while they are reduced as *a deluded person* and *truthful*, correspondingly.

While the expression *إِلَّا بَشَرٌ/ellā basharon/* is translated originally as *naught but a mortal*, it is replaced by *nothing but a mortal*. Although Muhammad Ali (1917) has employed equivalents *naught* and *ought* in his rendition of some verses, he has been inconsistent in this respect since in other verses the same expressions were rendered using equivalents such as *nothing*, *anything*, *at all* and *in the least*. Compare the abovementioned instance with the following one.

11. Removing redundant expressions:

ST	لَا هِيَ قُلُوبُهُمْ وَأَسْرُوا النَّجْوَى الَّذِينَ ظَلَمُوا هَلْ هَذَا إِلَّا بَشَرٌ مِّثْلُكُمْ أَفَتَأْتُونَ السَّجَرَ وَأَنْتُمْ تَبْصُرُونَ {الأنبياء/3}
TT	Their hearts trifling; and those who are unjust counsel together in secret: He is nothing but a mortal like yourselves; what! will you then yield to enchantment while you see? (Muhammad Ali 1917: 643)
RTT	their hearts trifling. And they—the wrongdoers—counsel in secret: He is nothing but a mortal like yourselves; will you then yield to enchantment while you see? (Aziz 2010: 398)

The redundant *what!* and *together* is removed in the edited version. Again, as can be seen, here the same expression *إِلَّا بَشَرٌ/ellā basharon/* appears identically in both the translation and the edition: *nothing but a mortal*. In general, the edited version was detected to be more consistent in terms of employing equivalents.

Furthermore, while the Arabic expression *الَّذِينَ ظَلَمُوا*/*al lazina zalamū*/ is literally translated as *those who are unjust*, it appears more concise in the edited version: *the wrongdoers*. Therefore, again, the original translation was more source-text oriented than the edition. It should also be reminded that Muhammad Ali has again been less consistent than Aziz in terms of equivalent choice since the words *wrongdoer*, *unjust* and *iniquitous* have been interchangeably used in various verses. Take the following instances into consideration:

ST1	وَلَقَدْ جَاءَكُمْ مُوسَىٰ بِالْبَيِّنَاتِ ثُمَّ اتَّخَذْتُمُ الْعِجْلَ مِن بَعْدِهِ وَأَنْتُمْ ظَالِمُونَ {البقرة/92}
TT	And most certainly Moses came to you with clear arguments, then you took the calf (for a god) <i>in his absence</i> and you were unjust. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 48)
RTT	And Moses indeed came to you with clear arguments, then you took the calf (for a god) in his absence and you were wrongdoers. (Aziz 2010: 21)
ST2	وَكَذَٰلِكَ نُوَلِّي بَعْضَ الظَّالِمِينَ بَعْضًا بِمَا كَانُوا يَكْسِبُونَ {الأنعام/129}
TT	And thus do We make some of the iniquitous to befriend others on account of what they earned. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 183)
RTT	And thus do We make some of the wrongdoers to befriend others on account of what they earn. (Aziz 2010: 315)

While the synonymous terms *الظالمون*/*zālemūn*/in ST1 and *الظالمين*/*zālemīn*/ in ST2 are respectively rendered by Muhammad Ali as *unjust* and *iniquitous*, Aziz has consistently chosen *wrongdoers* in all cases. Aziz has also been more considerate of the TT grammatical rules in terms of verb-tenses—*do*, *make*, and *earn* are all simple present.

12. Condensing the footnotes and even removing them in some cases:

ST	وَظَلَّلْنَا عَلَيْكُمُ الْغَمَامَ وَأَنْزَلْنَا عَلَيْكُمُ الْمَنَّاءَ وَالسَّلْوَىٰ كُلُوا مِن طَيِّبَاتِ مَا رَزَقْنَاكُمْ وَمَا ظَلَمُونَا وَلَكِن كَانُوا أَنفُسَهُمْ يَظْلِمُونَ {البقرة/57}
TT	And We made the clouds to give shade over you* and We sent to you manna and quails*: Eat of the good things that We have given you; and they did not do Us any harm, but they made their own souls suffer the loss. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 33)
RTT	And We made the clouds to give shade over you and We sent to you manna and quails. Eat of the good things that We have given you. And they did Us no harm, but they wronged their own souls. (Aziz 2010: 13–14)

Asterisks are added to the above TT by the researcher to show where Muhammad Ali has marked for providing footnotes. As can be seen, both footnotes have been removed in the edited version. Other changes include replacing a full stop by a colon/semicolon; simplifying the expression *they did not do Us any harm as they did Us no harm*; and abridging the expression *they made [...] suffer the loss by they wronged*.

13. Substituting longer expressions with shorter ones:

ST	وَإِذِ اسْتَسْقَىٰ مُوسَىٰ لِقَوْمِهِ فَقُلْنَا اضْرِبْ بِعَصَاكَ الْحَجَرَ فَانْفَجَرَتْ مِنْهُ اثْنَا عَشَرَ عَيْنًا قَدْ عَلِمَ كُلُّ أُنَاسٍ مَّشْرِبَهُمْ كُلُوا وَاشْرَبُوا مِن رِّزْقِ اللَّهِ وَلَا تَعْتُوا فِي الْأَرْضِ مُفْسِدِينَ {البقرة/60}
TT	And when Moses prayed for water for his people, We said: Seek with <i>your staff</i> a way into the mountain. So there flowed from it twelve springs; each tribe knew its drinking-place: Eat and drink of the provisions of Allah, and do not act corruptly in the land, making mischief. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 34)

RTT	And when Moses prayed for water for his people, We said: March on to the rock with <i>your</i> staff. So twelve springs flowed from it. Each tribe knew their drinking-place. Eat and drink of the provisions of Allah, and do not act corruptly, making mischief in the land. (Aziz 2010: 14)
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Longer and more complex expressions in the original translation are substituted with simpler and more succinct constructions. For instance, *Seek with your staff a way into the mountain* and *So there flowed from it twelve springs* are revised as *March on to the rock with your staff* and *So twelve springs flowed from it*, respectively. The original is structurally closer to the ST. Furthermore, consider the sentence *وَلَا تَعْتُوا فِي الْأَرْضِ مُفْسِدِينَ* /*wa lā tathū felarṣ mofsedīn*/ which is literally rendered by Muhammad Ali as *and do not act corruptly in the land, making mischief*. It is then revised by Aziz and has become more adapted to the target language grammatical rules: *do not act corruptly, making mischief in the land*.

14. Capitalizing religious-bound terms:

ST	كُلُّ نَفْسٍ ذَائِقَةُ الْمَوْتِ وَإِنَّمَا تُوَفَّوْنَ أَجُورَكُمْ يَوْمَ الْقِيَامَةِ فَمَنْ زُحِرَ عَنِ النَّارِ وَأُدْخِلَ الْجَنَّةَ فَقَدْ فَازَ وَمَا الْحَيَاةُ الدُّنْيَا إِلَّا مَتَاعُ الْغُرُورِ {آل عمران/185}
TT	Every soul shall taste of death, and you shall only be paid fully your reward on the resurrection day; then whoever is removed far away from the fire and is made to enter the garden, he indeed has attained the object; and the life of this world is nothing but a provision of vanities. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 192)
RTT	Every soul must taste of death. And you will be paid your reward fully only on the day of Resurrection. Then whoever is removed far from the Fire and is made to enter the Garden, he indeed attains the object. And the life of this world is nothing but a provision of vanities. (Aziz 2010: 101)

The two religious-bound terms *الْقِيَامَةِ* /*alqiāmat*/ ('Resurrection') and *النَّار* /*alnār*/ ('Fire'/'Hell'), *الْجَنَّة* /*aljannat*/ ('Garden'/'Paradise') are capitalized in the revised edition. Moreover, the verse is divided into three separate sentences by Aziz and is made more target-reader friendly. The less frequently used *shall* is also replaced by *must* and *will*.

15. Replacing specialized terms with more general ones:

ST	وَمَنْ يَعْمَلْ مِنَ الصَّالِحَاتِ مِنْ ذَكَرٍ أَوْ أُنْثَىٰ وَهُوَ مُؤْمِنٌ فَأُولَٰئِكَ يَدْخُلُونَ الْجَنَّةَ وَلَا يُظْلَمُونَ نَبِيًّا {النساء/124}
TT	And whoever does good deeds, whether male or female, and he (or she) is a believer—these shall enter the garden, and they shall not be dealt with a jot unjustly. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 235)
RTT	And whoever does good deeds, whether male or female, and is a believer—these will enter the Garden, and they will not be dealt with unjustly in the least. (Aziz 2010: 129)

The phrase *a jot* is replaced by *in the least*, which is more general and understandable for the TT readers. In this case, neutralization of specialized terms is a target-oriented behavior on the part of the editor. Other changes include the capitalization of the religious-bound term *Garden*, the removal of the redundant *he (or she)*, and the replacement of the less frequently used modal *shall* with *will*.

16. Removing brackets:

ST	وَاتذَكُرُوا اللَّهَ فِي أَيَّامٍ مَّعْدُودَاتٍ فَمَنْ تَعَجَّلَ فِي يَوْمَيْنِ فَلَا إِثْمَ عَلَيْهِ وَمَنْ تَأَخَّرَ فَلَا إِثْمَ عَلَيْهِ لِمَنِ اتَّقَى وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ وَاعْلَمُوا أَنَّكُمْ إِلَيْهِ تُحْشَرُونَ {البقرة/203}
TT	And laud Allah during the numbered days; then whoever hastens off in two days, there is no blame on him, and whoever remains behind, there is no blame on him, (this is) for him who guards (against evil), and be careful (of your duty) to Allah, and know that you shall be gathered together to Him. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 93)
RTT	And remember Allah during the appointed days. Then whoever hastens off in two days, it is no sin for him; and whoever stays behind, it is no sin for him, for one who keeps his duty. And keep your duty to Allah, and know that you will be gathered together to Him. (Aziz 2010: 47)

As can be seen, Aziz has removed brackets in his edited version. Since numerous uses of brackets can distract the attention of the target readers, such elimination can be thought of as an action towards making the text more target-oriented by the editor. Moreover, while Muhammad Ali has selected the less accurate equivalents *laud*, *numbered*, and *sin* for *تذكروا* /*edhkorū*/, *معدودات* /*ma'dūdāt*/, and *إثم* /*ithm*/, respectively, Aziz has replaced them with the more precise and most common equivalents *remember*, *appointed*, and *sin*, respectively. Furthermore, in translating this verse, Muhammad Ali has selected the equivalent *remain*; however, he has inconsistently opted for *stay*, or even the less familiar word *tarry*, in other cases. Other instances of (in)consistencies can be seen in the following example.

17. Observing consistency in equivalent-choice:

ST	فَلَمَّا فَصَلَ طَالُوتُ بِالْجُنُودِ قَالَ إِنَّ اللَّهَ مُبْتَلِيكُمْ بِنَهَرٍ فَمَنْ شَرِبَ مِنْهُ فَلَيْسَ مِنِّي وَمَنْ لَمْ يَطْعَمْهُ فَإِنَّهُ مِنِّي إِلَّا مَنْ اعْتَرَفَ بِغُرْفَةٍ يَدِيهِ فَشَرِبُوا مِنْهُ إِلَّا قَلِيلًا مِنْهُمْ فَلَمَّا جَاوَزَهُ هُوَ وَالَّذِينَ آمَنُوا مَعَهُ قَالُوا لَا طَاقَةَ لَنَا الْيَوْمَ بِجَالُوتَ وَجُنُودِهِ قَالَ الَّذِينَ يَظُنُّونَ أَنَّهُمْ مُلَاقُوا اللَّهِ كَمْ مِنْ فِئَةٍ قَلِيلَةٍ غَلَبَتْ فِئَةً كَثِيرَةً بِإِذْنِ اللَّهِ وَاللَّهُ مَعَ الصَّابِرِينَ {البقرة/249}
TT	So when Saul departed with the forces, he said: Surely Allah will try you with a river; whoever then drinks from it, he is not of me, and whoever does not taste of it, he is surely of me, except he who takes with his hand as much of it as fills the hand, but with the exception of a few of them they drank from it. So when he had crossed it, he and those who believed with him, they said: We have to-day no power against Goliath and his forces. Those who were sure that they would meet their Lord said: How often has a small party overcome a numerous host by Allah's permission, and Allah is with the patient. (Muhammad Ali 1917: 116–17)
RTT	So when Saul set out with the forces, he said: Surely Allah will try you with a river. Whoever drinks from it, he is not of me, and whoever does not taste it, he is surely of me, except he who takes a handful with his hand. But they drank of it except a few of them. So when he had crossed it, he and those who believed with him, they said: We have today no power against Goliath and his forces. Those who were sure that they would meet their Lord said: How often has a small group overcome a numerous army by Allah's permission! And Allah is with the steadfast. (Aziz 2010: 60)

Although Muhammad Ali (1917) has used the less common equivalent *host*, he has selected the more familiar equivalents such as *force*, and *army* in other cases. In general, as far as equivalent choice is concerned, he was found to be more inconsistent than his editor. Other changes include:

- Removal of some words: for instance, *then* in *whoever then drinks*, or *of* in *taste of it*. It should be remembered that Muhammad Ali's translation is close to the source-text since the word *then*, considered presumably unnecessary by the editor and consequently removed by him, is the equivalent for *ف*/*fa*/ appeared at the beginning of the expression *فَمَنْ شَرِبَ*/*fa man sharaba*/ (i.e. *then whoever drinks*).
- Replacement of formal words with more everyday ones: *departed/set out*.
- Breaking longer sentences into shorter ones: The original translation is made of three sentences, while the edited version includes six sentences.
- Substitution of longer complex constructions with simpler ones: For instance, *who takes with his hand as much of it as fills the hand* and *with the exception of a few of them they drank from it* are replaced respectively by *who takes a handful with his hand*, and *they drank of it except a few of them*.

5. Concluding remarks

As regards the Holy Qur'an as the sacred literary text, the editor has strived to "bring the language closer to the general readership" (Aziz 2010:1–2), presumably because he has considered that, compared to the 20th-century readership, 21st-century readers are less familiar with archaic terms and traditional literary style.

Altogether, as the changes applied by the editor revealed, the revised version of the Holy Qur'an was detected to have the following features:

- Replacing the less familiar equivalents with more familiar ones;
- Replacing more traditional (or formal) expressions by modern (everyday) words;
- Replacing *thou/thee* and *thy* by *you* and *your*, respectively;
- Modernizing old-fashioned constructions, words and antiquated endings to English verbs
- Replacing literary constructions with everyday ones;
- Simplifying complex constructions;
- Avoiding prolixity and observing brevity;
- Removing redundant expressions;
- Observing TL grammatical rules more meticulously;
- Manipulating footnotes: condensing or totally removing them;
- Manipulating brackets: reducing the number of them or totally removing them;
- Generalizing or neutralizing some specialized (or incomprehensible) equivalents;
- Observing consistency in equivalent choice;
- Capitalizing religious-bound terms referring to God, Paradise, Hell, the Hereafter, etc.

The aforementioned features of the revised edition of the sacred text can lead to the suggestion or pre-formulation of a new hypothesis, namely the RH. This is a tentative hypothesis which needs to be tested by other researchers working on other text-types and/or other language pairs. Concerning the religious texts, the major principle of the RH is that the translation of a sacred text is less target-oriented than its edited version. Therefore, the main principle of the RH stands in stark contrast to that of the retranslation hypothesis.

Attempting to update the translation of a religious book, a reviser, like Aziz, embarks on a nuanced process of modernization, simplification, streamlining, etc. This approach can be interpreted through various theoretical lenses, including Skopos theory and relevance theory, each shedding light on different dimensions of the reviser's work.

Skopos theory, which prioritizes the purpose of a revision or translation, helps explain the rationale behind Aziz's decisions. His focus on modernization and clarity indicates a goal aimed at enhancing the text's relevance for contemporary readership. By making the text accessible and understandable to a modern audience, Aziz ensures that the translation remains a source for guidance in faith, worship, and moral conduct. This emphasis on accessibility, inclusivity, and coherence aligns the translation closely with its intended purpose.

Relevance theory, on the other hand, posits that communication is most effective when it maximizes relevance for the audience (Gutt 2010). When applied to a religious text, this theory suggests that the reader's ability to understand, internalize, and practice the teachings is fundamentally shaped by the text's readability and comprehensibility. Aziz's efforts to simplify and modernize the translation make it more accessible, thereby facilitating deeper engagement with its message.

When it comes to the aims of modernization and simplification, it is important to note that updating the language and making the text easier to understand enhances the text's appeal to contemporary readers. These revisions help ensure that the sacred text resonates with a broader audience, even those who might find archaic language, outdated terminology, intricate theological concepts or overly complex expressions challenging.

Through this simplification, the reviser prioritizes clarity for the target audience, consciously avoiding convoluted language and superfluous details that could hinder understanding. This approach is in line with a Skopos that seeks to make the text accessible and engaging, particularly for those who may lack extensive background knowledge of the original text. By prioritizing an inclusive, clear translation, Aziz has seemingly attempted to ensure that the Holy Qur'an fulfills its role as a meaningful and relevant guide for diverse readers.

Aziz likely recognized that the purpose, or Skopos, of the Holy Qur'an might involve reaching a broad and diverse audience, necessitating a clear, straightforward language and a clear style. In fact, by applying Skopos theory, we can examine various crucial factors when analyzing the work of a reviser who modernizes a translation. In this case, Aziz's choice to modernize the language appears purpose-driven. This could entail enhancing accessibility and relevance for modern readers, incorporating contemporary language norms, or adapting to cultural shifts that have occurred since the original translation. The main goal of the revised translation would be to convey the original message in a way that connects with modern readers, preserves the ST's impact, and allows it to continue serving its role as a source of inspiration and guidance.

Indeed, modernization may target a particular audience demographic necessitating adjustments in language, style, and references to engage effectively. While the original translation by Muhammad Ali probably aimed at a scholarly audience, Aziz's revised version is likely targeted towards a broader, more inclusive readership. The language has been

simplified by Aziz to better meet the expectations and comprehension levels of the new target audience. The reviser's role when creating a modernized translation can be to ensure that the text fulfills its intended purpose in a contemporary setting, possibly as an educational resource. This could lead to alterations that put the reader's experience ahead of strict adherence to the structure or wording of the ST. Moreover, the reviser needs to take into account the cultural implications of the translation. Aziz's editing process modernizes the text by removing archaic terminology and outdated structures that could alienate contemporary readers, thus ensuring cultural relevance and sensitivity.

Even though Skopos theory accepts that translations can deviate from the original text, the reviser still has the responsibility to maintain the original's intent and message. In this study, Aziz's revision is a well-executed modernization since it strikes a balance between the need for contemporary language and style with fidelity to the main message of the Holy Qur'an.

According to the present study, Aziz most likely sought to produce a revision (or possibly, a new translation) that could serve a specific purpose for the target audience. This required changes in language, structure, and the format of some cultural references to ensure his revised text remains effective and relevant in a contemporary setting.

Regarding the aim of shortening or eliminating footnotes, it is important to note that in religious texts, footnotes may often serve to provide commentary, historical background, or theological interpretation. Excessive footnotes, however, can interrupt the reading process. Aziz's decision to utilize shorter footnotes or remove them altogether can be seen as an effort to prevent disrupting the flow of reading. Cutting down on the length or quantity of footnotes caters to an audience who prioritize smooth reading over scholarly intricacies. This implies that Aziz's objectives in the present study align with a purpose that values promoting engagement and comprehension rather than focusing on exhaustive detailed information. Additionally, Aziz's revisions might reflect a thoughtful consideration of the target audience's demands and expectations. Aziz most likely intended to reach a wider or less specialized readership; therefore, simplification and minimal footnoting has seemingly turned to be his strategic choices to ensure that his revision fulfills the intended goal. Aziz has also attempted to address cultural factors—recognizing that the target audience might lean towards succinctness and directness over lengthy explanations typical in more scholarly or intricate translations.

In brief, from the perspective of Skopos theory, Aziz's strategy of simplifying the translation and modifying the use of footnotes serves a specific purpose aimed at improving clarity, enhancing accessibility, and engagement for the intended readership. His decisions reflect how the revision process is closely linked to the function of the text, illustrating how translation and revision are intrinsically tied to their intended function and audiences.

When it comes to avoiding prolixity, it is important to keep in mind that reducing unnecessary complexity goes hand in hand with the core idea of relevance, since overly complicated language can distract from the main points and diminish reader interest. In the context of the Holy Qur'an, as a religious text, clarity is crucial for conveying sacred meaning and enhancing spiritual connection.

In the field of translation studies, discussions of equivalence often revolve around the extent to which a TT mirrors the ST's intended meaning and impact within the TL. Regarding consistency in equivalents, it is important to note that eliminating discrepancies in choosing equivalents contributes to a coherent and unified reading experience. When dealing with sacred texts, like the Holy Qur'an, consistency in equivalent choice is crucial for upholding theological integrity among varied readerships.

When it comes to capitalization of religious terms, it is important to recognize that capitalizing religious-specific terms or even common names hinting at such terms (e.g. *Garden*, *Fire*, etc.) often highlights their importance and distinction, reinforcing their significance in religious practice and theology. This choice enables readers to easily understand the religious significance of the text while navigating through it.

As far as gender neutrality is concerned, choosing to use non-gendered language is in line with contemporary understandings of accessibility and inclusivity in religious discourse. Additionally, this cultural sensitivity shows awareness of the evolving attitudes towards gender roles and portrayal of people in sacred texts. By using gender-neutral language, the reviser makes the text more inclusive, allowing a wider audience to feel represented and engaged with the scriptures. Aziz, as the reviser of this sacred text, has broadened the text's audience by avoiding gender-specific terms, making the revised text more inclusive and engaging for everyone.

In conclusion, Aziz's role as the reviser of Muhammad Ali's translation involves modernizing, simplifying, avoiding prolixity or eliminating verbosity to enhance the text's relevance and readability for contemporary readers. By drawing on ideas from relevance theory, functionalist approaches, and Skopos theory, we can appreciate the multifaceted objectives of such revisions in making religious texts resonate with contemporary readers while preserving doctrinal integrity. The Holy Qur'an aims at educating all people about Islamic principles and providing guidance to anyone, anywhere, at any time. Aziz has made an effort to make timeless spiritual truths accessible to contemporary readers, enabling them to understand and apply in their daily lives.

It may be stated that the researcher cannot assertively posit a hypothesis for revisions of sacred texts simply by investigating one single case study; however, this effort of the researcher is optimistically expected not to be taken into account as an unforgivable sin to suggest just a tentative RH to be validated by prospective researchers. Future researchers are encouraged to study more texts and more translations and their post editions to obtain more conclusive results. In fact, this RH is not formulated in absolute terms. The validity of its principles needs to be tested by other researchers by initially focusing on specific genres (i.e. religious texts, children's literature, etc.). Future studies can also deal with translations and revisions of the same text into languages other than English.

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Mahmoud Afrouz
Department of English
University of Isfahan
Email: m.afrouz@fgn.ui.ac.ir

Translating LOVE and BELOVED Metaphors: A Cogno-Cultural Analysis of *La Sombra del Viento* by Carlos Ruiz Zafón and its Arabic Translation

Aseel Zibin^{*§}, Renad Al-Momani^{*}, Areej Allawzi^{*}, and Dina Salman^{*}

^{*}University of Jordan, [§]Applied Science Private University

Abstract

This study explores metaphor translation through analyzing Muaweyah Abdel Majeed's rendition of La Sombra del Viento from Spanish to Arabic. Adopting a cogno-cultural framework developed by Mandelblit (1995) and Al-Zoubi et al. (2007) as well as Newmark's (1981) translation strategies, three metaphor mapping categories are examined: 1) metaphors of similar mapping conditions realized similarly; 2) metaphors of similar mapping conditions realized differently; and 3) metaphors of different mapping conditions. The results showed that the translator employed the strategy of direct image reproduction in the target language, preserving both conceptual and linguistic elements, exemplified in the first mapping category. The second category utilizes the same metaphor combined with sense to strengthen the image strategy, which balances faithfulness to the original metaphor with cultural relevance. The final category, addressing metaphors of different mapping conditions, employs replacement of the source language image with a culturally appropriate target language image and direct image reproduction in the target language. We propose that despite the differences between the two languages which belong to different families, the cognitive model of love and beloved could be similar between Spanish and Arabic with source domains such pain, suffering, wound, killer and others being prototypical members of this model. This similarity can be ascribed to historical and cultural elements, specifically the interconnected past of Arabs and Spaniards during the Al-Andalus era.

Keywords: cognitive semantics, metaphor translation, literary texts, Spanish, Arabic, culture

1. Introduction

This study explores metaphor translation, specifically focusing on the Spanish novel *La Sombra del Viento* (2001) by Carlos Ruiz Zafón and its translated counterpart in Arabic by Muaweyah Abdel Majeed (2016). The significance of this study lies in its attempt to compare metaphors originating from two languages belonging to different families. In doing so, we aim to reveal how cultural aspects may influence the production of metaphors within literary works. Furthermore, this study explores the translation strategies employed in each type of mapping conditions under the cogno-cultural approach by Al-Zoubi et al. (2007), shedding light on the interaction between language, culture, and metaphorical expression. These mapping conditions include metaphors of similar mapping conditions realized similarly, metaphors of similar mapping conditions realized differently, and metaphors of different mapping conditions (Al-Zoubi et al. 2007). This study is unique as its focal point diverges from the conventional focus on translation between English and Arabic. We aim to enrich the discourse on metaphor translation by examining a less-explored linguistic context through investigating the Spanish-

to-Arabic translation. The study also provides concrete examples of how cognitive processes, such as conceptual mapping, image reproduction, and cultural adaptation, operate in real-world literary translation. This is done through identifying the translation strategies utilized in accordance with the principles outlined by the cogno-cultural approach which is based on cognitive translation hypothesis (Mandelblit 1995).

2. Theoretical framework

The cogno-cultural approach is grounded in the cognitive translation hypothesis (CTH) as well as conceptual metaphor theory (CMT, Lakoff & Johnson 1980). In CMT, it is argued that metaphor is not only a figure of speech, but it is a cognitive device through which humans understand abstract concepts. CMT proposes that humans' cognitive system is grounded in concrete, sensory experiences, establishing mappings from a typical concrete source domain to a typical abstract target domain (see Kövecses 2010; Zibin et al. 2025; Abu Romman 2025).

In literature, CMT enables the discovery of the complexities of metaphors found in narratives. Moreover, when we extend the application of CMT beyond literature, we find its connection with culture. Metaphors used in literary works usually serve as mirrors reflecting the culture of the author. We can obtain insights into the values, beliefs, and experiences that influence the authors' perspective through analyzing these metaphors.

CTH explores how metaphors are translated between different linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Mandelblit (1995) proposed CTH, suggesting two schemas of cognitive mapping conditions: Similar mapping condition (SMC) and different mapping condition (DMC) based on the similarities and differences between the source and target domains of a metaphor. This is further influenced by the "difference in reaction time due to a conceptual shift" (Mandelblit 1995: 493), where the reaction time of translators is a parameter used to detect a DMC (Taheri-Ardali et al. 2013). Essentially, metaphors take more time and effort to translate when there are different conceptual mappings between the source and target domains, necessitating the translator to search for an alternative mapping.

Mandelblit focused on reaction times and conceptual shifts, but other scholars such as Al-Zoubi et al. (2007) focused on the translated products and how they are influenced by mapping conditions. They argued that it is the translator's responsibility to adjust the mappings to suit the target language (TL) and culture. Thus, they introduced the cogno-cultural approach, which includes three categories of cognitive mapping conditions for metaphor translation.

1. Metaphors of similar mapping conditions realized similarly, known as *cultural universals*, and are expressed identically in both languages. For example, the idiom *actions speak louder than words* is similarly expressed in Arabic as *الأفعال أبلغ من الأقوال* ('actions speak louder than words').
2. Metaphors of similar mapping conditions realized differently which have the same conceptual basis but are translated differently due to differences in cultural and religious backgrounds. For instance, the expression *fan the flames* is translated in Arabic as *يصب زيت على النار* ('pour oil on a fire').

3. Metaphors of different mapping conditions are culture-specific and have distinct conceptual domains in different languages and cultures. This category includes root metaphors, primarily mapped onto political, cultural, and religious domains. An example of this category is the idiom *the elephant in the room* which, when translated, requires a literal approach to align with the target culture.

The cogno-cultural approach illustrates the translator's efforts and strategies in translating metaphors across diverse cultures, focusing on how translators address challenges in rendering identical, similar, and different mapping conditions. It helps in preserving the cultural aspects and context of the original work. This is essential for ensuring that the translated text stays faithful to the source material and that readers in the target culture can understand and appreciate the cultural references (Khalifah & Zibin 2022).

3. Background

3.1. *The target novel*

The Shadow of the Wind, titled *La sombra del Viento* in Spanish, is a successful novel written by the renowned Spanish author Carlos Ruiz Zafón in 2001 which was translated as ظل الريح ('The Shadow of the Wind') by Muaweyah Abdel Majeed in 2016. In 2004, Lucia Graves translated the book into English, which resulted in it selling over a million copies in the UK. Prior to this, the book had already achieved popularity in continental Europe, where it topped the Spanish bestseller lists for several weeks. The book is estimated to have achieved a global sales figure of 15 million copies, placing it among the highest-selling novels in history. The novel is, in fact, a narrative contained within another narrative. The novel commences in the 1940s, introducing the central character, Daniel, a little boy whose father is the proprietor of a bookshop in Barcelona. One day, his father escorts him to the Cemetery of Forgotten Books—an undisclosed library that contains valuable and prohibited volumes. Daniel is attracted to a book titled *The Shadow of the Wind* by Julian Carax and decides to bring it back to his home. Daniel rapidly peruses and becomes enamored with the narrative. He quickly realizes that the enigmatic writer of the book, Carax, has disappeared along with all the other copies of *The Shadow of the Wind* and the majority of his other writings. Subsequently, Daniel embarks on a quest to ascertain the fate of the author and his literary works. The story includes elements of romance, mystery, loss and love. It was selected because of its popularity, and, upon cursory examination, it was found that it is rich in metaphor.

3.2. *Metaphor in translation*

Translating metaphors has posed a challenge to translators and translation scholars who have concerns “about the problems of transferring metaphors from one language into another” (Schäffner 2004: 1254). Addressing metaphor in translation introduces more complexities because the challenges of dealing with one language are “at least doubled—if not squared—when two languages come into play” (Rojo 2015: 721). Translators will, thus, “suffer” twice when handling metaphors as they must first have a solid comprehension of the meaning of metaphors in the source text (ST) and then find an equivalent meaning with a similar function in the target text (TT) (Al-Zoubi et al. 2007: 230).

Most arguments about metaphor in translation studies is based on the traditional understanding of metaphor as a figure of speech, as a linguistic expression which replaces another expression (with a literal meaning), and whose main function is the stylistic adornment of the text (Schäffner 2004: 1254). Departing from this traditional view of metaphor and adopting a cognitive approach has been recent in translation studies (see Khalifah & Zibin 2022).

Linguistic approaches to translation involve defining it as the transfer of meaning, substituting signs in the source language (SL) with equivalent signs in the target language (TL). The primary goal is to reproduce the ST in the TL as closely as possible, considering both content and form. This approach focuses on identifying the smallest equivalent units at lexical and grammatical levels that can be substituted for each other in the actual text (Catford 1965; Schäffner 2004: 1254).

Textlinguistic approaches, on the other hand, view translation as the production of a TT induced by the ST (Neubert 1985). The text itself is considered the unit of translation, emphasizing that a text always exists within a specific situation and culture. This approach requires consideration of situational factors, genre conventions, addressee knowledge and expectations, and text functions. The central concept of equivalence is applied at the textual level, defined as communicative equivalence, where TT and ST hold equal value in their respective communicative situations within their cultures (Schäffner 2004: 1254).

Functionalist approaches define translation as a purposeful activity (cf. Nord 2014), including a transcultural interaction (Holz-Mänttari 1984), and as production of a TT customized for its specified purpose for target audience in a target culture (cf. Vermeer's Skopos theory, e.g., Vermeer 1996). The actual form of the TT is, therefore, not only dependent on the structure of the ST but also on the intended purpose of the text in the target culture. The quality of the TT is assessed based on its appropriateness of the purpose rather than the equivalence to the TT. More modern linguistic approaches recognize that translation is a complex text-processing activity, but they still emphasize that the term *translation* should be reserved for cases where an equivalence relation exists between ST and TT (House 1997; Koller 1992; Schäffner 2004: 1254).

Equivalence is the most controversial notion in translation studies. Some translation scholars reject this notion contending that maintaining equivalence in the vocabulary allows translators to bypass the issue that "it is difference, not sameness or transparency or equality, which is inscribed in the operations of translation" (Hermans 1998: 61). The same perspective is also reflected in recent approaches that are inspired by postmodern theories and cultural studies, which argue that texts do not acquire any essentially fixed meaning that could be replicated elsewhere (e.g. Arrojo 1998; Venuti 1995; Schäffner 2004: 1255). According to Venuti (1995: 306), the target text should be "the site where a different culture emerges, where a reader gets a glimpse of a cultural other." The controversy that the notion of equivalence creates is very evident in the translation of metaphor due to the challenge it creates for translators when attempting to create the same meaning and influence in the TL.

Most translation scholars agree that the image in the ST cannot always be maintained in the TT, because the image that is linked to the metaphor is unknown in the TL, or the associations triggered by the SL metaphor get lost in the TL (Schäffner 2004: 1256). Consequently, several translation procedures have been suggested as alternative solutions to the ideal of reproducing the metaphor intact. Van den Broeck (1981: 77), for example, proposed a set of strategies for translating metaphors, which aim to address the challenges and complexities involved in rendering metaphors from one language to another.

1. Translation sensu stricto (i.e. transfer of both SL tenor and SL vehicle into TL)
2. Substitution (i.e. replacement of SL vehicle by a different TL vehicle with more or less the same tenor)
3. Paraphrase (i.e. rendering a SL metaphor by a non-metaphorical expression in the TL) (Van den Broeck 1981: 77)

Newmark's translation procedures, in contrast to Van den Broeck's descriptive framework, are given in a prescriptive manner with the intention of offering principles, strict rules, and standards for translating and translator training. He classifies metaphors into five categories: dead, clichéd, stock, recent, and innovative. He suggests seven translation techniques, which have been widely used in the literature. These procedures are arranged in order of Newmark's (1981: 87–91) preference:

1. Direct image reproduction in the TL: For instance, literally translating *golden hair* to *goldenes Haar*, which preserves the same imagery in the TL (ibid 88).
2. Replacement of the SL image with a culturally appropriate TL image: An example is translating *other fish to fry* to *d'autres chats à fouetter*, replacing the fish metaphor with a culturally relevant one (ibid 89). The phrase *d'autres chats à fouetter* is a French idiom meaning 'other issues to deal with' or 'other matters to attend to', which conveys a similar idea in a culturally appropriate way
3. Translation of metaphor by simile, retaining the image: For instance, rendering *Ces zones cryptuaire où s'élabore la beauté* as *The crypt-like areas where beauty is manufactured*. Newmark suggests this approach to tone down the impact of the metaphor (ibid 90).
4. Translation of metaphor (or simile) using simile plus sense: For example, translating *tout un vocabulaire molièresque* as *a whole repertoire of medical quackery such as Molière might have used*. This approach is recommended to enhance comprehension but may result in a loss of the original effect (ibid 90).
5. Conversion of metaphor to sense: An example is translating *sein Brot verdienen* as *to earn one's living*. This strategy is suitable when the TL image is more general or better suited to the context, but it may sacrifice the emotional elements (ibid 91).
6. Deletion of redundant metaphors: When a metaphor is redundant, it may be omitted from the translation.
7. Use of the same metaphor combined with sense to strengthen the image: In some cases, the same metaphor can be retained alongside an explanation to reinforce the intended image. For example, in translating the metaphor *the tongue is a fire*, the translator may add *a fire ruins things; what we say also ruins things* (ibid 91).

These strategies will be used to discuss how metaphors were translated from Spanish to Arabic.

3.3. Previous studies on the translation of metaphors

Khalifah & Zibin (2022) contend that a cognitive approach to metaphors in literature can better explain the strategies employed in their creation. The study creates a nexus between the cognitive and socio-cultural aspects of translating metaphors in literary texts. The researchers adopt conceptual metaphor theory based on the notion of main meaning focus (Kövecses 2017)

and the cogno-cultural approach (Al-Zoubi et al. 2007) as a theoretical framework. The text the researchers used to collect the metaphors from is the Arabic novel *Zuqaq Al-Midaq*, or *Midaq Alley*, written by Naguib Mahfuz's and translated by Trevor Le Gassick. Moreover, the metaphors that were collected in the study were identified using the Metaphor Identification Procedure (MIP) followed by Steen's (2007) five-step procedure. Data collected fell into four main categories: metaphors with similar mapping conditions realized similarly, metaphors of similar mapping conditions realized differently, metaphors of different mapping conditions, and metaphors that were not translated or discussed at all. The researchers concluded with several deductions, but the most important one was that analyzing metaphors in a work of literature through the lens of cognition can help translators choose more appropriate strategies in translating the metaphors from one language to the other.

Park's (2009: 158–59) study investigates how culture and metaphor are connected. The researcher relies on Katharina Reiss's (1989) classification of text types: an informative text type, an expressive text type, an operative text type and an audio-medial text type. The paper also incorporates Newmark's (1981) seven procedures in metaphor translation. Moreover, the study uses Edgar Allen Poe's short story "Ligeia" to collect data together with five different Korean translations of the same short story.

Another important study on the translations of metaphors in the genre of the novel is Dagnev & Chervenкова's (2020) study that examines the conceptual metaphor behind the metaphorical linguistic expressions in key texts, all of which are canonical novels and their translations in Bulgarian. The researchers analyzed the texts in both languages using Steen's MIPVU approach and three types of metaphors were focused on: sleeping metaphors, linguistically expressed conceptual metaphors and creative metaphors. The researchers found that many translated metaphors share similar mapping conditions between English and Bulgarian, likely due to shared cultural backgrounds and globalization.

Another study that examines the translation of metaphors in the novel is Mudaghmesh & Allawzi (2023). The study examines the translatability of Eliot's novel *The Lifted Veil* through several stylistic features such as different types of figurative language and idioms. The researchers use several translation strategies by Baker (1992), Newmark (2001), Pierini (2007), Chesterman (1997), and Venuti (1995). In translating the metaphors located in the novel into the Arabic language, the authors used Nida's (1964) formal equivalence approach as well as Newmark's (2001) second metaphor translation strategy. An apt example used by the researchers is in the translation of *poured forth to me wonderful narratives of his professional experience*. The phrase *poured forth* was translated with its intended meaning rather than a literal translation, using the Arabic term سكب ('poured') instead of حيث أمطرنني ('where he rained upon me'). The researchers argue that employing Nida's formal equivalence approach was sometimes unnatural due to the cultural differences between the English and Arabic languages. The researchers utilize Newmark's second metaphor translation strategy, which involves replacing the source language (SL) image with a culturally appropriate target language image, alongside Nida's dynamic equivalence approach. This approach emphasizes conveying the meaning of the original text rather than providing a literal word-for-word translation in English.

Chita & Stavrou (2020) investigate metaphor as a cultural concept by comparing English, Greek, and German. They apply Newmark's theory of translation, particularly his typology of metaphors, and analyze Oscar Wilde's novel *The Picture of Dorian Gray* to gather data on metaphors. The researchers aim to explore whether the translations of metaphors in Greek and German differ, as these languages belong to different branches of the Indo-European family. They conclude that the Greek and German translations preserved the metaphors found in the

English version. They also note that there are “more similarities in metaphorical expressions between German and English than between English and Greek” (Chita & Stavrou 2020: 128). The study concludes that, in many instances, the translators’ efforts to convey the metaphors in the target language (TL) were unsuccessful.

Hasar & Panahbar (2017) argue that translators should consider the interaction between metaphorical linguistic expressions, conceptual metaphors, and cultural models, based on Cienki’s (1999) work on conceptual metaphors. The researchers offer a thorough investigation of the metaphor in cognitive linguistics and center their corpus on three of Khayyam’s quatrains with translated works by Fitzgerald and Abdorahman Sharafkandi (a Kurdish translator). Hasar & Panahbar (2017) found that differences in cultural understanding are the main reason for challenges in translation. Their analysis of three quatrains and their translations illustrates this point. They further note that if a translator is unaware of or unable to address these unique cultural perspectives, important metaphors tied to them might be missing in the translated work. They recommend that translators pay attention to the way ideas are expressed, the underlying conceptual metaphors, and how these metaphors relate to the cultural context of the target language. They emphasize that without considering these three elements, achieving a true sense of equivalence in translation is unlikely.

Another study that also centers on the examination of metaphor translation in poetry is Ritchie & Zhao’s (2020). The researchers concentrate on the renowned Chinese translator and theorist Xu Yuanchong and revisit his traditional approach to translating metaphors. They aim to examine the conceptual metaphors and potential perceptual stimuli related to the original Chinese language and their literal word-by-word translation. Additionally, they compare these with the conceptual metaphors and perceptual simulations present in Xu’s English translations. This comparison helped assess how Xu’s metaphor choices influence the range of meanings available to readers. The researchers come to the conclusion that applying a contemporary cognitive linguistics theory to the Chinese poems translated by Xu Yuanchong shows major differences in the two sets of translations. Xu Yuanchong’s translations demonstrate differences in themes and shades of meaning, with instances highlighting how his work was inspired by the original Chinese version. In the results and conclusion section of the study, the authors argue that if one views metaphors and other figurative language as “merely decorative,” Xu’s traditional approach to translating these metaphors is justified (Ritchie & Zhao 2020: 134). They suggest that translators take into account the metaphors, metonyms, potential perception simulations, and cultural associations present in both the original poem and its alternative translations. This highlights how cognitive linguistics theories aid in understanding the complexities of poetry translation.

Finally, Ali’s study (2006) highlights the previous misconceptions and observations about metaphors and examines them from a translation perspective, aiming to illustrate the advantages and disadvantages of various translation procedures. The researcher investigates the different ways that metaphors are translated and examines different facets of the literary technique. Several sections examine the metaphor’s features and the differences between metaphors and similes. In comparing similes to metaphors, the researcher concludes that applying standard translation procedures as “alternative solutions” when a SL metaphor cannot be directly retained in a TL carries risks (Ali 2006: 134). The author argues that employing “alternative solutions” in translation can become a “random process” that fails to account for the specific structure and function of the metaphor in question (Ali 2006: 134). The author suggests that a metaphor in the SL might be translated incorrectly in the TL as a simile or even deleted altogether. In conclusion, the author suggests that a translator’s decision to translate a metaphor

should consider the metaphor's complexity, its distinct characteristics, its relevance to the TL, and the translator's overall approach to translation—whether prioritizing a semantic translation (faithful to the SL culture) or a communicative translation (primarily oriented towards the TL reader) (Ali 2006: 134).

Against this background, the contextualization of this study within the broader literature on metaphor translation strengthens its significance. Park's (2009) examination of the connection between culture and metaphor, Dagnev & Chervenkova's (2020) study of conceptual metaphors in canonical novels, and Mudaghmesh & Allawzi's (2023) study on stylistic features in translation offer a rich background. Additionally, studies by Chita & Stavrou (2020), Hasar & Panahbar (2017), Ritchie & Zhao (2020), and Ali (2006) provide diverse perspectives on metaphor translation, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the subject. The foundation of this study aligns with the cognitive linguistic perspective presented by Khalifah & Zibin (2022), which highlights that understanding metaphors from a cognitive viewpoint offers a clearer rationale for the translation strategies used. This approach establishes an important connection between cognitive and socio-cultural elements, enhancing the exploration of metaphors in literary texts. Khalifah & Zibin (2022) focused on Arabic-English translation, but this study shifts the focus to Spanish-Arabic translation, broadening the investigation to a different linguistic context.

4. Methodology

The data for this study was collected through a thorough examination of both the Spanish and Arabic versions of the target novel. In employing a type-based approach, emphasis was placed on the quality rather than the quantity of linguistic expressions, aligning with the methodology outlined by Kövecses et al. (2019). This approach involves an analysis of phrases and expressions. The collected data comprised 124 metaphors, but in this study, we only analyzed four examples under each category provided by Al-Zoubi et al. (2007) due to word limit constraints. Our purpose is to demonstrate the similarity or lack of similarity between Spanish and Arabic in terms of metaphors at the linguistic and conceptual levels. Therefore, the focus was on type rather than frequency (see Alazazmeh & Zibin 2023). The identification of metaphors in the text was done using the Metaphor Identification Procedure (MIP) (Pragglejaz Group 2007). MIP offers a systematic and explicit means of identifying words employed metaphorically in discourse. Addressing the challenge that scholars face in distinguishing literal from metaphorical language, Pragglejaz Group (2007) argues that such determinations often rely on theoretical perspectives and research objectives, resulting in inconsistencies and disagreements among scholars, which in turn may compromise the validity and reliability of metaphorical claims (Steen et al. 2010: 165). To mitigate this issue, Pragglejaz Group proposed the MIP as a tool to establish clear criteria for identifying linguistic metaphors in both spoken and written discourse. In essence, MIP serves as a research instrument for discerning words that carry metaphorical connotations within their respective contexts (Pragglejaz Group 2007: 2).

Following the identification of metaphorical expressions, contextual metaphors were extracted using the steps outlined by Steen (2007), which involves establishing analogies between two concepts that may not initially appear to be related (see Khalifah & Zibin 2022; Alazazmeh & Zibin 2023; Zibin et al. 2022). Subsequently, the translation of these metaphors was examined using the cogno-cultural approach by Al-Zoubi et al. (2007) and the translation strategies were identified relying on Newmark (1981).

5. Data analysis and discussion

The analysis of metaphors extracted from the novel reveals the presence of three types of mappings as proposed by Al-Zoubi et al. (2007). These metaphors are presented in the following subsections along with illustrative examples from both the source and target texts and an English translation for the reader's convenience.

5.1. Metaphors of similar mapping conditions realized similarly

In this type of metaphor, both at the conceptual and linguistic levels in the ST (Spanish) and the TT (Arabic), the mapping conditions, metaphorical expressions, and the sense of enchantment are preserved:

- (1) Llegado a este punto, yo había quedado reducido a pasmarote, a merced de aquella criatura cuyas palabras y cuyos encantos no tenía yo modo, ni ganas de resistir. (ST: 14)

لم أستطع أن أقول شيئاً إذ كنت أرزح تحت رحمة ذلك المخلوق الذي يفتنني بصوته فلا أقوى عليه ولا أريد أن أقاوم سحره (TT: 40)

(‘At this point, I had been reduced to a stupor, at the mercy of that creature whose words and charms I had neither the means nor the desire to resist.’)

In example (1), the antagonist Daniel is talking about Clara, his first love, describing her as the woman who has bewitched him; she was older than him and showed no interest in having a romantic relationship with him. Both the source text (ST) and the target text (TT) employ the conceptual metaphor LOVE IS MAGIC. The conceptual mapping involves equating the experience of being captivated by love to the enchantment of magic. The similarity is not only found at the conceptual level, but also at the linguistic one. In the ST, the speaker describes being reduced to a *pasmarote* (‘a person struck dumb or senseless’) under the influence of the creature’s words and charms.

The TT maintains a similar metaphorical expression, stating that the speaker was unable to say anything *لم أستطع أن أقول شيئاً* (‘I could not say anything’) while being enchanted by the creature’s voice. Linguistically, both texts use words associated with magic and enchantment. In the ST, *encantos* (‘charms’) is used, and in the TT, *سحره* (‘his magic’) is employed. Concerning the translation strategy used, it is the direct image reproduction in the target language (TL). The conceptual metaphor LOVE IS MAGIC remains consistent in both texts, indicating a direct reproduction of the metaphorical image without introducing changes. The similarities are also present in the linguistic expressions used in both languages.

- (2) Clara Barceló me robó el corazón, la respiración y el sueño. Al amparo de la luz embrujada del Ateneo, sus manos escribieron en mi piel una maldición que habría de perseguirme durante años. (ST: 11)

سلبت مني كلارا برسلوه النوم والقلب والأنفاس، طبعت يداها على وجهي، تحت ذلك الظل الذي يحوم في تلك الصلاة، لعنة كانت تلاحقني إلى الأبد (TT: 33)

(‘Clara Barceló stole my heart, my breath, and my sleep. Her hands left an imprint on my face under that shadow that hovers in that hall. A curse that would follow me forever.’)

In example (2), Daniel is still describing his love for Carla which is depicted here as a curse giving rise to the metaphor LOVE IS A CURSE. There are similarities between Spanish and Arabic, manifesting both at the conceptual and linguistic levels. They have shared conceptual mappings, including unpredictability, complexity, long lasting effects, and inescapability. This similarity is reflected through comparable metaphorical expressions used in both languages *maldición* and لعنة (‘curse’). The shared metaphorical expression LOVE IS A CURSE in both Spanish and Arabic highlights a cultural parallel between the two linguistic traditions. This commonality can be attributed to a shared belief in the potency and transformative nature of curses within these cultures. In both Spanish and Arabic societies, there is a cultural acknowledgment of the impact of curses on individuals’ lives. The metaphor, in this case, becomes a linguistic reflection of a cultural belief that associates love with a potentially challenging or even adverse fate. Love, being a powerful and complex emotion, is metaphorically equated with a curse to convey the depth of its impact on an individual’s life.

This shared cultural belief in the influence of curses serves as a foundation for the linguistic expression, creating a cross-cultural resonance in the metaphorical understanding of love. As pertaining to the translation strategy used, the translator follows the direct image reproduction in the TL. The conceptual metaphor LOVE IS A CURSE remains the same in the ST and the TT, and thus, demonstrates an exact replication of the metaphorical image without introducing significant changes. The linguistic terms employed in the two languages exhibit similarities as well.

- (3) Mientras a mí sólo me estaba permitido anhelarlo. Si me hubiese parado a pensarlo, me hubiera comprendido que mi devoción por Clara no era más que una fuente de sufrimiento. (ST: 23)

لم أكن أتجرأ على فعل ذلك، لو أنني تمعنت في الأمر قليلاً لأدركت أن هيامي المطلق كان ينبعا من الألم لا ينضب (TT: 55)

(‘While to me, only yearning for it was allowed. If I had stopped to think about it, I would have understood that my devotion to Clara was nothing more than a source of suffering.’)

In example (3), Daniel characterizes his affection for Clara as a wellspring of anguish and distress, which gives rise to the abstract metaphor LOVE IS SUFFERING/PAIN. The mapping circumstances share similarities in terms of intensity and difficulty, and the metaphorical expressions used, such as *fuentes de sufrimiento* (‘source of suffering’) and ينبعا من الألم (‘a spring of pain’), are closely similar. In Arab culture, the correlation between pain and suffering is evident in several literary works, poetry, and songs (see Zibin et al. 2022). The symbolic connection between love and pain is also a prominent and recurring motif in both Spanish and larger Hispanic cultures. The merging of love and sorrow is a reoccurring topic in notable literary works, such as the sonnets of Spanish writers like Gustavo Adolfo Bécquer and Federico García Lorca. Like in the previous two examples, the translator employs the approach

of direct image reproduction in the TL by preserving the metaphor of LOVE IS SUFFERING. The TT offers an accurate representation of the metaphor in relation to its meaning and the linguistic choices made for the word. The translation, thus, shows no notable disparities from the ST.

(4) ¿Dijo acaso el bollito que era mi novia? (ST: 74)

وهل قالت تلك الشامببلا بأنها خطيبيتي يا ترى (TT: 152)

(‘Did the little sweetie say she was my girlfriend?’)

In example (4), Fermín, Daniel’s friend describes the girl he has a crush on as a dessert giving rise to the conceptual metaphor THE OBJECT OF LOVE OR DESIRE IS FOOD\DESSERT. *Ciambella* is a type of Italian dessert that looks like a bun or ring cake, while it is not mentioned in the ST where it is referred to as *a little bun (el bollito)*. The mappings between THE OBJECT OF LOVE\DESIRE and DESSERT include sweetness, attraction, indulgence, and delight. At the linguistic level, both *Ciambella* and *little bun* mean something similar, but the choice of the word *Ciambella* could have been intentional. Even though this word is not common in Arabic, the translator may have chosen it due to the way it sounds. The alternatives, *نونت* (‘daunt’) or *كعكة* (‘cake’), may not have conveyed the same sense of endearment and playfulness as *Ciambella*. Concerning the translation strategy, the translator adopts the strategy of the same metaphor combined with sense to strengthen the image in this example. Instead of using a word similar to the one used by the author in the source text, like *حلوتي* (‘sweetie’), the translator adopts a similar metaphor at the conceptual levels with some differences at the linguistic level metaphor. The translator skillfully chooses a similar term that reinforces the connotation while also creating a lasting impact and a sense of playfulness.

5.2. Metaphors of similar mapping conditions realized differently

In this category, the conceptual schema exists in both languages, but it is linguistically realized in distinct ways. The difference in this context pertains to the manner in which the conceptual schema is linguistically expressed in each language.

(5) Según me explicó la criada, Barceló había bautizado como Ortega y Gasset, respectivamente. Clara me esperaba en un salón al otro lado de este bosque que miraba sobre la plaza. (ST: 21)

وقالت لي الخادمة أن يرسلوه أسماهما أورتيغا وغاسيت. وجدتُ معذبتي بانتظاري في صالة عند حدود تلك الغابة الاصطناعية (TT: 52)

(‘As explained to me by the maid, Barceló had baptized the rooms as Ortega and Gasset, respectively. Clara was waiting for me in a lounge on the other side of this forest overlooking the square.’)

In example (5), THE OBJECT OF LOVE OR DESIRE is portrayed as A TORMENTOR, giving rise to the conceptual metaphor THE OBJECT OF LOVE/DESIRE IS A TORMENTOR. The context is about an actress whose name is Verónica and who is supposed to be very attractive. Both Daniel and his friend Fermín were watching a movie in the movie theatre featuring Verónica. The mappings between THE OBJECT OF LOVE\DESIRE and TORMENTOR or TORTURER include the intense control exerted over emotions, the experience of emotional pain, the inability to have a romantic or physical relationship with the target person, and the anticipation of the lover’s actions. At the linguistic level, there is no direct mention of a torturer/tormentor in the ST; the narrator only mentions the name of Daniel’s first flame, Clara. In the TT, however, the name is

not mentioned, but the term *معذبتي* ('tormentor') is used instead. The translation strategy used in this example is the replacement of the SL image with a culturally appropriate TL image. The translator uses the term *معذبتي* ('tormentor') to replace the name of Daniel's first flame, Clara. The use of this term gives rise to a metaphor that may exist in the SL at the conceptual level but not at the linguistic level. It is, however, commonly used in the TL and culture.

THE OBJECT OF LOVE/DESIRE in Spanish can be perceived negatively, as a killer, for example, as shown in example 6.

- (6) Guardé el caramelo en el bolsillo de la chaqueta y navegué por el resto de la película sin prestar atención ni a Verónica Lake ni a las víctimas de sus fatales encantos. (ST: 51)

وضعتُ حبة السكاكر في جيب سترتي وتابعت باقي الفيلم في شرود، دون أن أتحمس لجمال فيرونيكا ليك الفتاك ولا لمصير ضحاياها (TT: 108)

('I kept the candy in the jacket pocket and sailed through the rest of the movie, paying no attention to either Verónica Lake or the victims of her fatal charms.')

Or in example (3) where love is perceived as suffering. Thus, the conceptual scheme of perceiving THE OBJECT OF LOVE\DESIRE as a TORTURER may also exist in Spanish even if it is not linguistically stated. In Arabic, conceiving of THE OBJECT OF LOVE as A TORTURER is salient and can be found in various literary texts. More examples that illustrate the existence of negative source domains depicting love and the object of love in Spanish are provided below.

- (7) A su manera, no mentía. ¿Qué le puedo decir? Pues, sí, yo creo que Nuria todavía se acuerda de ese hombre, aunque no lo diga. Y, la verdad, yo eso no se lo perdonaré a Carax jamás. Usted es muy joven todavía, pero yo sé lo que duelen esas cosas, si quiere saber mi opinión, Carax era un ladrón de corazones, y el de mi hija se lo llevó a la tumba o al infierno. (ST: 41)

كانت محقة من زاوية معينة. ماذا يسعني أن أقول؟ أجل، أعتقد أن نوريا ما تزال تفكر في كاراكس ولهذا لن أستطيع أن أغفر له ما حبيبت. ما زلت صغيرا لتعرف أن هذا العذاب يترك جرحا لا يندمل. وإن أرجت رأيي فإن كاراكس رجل غاو وإنه قد أخذ قلب ابنتي وحمله معه إلى القبر أو إلى الجحيم. (TT: 88)

('In his own way, he didn't lie. What can I tell you? Well, yes, I believe Nuria still remembers that man, even if she doesn't say it. And, truthfully, I will never forgive Carax for that. You are still very young, but I know how much those things hurt, if you want to know my opinion, Carax was a heart thief, and he took mine to the grave or to hell.')

In example (7), the metaphorical depiction of BEING IN LOVE is manifested as BEING HURT, and THE OBJECT OF LOVE is depicted as a THIEF. In this instance, Isaac narrates his daughter's relationship with Carax, expressing his belief that she has suffered due to Carax. Both the Spanish and Arabic texts convey the idea that being in love equates to emotional pain. However, there are distinctions in the degree of intentionality and specific expressions used in the metaphor. In the Spanish text, Carax is explicitly labelled a *ladrón de corazones* ('thief of hearts'), accentuating the romantic aspect of the metaphor. On the other hand, the Arabic term *غاو* ('led by desire') is more general, describing Carax as 'a stray led by desire', suggesting a level of unintentional captivation. The use of the word *جرح* ('wound') in Arabic intensifies the emotional impact, emphasizing a more deliberate hurt or injury. The translator uses the same metaphor combined with sense to strengthen the image. The ST uses the metaphorical image of being in love hurts, but the target text intensifies the meaning using the word *عذاب* ('torture') and further explains that this torture leaves a wound that does not heal. The ST also uses the

strategy of conversion of metaphor to sense using the word *غامي* ('led by desire') for the metaphor thief. Put differently, the text explains the metaphor by illustrating how Carax was infatuated with Nuria and how their love inflicted her with pain and suffering.

- (8) Que Carax andaba un poco atontado con ella. Mi Nuria es de las que rompen corazones con sólo entrar en una tienda. (ST: 39)

أن كاراكس وقع في شرك الغرام بها. نوريا من النساء اللواتي يُصعقن المرء بحبهن من النظرة الأولى (TT: 85)

(‘That Carax was a bit dazed by her. My Nuria is one of those who break hearts just by entering a store.’)

In example (8), the narrator describes the relationship between Carax and Nuria. The metaphor here is BEING IN LOVE IS BEING DAZED. In Spanish, the idea of Carax being ‘dazed’ suggests a state of enchantment or infatuation. In Arabic, the notion that Carax ‘fell into the love snare’ conveys a sense of being entrapped by love. While being dazed and being trapped by love could be considered different linguistically speaking, they share many conceptual mappings, including loss of control, captivation, overwhelming sensation, intense emotional impact, temporariness, and others. Additionally, both the Spanish expression of Nuria ‘breaking hearts’ by entering a store implies her irresistible charm, and the Arabic expression of her ‘shocking people with her love from the first glance’ similarly emphasizes the powerful and immediate effect of her love in both texts, even though the metaphorical expressions are not the same. The same metaphor combined with sense to strengthen the image is used in this example. For the term *dazed*, the translator uses the metaphor of *وقع في شرك الغرام بها* (‘fell into the love snare’) which is commonly used in the Arabic language to refer to someone who is deeply in love. The same strategy is also used for the metaphor of Nuria breaking hearts which is delivered as *تصعق المرء بحبها* (‘shocks people with her love’). Although the implied meaning of the metaphor remains consistent across both texts, the TT intensifies the connotation.

5.3. Metaphors of different mapping conditions

Metaphors with different mapping conditions are unique to each culture, exhibiting different conceptual domains across languages and cultures. This encompasses root metaphors, predominantly linked to political, cultural, and religious contexts. This section provides examples of this category:

- (9) El corazón de la hembra es un laberinto de sutilezas que desafía la mente cerril del varón trapacero. (ST: 75)

إن قلب المرأة آلة معقدة، لا يهتز لطيش الصبيان الجلفين (TT: 85)

(‘The female heart is a labyrinth of subtleties that challenges the stubborn mind of the deceitful male.’)

In example (9), Fermín is imparting to Daniel insights into the complexities of females’ hearts while sharing his own feelings for Bernarda. This example employs two metaphors: in the Spanish text, THE BELOVED HEART is likened to A LABYRINTH, and in the Arabic text, it is described as A COMPLICATED MACHINE. The use of *laberinto* (‘labyrinth’) in Spanish may evoke a sense of mystery and complexity associated with a labyrinth, while the Arabic metaphor utilizes the idea of a complicated machine, offering a distinct cultural perspective on intricacy. The inclusion of *لطيش الصبيان الجلفين* (‘the mischievousness of unruly boys’) in the Arabic text

adds a layer of meaning, emphasizing the recklessness of playful boys in contrast to the complexity of the female heart. The metaphor 'complicated machine' suggests precision, order, and a certain predictability. Machines are often designed with specific functions and mechanisms, emphasizing a structured and engineered complexity.

In contrast, a 'labyrinth' implies a more mystical and unpredictable complexity. Labyrinths are associated with winding paths, choices, and sometimes an element of mystery, symbolizing a journey with unforeseen twists and turns. Labyrinths, as metaphorically depicted in Spanish culture, often carry symbolic significance related to mystery, complexity, and intricate paths. Within Spanish literature and cultural expressions, labyrinths frequently serve as powerful symbols representing the challenging and enigmatic aspects of human experiences, emotions, and relationships (see NBM News 2014). The translation uses the strategy of replacement of the source language (SL) image with a culturally appropriate target language (TL) image. A labyrinth that is used to describe the beloved heart is replaced with a complicated machine, indicating the replacement of the metaphorical image with a more culturally appropriate one.

- (10) Con decirle que soy capaz de pasar por una iglesia después de treinta y dos años de abstinencia clerical y recitar los salmos de San Serafín o lo que haga falta por ella.
(ST: 108–109)

تصور أنني من أجلها مستعد أن تطأ قدمي الكنيسة، بعد اثنين وثلاثين عاماً من الصيام عن الدين، كي أتلو مزامير القديس سيرافين أو أي قديس آخر (TT: 213)

(‘Just to tell you, I am capable of passing by a church after thirty-two years of clerical abstinence and reciting the psalms of Saint Seraphim or whatever is needed for it.’)

In example (10), Fermín is talking about his love for Bernarda, stating that because of her, he is going to church, giving rise to the metaphor that LOVE IS SALVATION AND REDEMPTION, with mappings including forgiveness, healing, renewal, transformation, and others. In the ST, there is a metaphorical expression that connects love and salvation through the imagery of the church. The speaker, Fermín, conveys the depth of his feelings for Bernarda by expressing his willingness to go to a church after thirty-two years of clerical abstinence. This act is not merely a physical visit to a church but is laden with symbolic meaning. The metaphor suggests that Fermín sees his love for Bernarda as a form of redemption or salvation. The act of reciting the psalms of Saint Seraphim adds another layer to the metaphor. Psalms are religious texts associated with praise, devotion, and spiritual reflection. Fermín's willingness to recite these psalms suggests a commitment and dedication to his love for Bernarda, elevating it to a sacred and reverential level. In the TT, the metaphor is retained in the translation, but the connection between love and God/Church may not be as salient in Arabic as it is in Spanish.

The emphasis in the target culture is on the link between God and marriage, which reflects the cultural and religious values that prioritize the sanctity of marriage as a legitimate and socially accepted expression of love. The act of going to a church in the TT and reciting psalms may be interpreted as a symbolic gesture of seeking divine blessings for the love that is to be expressed through the sacred institution of marriage. The translation strategy applied in this instance can be characterized as a form of literal translation or direct reproduction. It involves preserving the core elements of the metaphor. The decision to retain the metaphor is in line with the fact that, for the Arab audience, the concept of love between couples is not necessarily linked to salvation; rather, the emphasis is on marriage. Therefore, the translator

may have chosen a literal translation to maintain the cultural significance of love and salvation found in the Spanish context.

(11) Si tú eres más buena que el pan, Bernarda'. (ST: 24)

قلبك أطيب من رغيف خبز يا برناردا (TT: 213)

(‘If you are kinder than bread, Bernarda.’)

In example (11), Fermín describes the kindness of his beloved Bernarda as that of bread, giving rise to the metaphor OBJECT OF LOVE IS A LOAF OF BREAD. The conceptual mapping suggests that Bernarda is compared to something universally appreciated and valued, which is bread. There could be a cultural resonance with the significance of bread as a staple food and symbol of generosity. The focus is on her kindness, and the comparison highlights the inherent goodness and warmth associated with bread. The ST uses the word *buena* (‘good/kind’) to convey positive qualities, and *pan* (‘bread’) serves as a symbol of something essential. The TT introduces the word قلبك (‘your heart’), placing a direct focus on Bernarda’s heart. The translator may have opted to add *heart* since, without it, the metaphor would sound odd to an Arab audience. The choice of the metaphor might be influenced by cultural associations with food used to perceive THE OBJECT OF LOVE. In many Arabic poetic traditions, fruits such as dates, pomegranates, oranges, apples, or even more broadly, the sweetness of fruits, are used to symbolize various qualities associated with love, beauty, and desirable traits in a person (see Zibin et al. 2022) but never bread. The strategy used is the replacement of the SL image with a culturally appropriate TL image. As mentioned earlier, the translator adds the word *heart* to the metaphor to make the metaphor more familiar to the target readers. The metaphorical image is, thus, changed from *you are kinder than bread* to *your heart is kinder than bread* which is more culturally appropriate.

(12) Y eso del beso es para amateurs y diletantes de pantufla. A la mujer de verdad se la gana uno poco a poco. Es todo cuestión de psicología, como una buena faena en la plaza. (ST: 75)

والقبلة في اللقاء الأول أمر لا يقوم به إلا الهواة. يجدر بالخبير أن يستحوذ على قلب النساء الحقيقيات رويدا رويدا. إنها استراتيجيات سيكولوجية، تشبه نقات مصارع الثيران (TT: 154)

(‘And that business of the kiss is for amateurs and slipper dilettantes. A real woman is won over little by little. It’s all a matter of psychology, like a good bullfight in the arena.’)

In example (12), Fermín is explaining to Daniel the art of seducing women. The expression used is a simile where love is being compared to bullfighting. The comparison suggests that the process of winning a woman’s heart is like a bullfight. It implies a gradual approach, emphasizing the need for skill and patience, similar to the artistry and strategy involved in a bullfight. Bullfighting is a traditional and culturally important activity in Spain. It involves a choreographed performance between the matador and the bull, demonstrating skill, bravery, and finesse. The simile, therefore, draws on a culturally embedded reference that may appeal to the audience’s understanding of courtship. The TT also draws on the simile with bullfighting, but it is essential to note that bullfighting is not a prevalent cultural practice in Arabic-speaking regions. Therefore, the metaphor might be more of a literary device than a direct cultural reference. Since the Arab audience may not be very familiar with bullfighting, the added term نقات (‘leaps’) in the TT introduces a dynamic element, emphasizing the gradual and strategic approach in a more vivid manner. This term, while not present in the original,

contributes to the metaphor by drawing a parallel with the movements of a bullfighter. The translator uses direct image reproduction in the TL as their translation approach. Since the simile that compares love to bullfighting does not change significantly between the source and target texts, it indicates a precise replication of the simile in the linguistic expression employed in both texts to preserve the meaning and cultural references.

5.4. Discussion

Muaweyah Abdel Majeed's translation of the three types of metaphor mappings reveals a careful and deliberate approach. The selected translation procedures offer insight into how the depth of metaphors are maintained or modified between Spanish and Arabic. In the category of metaphors with similar mapping conditions, the conceptual metaphors are maintained in both languages and conveyed with linguistic resemblances. The translation approach employed was recognized as direct image reproduction in the target language (TL). This strategy entails preserving the metaphorical image without making significant alterations. The examples given, such as LOVE IS MAGIC and LOVE IS A CURSE, demonstrate the translator's effective preservation of both the conceptual and language aspects of the metaphors. Preserving these metaphors improves cross-cultural comprehension and emphasizes the common elements of metaphorical language in love and beloved-related settings in Spanish and Arabic.

The second category, known as metaphors of same mapping conditions realized differently, involves conceptual schemas that exist in both languages, but the linguistic expressions differ. The translation approach is characterized as the combination of the same metaphor with a sense of reinforcement to enhance the image. The translator preserves the central metaphorical idea while adjusting the linguistic representation to align with the TL and cultural context. This is demonstrated through examples such as THE OBJECT OF LOVE/DESIRE IS FOOD/DESSERT and BEING IN LOVE IS BEING DAZED. This approach enables a harmonious combination of faithfulness to the original metaphor and cultural appropriateness in the translation.

The final group, referred to as metaphors of diverse mapping conditions, includes metaphors that incorporate different conceptual domains across languages. The translation approach used is the substitution of the image in the source language (SL) with a culturally suitable image in the TL, as well as the direct reproduction of the image in the TL. The metaphor THE BELOVED HEART IS A LABYRINTH employed the first strategy to enhance the understanding of the intended audience. It demonstrated how the translator modified the metaphorical image to align it with the target culture. This method adapts the metaphor to align with the cultural context of the Arabic-speaking audience, which may involve changes to the original metaphorical term. The disparities found between the two languages can originate from the cultural values that govern a certain community. According to Kövecses (2010: 218), these differences might be traced to the wider cultural context and the impact of the natural and physical surroundings (see Altakhaineh & Zibin 2024). That is, language is influenced by its surrounding conditions.

On the other hand, in LOVE IS SALVATION AND REDEMPTION, the direct reproduction of the image in the TL strategy was employed to maintain the depiction utilized in the original text. One potential drawback of using this strategy is that it may be challenging to fully understand the meaning of the original metaphor. This suggests that translating examples belonging to this category, which are marked by differences between the metaphors in both the conceptual and

language aspects, may be regarded as the most challenging when compared to the two categories described earlier (see Khalifah & Zibin 2022).

Moreover, when analyzing the conceptualization of LOVE and BELOVED in both Spanish and Arabic, it is important to observe that specific metaphorical connections remain unchanged. The common cultural domain of linking LOVE with PAIN and SUFFERING and THE BELOVED with a KILLER is apparent in both languages. This similarity can be ascribed to historical and cultural elements, specifically the interconnected past of Arabs and Spaniards during the Al-Andalus era. It could be argued that this historical connection has influenced the development of shared metaphorical patterns pertaining to the concepts of LOVE and the BELOVED. The metaphorical correlation between LOVE and SUFFERING is grounded in the literary traditions of both Arabic and Spanish cultures. This acknowledges the challenges and complexities inherent in romantic relationships.

When comparing and contrasting the results of the current study with the findings from the relevant literature, interesting similarities and differences are revealed. Khalifah & Zibin (2022) focus on cognitive perspectives, which is in line with current research. Both highlight the importance of comprehending metaphors in literary texts for successful translation. However, it appears that the differences that exist in the translations of metaphors from Arabic to English are more pronounced than the differences observed in translations from Spanish to Arabic. Therefore, it can be suggested that the cognitive model of LOVE and BELOVED could be comparable in Spanish and Arabic. In this model, source domains such as PAIN, SUFFERING, WOUND, KILLER, and others are considered to be typical members (cf. Kövecses 2014). Park's (2009) research on the influence of culture on metaphor translation provides further support for the central role of cultural models in achieving equivalent translations, as argued in this study. The analysis of metaphor translation strategies conducted by Dagnev & Chervenkova (2020), Mudaghmesh & Allawzi (2023), Chita & Stavrou (2020), Hasar & Panahbar (2017), as well as Ritchie & Zhao (2020), offers a wider perspective on the various methods used in distinct linguistic and cultural environments. Nevertheless, differences emerge, especially when considering stylistic elements, canonical works, and poetry. Ali's (2006) warnings about the challenges of translating metaphors align with specific obstacles identified in this study, emphasizing the importance of a thoughtful methodology. This study demonstrates the individuality of the current investigation within the wider field of metaphor translation studies.

The discussion emphasizes the need to preserve metaphorical depth while adapting to the linguistic and cultural context of the target culture. Additionally, the analysis reveals metaphorical patterns in how LOVE and the BELOVED are conceptualized across various linguistic backgrounds.

This analysis has important implications for translation studies. First, it highlights the need for cultural sensitivity and thoughtful decision-making in translating metaphors. Remaining faithful to the ST may seem ideal; however, this study shows that translators often need to adapt metaphors, so they appeal to the target audience while keeping the original meaning intact. The instances where direct translation fell short emphasize the necessity for translators to look beyond literal meanings and consider the cultural context and the potential effects of metaphors on their readers.

Secondly, this study adds to the growing research on cognitive approaches to translation through providing real-world evidence of how cognitive processes such as conceptual mapping and image reproduction function in translation. We can better understand the cognitive processes involved in navigating differences across languages and cultures through looking closely at the strategies used by the translator in *La Sombra del Viento*. Such insights can help develop translator training programs, e.g. AI translation, giving future translators a better understanding of the cognitive aspects of their work.

6. Conclusion

The analysis of metaphor translation in *La Sombra del Viento* and its Arabic equivalent reveals several strategies employed in translating metaphors from Spanish to Arabic. These strategies, including direct image reproduction, same metaphor combined with sense to enhance the image, and replacement of the source language (SL) image with a culturally appropriate target language (TL) image, demonstrate a careful approach to maintaining the original metaphors while ensuring cultural appropriateness in the TL. The study found that, despite linguistic differences, the cognitive model of LOVE and BELOVED shows similarities between Spanish and Arabic. This suggests that there could be common metaphorical patterns influenced by historical and cultural variables. The study highlights the importance of cogno-cultural models in establishing equivalent translations and emphasizes the need for an analytical approach to address potential challenges in translating metaphors. This research contributes to the understanding of metaphor translation through demonstrating the importance of careful decisions in bridging linguistic and cultural differences, which preserves metaphorical depth and recognizes shared metaphorical patterns across linguistic traditions. Future research could investigate specific factors that influence the choice to adapt or replace metaphors, such as the text's genre, the target audience's familiarity with the source culture, and the overall purpose of the translation. Future studies could also explore metaphor translation in other linguistic contexts, particularly between languages from different families.

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Aseel Zibin

*Department of English Language and Literature
School of Foreign Languages
University of Jordan
Amman, Jordan, 11942
Email: a.zabin@ju.edu.jo*

Renad Al-Momani

*Department of European Languages
School of Foreign Languages
University of Jordan
Amman, Jordan, 11942
Email: r.momani@ju.edu.jo*

Areej Allawzi

*Department of English Language and Literature
School of Foreign Languages
University of Jordan
Amman, Jordan, 11942
Email: A.Allawzi@ju.edu.jo*

Dina Salman

*Department of English Language and Literature
School of Foreign Languages
University of Jordan
Amman, Jordan, 11942
Email: dina.salman@ju.edu.jo*

Multimodal Translation and Ideological Representation in Picture Books: A Case Study of *King and King*

Roberto Martínez Mateo, Universidad de Castilla La Mancha

Abstract

This paper presents a multimodal contrastive analysis of the picture book King and King (De Haan & Nijland 2000) and its Spanish translation. By integrating Halliday's (2004) functional systemic linguistics, Kress & van Leeuwen's (2006) social semiotics, and Nikolajeva & Scott's (2001) taxonomy of text–image relationships—expanded by Martínez (2022)—the study explores how linguistic and visual choices interact to construct and translate representations of non-traditional princesses and homosexual couples. The analysis reveals that translation decisions are influenced by the visual narrative, resulting in linguistic modulations that challenge traditional gender stereotypes. Findings show that complementary, expanding, and counterpoint relations between text and image play a pivotal role in shaping inclusive meanings and redefining the portrayal of gender and sexuality in the target text. The study concludes that picture book translation is an ideologically charged, multimodal process through which translators act as mediators of cultural and ethical values.

Keywords: *gender stereotypes, multimodality, picture book translation, text–image interaction, inclusivity*

1. Introduction

Picture books (PBs) have long proven to be an invaluable resource for addressing complex and sensitive topics within the educational and cultural spheres (Evans 2015). Built upon narrative and visual interaction, PBs provide an engaging medium through which issues like identity, equality, and diversity can be explored in accessible yet profound ways (Colomer 2018). As Fernández (1996) notes, one of the challenges in studying children's literature is the fluidity of its definition, which encompasses a wide range of multimodal texts—from illustrated albums to digital adaptations—making it both heterogeneous and theoretically rich (O'Sullivan 2013).

Another issue confronted by PBs is that the critical perception of the public was that, as it falls within the scope of children's literature, they did not deserve to be called “literature”, but something second-rate, with a few notable and time-honored exceptions (Lathey 2016: 17). Added to this, the didactic purpose of PBs has justified the great abuses they have undergone (Alderete & Owen 2019), arguing that they were done for the benefit of infancy, PBs' theoretical main audience. It is precisely this formative-didactic value what has led to turn the PB into a dangerous genre for those who made a biased use of PBs (Fernández 2000: 232). Historically, PBs were often dismissed as inferior or didactic tools (Lathey 2016), yet recent scholarship has demonstrated their complexity as multimodal cultural artefacts capable of shaping ideological values. Through their visual and verbal narratives, PBs act as semiotic systems that transmit collective memories, beliefs, and social models (Svensson 2020). This influence renders them powerful vehicles for ideological negotiation, especially in translation, where linguistic and cultural transfers intersect.

In the last two decades, translation studies has increasingly addressed the role of PBs as sites of ideological and multimodal negotiation (Oittinen 2000; Kümmerling-Meibauer 2015). Authors such as Shavit (1986), O’Sullivan (2013), and Lathey (2016) have examined how translation mediates between cultures, particularly in relation to adaptation, censorship, and visual-verbal interaction. Leonardi (2020) expands this discussion by framing translation as a dynamic process of ideological propagation, where cultural values and ethical principles are not merely transferred but reshaped. Consequently, the translation of children’s literature becomes a powerful agent in the construction and perpetuation—or transformation—of ideological systems.

PBs are a multimodal ensemble where, as Lathey puts (2016: 55), there happens a sophisticated orchestration of text and image that demands a deep knowledge of multimodality and semiotics. It is precisely this text-image interaction which calls for a multidisciplinary approach from multimodal and critical discourse analysis. Hence, research in multimodal works has gained momentum and has already become a trendy research avenue in children’s books translation (Kümmerling-Meibauer 2015; Oittinen et al. 2018).

Amongst other scholars, Colomer (2010) and Pascua Febles (2016) highlight the fact that children’s literature has become more prone to cover topics previously regarded as inappropriate for children, namely gender stereotypes and homosexuality, to cite but a few. Despite this step forward, it has been checked that those PBs where these delicate issues are not central to the development of the story are more easily accepted (Febles 2016: 118).

PBs are part of the larger textual genre of children’s literature; yet they hold their particularities. The distinguishing feature of a PB is its graphic preponderance in quantitative terms. Here, illustrations cannot just be a mere accompaniment to the textual mode, but an active agent in meaning construction. Thus, a PB “is the result of a relationship between text and images such that neither would make sense in isolation” (Lathey 2016: 58). This intersemiotic connection established between the visual and the textual narrative generates a brand-new meaning construction that always leaves room for a personal interpretation by the reader, whomever it may be, to fill in the unavoidable interpretative gaps (Sipe 1998) on the side of the reader. In addition, translators of PBs are one kind of these possible readers that face the meaning construction of these cultural and social products and are agents who can intervene in the meaning transfer. But with the translator being the first reader, his task to convey meaning from one language/culture into another may result in the transference of unconscious nuances in the target text (TT) that may be imbued by different motives.

As García de Toro (2014) puts it, children’s literature is poliedric and biased as it has traditionally been considered a minor genre. Subsequently, this undervaluation on the hands of the diverse stakeholders has materialised in the cuts, adaptations, omissions, adjustments, and other offensive acts done to children’s literature over the years, as previous studies have extensively proved (Alvstad 2010; Martínez-Mateo 2015; Alderete & Owen 2019). It comes then as no surprise that controlling lobbies in the publishing industry have exerted their various types of influence over the final output of these so-called minor works, with a view to shaping belief systems at their discretion (Shavit 1986). This ideological manipulation in the translation of children’s literature has been made overt over the years on account of ethical and moral issues such as censorship and taboos of sensitive topics (Leonardi 2020). The PB under the magnifying glass here delves into gender studies and, more specifically, gender stereotypes, a question with a long tradition, as prove the numerous works by Sunderland (2012), Janet Evans (2015) and Moya-Guijarro & Cañamares-Torrijos (2020), for example. In particular, the work by Sunderland (2012) delves deep into how gender features are construed through language

and how characters are shaped through linguistic resources to create predetermined gender stereotypes.

Over the past few years, there is a wealth of PBs devoted to gender representations of various types, though they basically study the main characters (Evans & Davies 2000), amongst which some have focused on the many representations of parenting (Sunderland & McGlashan 2010; Moya-Guijarro & Ventola 2022). However, little attention has been paid to analysing the gender-stereotyping of women in secondary characters who also play their part in configuring the reader's cultural conceptions and stereotypes.

A theoretical framework for gender stereotyping moves beyond a simple traditional vs. non-traditional binary. It can be understood as a system of widely shared, oversimplified, and essentialist beliefs about the attributes, behaviours, and social roles deemed appropriate for men and women. These stereotypes are not merely descriptive but are prescriptive and normative, reinforcing a heteropatriarchal ideology that privileges male dominance and heterosexuality. This system often operates through a series of foundational binaries: active/passive, public/private, rational/emotional, and powerful/submissive. In this framework, masculinity is stereotypically associated with the first term of each binary (active, public, rational, powerful), while femininity is confined to the second (passive, private, emotional, submissive). These constructs are not natural but are dynamically produced and reproduced through discourse, including the multimodal discourse of children's literature (Sunderland 2012). Precisely, this preliminary study seeks to be part of an increasingly booming body of research on children's literature and the representations of non-traditional princesses and homosexual couples. Authors interested in these issues, such as Lester (2014) and Soler-Quílez (2016), contend that introducing in PBs characters whose sexual orientation does not fit into heteronormativity could pave the way for shifting the present situation of disregard of non-hegemonic discourses. In the same vein, empirical studies such as Sunderland & McGlashan's (2010) uses a selected corpus to review how visible homoparental families are. While studies increasingly address challenging topics like gender and homosexuality (Colomer 2010; Pascua Febles 2016), little attention has been paid to how translation, as a multimodal process, shapes the portrayal of secondary female characters. This paper fills this gap by investigating the translator's verbal choices in relation to the visual narrative. Despite the emerging trend of publications in this field having already tackled several topics, there are still many which have been understudied, as for example the representation of non-traditional princesses who are not the main characters of their PBs. This study situates itself within this growing field by focusing on *King and King*, a groundbreaking picture book that reimagines the fairy-tale paradigm through the inclusion of a homosexual couple and a diverse array of princesses. The analysis builds on the assumption that gender and sexuality representations are not static entities, but multimodal constructs articulated through text-image interaction and translation. Drawing on Halliday's (2004) ideational metafunction and Ketola's (2017) taxonomy of equivalence, this paper examines how linguistic and visual narratives converge or diverge to construct alternative models of identity.

Accordingly, the objectives of this study are threefold: (a) to analyse the representational metafunction in the source text (ST); (b) to contrast linguistic and visual equivalences between source and target versions; and (c) to determine how text-image relationships, following Nikolajeva & Scott (2001) and Martínez (2022), influence the translator's choices and the construction of gender stereotypes. By combining linguistic, visual, and ideological perspectives, this research seeks to contribute to the expanding body of scholarship on multimodal translation and on the role of translated PBs as instruments of social change.

The sections of this paper are organized as follows. Section 2 provides the theoretical framework and state of the art, outlining the linguistic, multimodal, translational, and ideological foundations that underpin this study and culminating in the integration of these perspectives into a unified analytical model. Section 3 describes the methodology adopted, detailing the procedures for the multimodal and contrastive analysis of *King and King*. Section 4 presents the results derived from the linguistic and visual analyses, highlighting how translation decisions are shaped by the visual narrative. Section 5 summarizes the results and, finally, Section 6 discusses the findings and draws the main conclusions, emphasizing the translator's role as a semiotic and ideological mediator in the construction of inclusive meanings in picture book translation.

2. State of the art

In the last few decades, multimodal studies have flourished in various fields, translation studies included. Amongst the most renowned, we cannot but mention Oittinen (2000) and Lewis (2001) regarding PB translation. The multimodal burden embedded in PBs turns them into a highly sophisticated element where text and illustration intermingle to create new aesthetic wholes that forge new interpretative possibilities (Sipe 2012: 4). As a sign of the complexity of such relation, see the studies by Nodelman (1988), Sipe (1998) and Nikolajeva & Scott (2001). All of them share the common ground that the full understanding of a PB is born from the verbal–textual interrelation. Hence, bearing in mind the dynamic character of the verbal–visual relationship, the meaning of the message would not be complete if only one of these items in this two-legged creature would be considered. That's why it is unavoidable to deal with word–image interplay when trying to untangle the full understanding of a PB. And this task inevitably involves two complementary approaches. One is linguistic, comprising two steps: first, an analysis of the source text and, second, the translational job (target text). The other approach is the one dealing with the multimodal relationship that stirs between words and images whose mutual impact enriches them both to generate new meanings.

2.1. Linguistic foundations

From a linguistic perspective, and given the multimodal nature of PBs, this study uses Halliday's (2004) functional systemic approach to linguistically analyse one of the three metafunctions, the ideational, and to specifically determine the actor, the process, the participants, their attributes, and the circumstances of the narrative. However, as PBs are multimodal products, it is also necessary to consider the communicative task that the visual narrative plays in the transmission of the message in the PB. In this study, we focus on the ideational metafunction which is encoded through the grammatical system of transitivity, and which consists in the linguistic expression of human experience through the processes, participants and associated circumstances that are present in the clause structure.

According to Halliday & Matthiessen (2004: 172), there are various processes that are central (i.e. material, mental and relational), and intermediate ones, such as behavioural (between material and mental), verbal (between mental and relational) and existential (between relational and material). Normally, each process has a type of role associated with it. Thus, in material processes there is an *Actor*, who performs the action, that affects a *Participant* (*Goal/Object*). Mental processes are carried out by a *Sensor/Processor* and affect what is

processed (*Phenomenon*). Relational processes refer to abstract relationships between two or more objects. These relations can be attributive (x belongs to class y) or identifying (x equals y). Moreover, relational processes construct three types of relations depending on the process: intensive (x is y); possessive (x has y) and circumstantial (x is / is in y). In behavioural processes, the actor is called the *Conductor*, and the phenomenon is known as the *Subject*. In verbal processes, the initiator of the linguistic exchange is the *Speaker* who addresses a *Receiver* by means of the *Said/Report*. Existential processes merely indicate that something exists or happens. Finally, there are the circumstantial elements, which are common to all processes and actors and their meaning does not vary to express spatial–temporal location, manner, or cause.

2.2. Multimodal foundations

The pioneering work of Nodelman (1988) and Sipe (1998, 2012) framed PBs as dialogic spaces where words and images interact to construct layered meanings. Nikolajeva & Scott (2001) later formalised this interdependence through their typology of text–image relationships—symmetrical, complementary, expanding, counterpoint, and contradictory—which remains one of the most comprehensive models for understanding visual–verbal intersemiosis. Their work underscores that text and image seldom tell the same story; instead, meaning arises in the interpretive tension between the two modes.

The translation of PBs is a process where the rich multimodal load of the ST must necessarily be kept in mind, which entails not only translating the verbal narrative in isolation, but it must also be considered in its intimate interrelation with the visual narrative, which can condition somehow the way in which the reader (and the translator, who would be its first reader), interprets the words (Nodelman 1988). However, the starting point of any classification of the semiosis generated between text and image, and that of Nikolajeva & Scott (2001) is no exception, is that these two narrative modes never tell the same story. It is precisely this discordance in the content of the message carried by each narrative mode that forces the reader (in this case, the translator) to embark on the task of filling the interpretative gap emerging between what he reads and what he sees. The imaginary space hidden in the interplay between words and images is the central notion of PBs (Styles & Watson 1996). Or in the words of Nodelman (1998: 200), in PBs, the whole is much more than the sum of its parts (in reference to text and image). For this reason, we resort to Nikolajeva & Scott's (2001) classification of word–image relationship, one of the most complete ones. They set five categories to designate text–image interaction in PBs. *Symmetrical* (SYM), when both modes tell the same story; *Complementary* (COM), when both modes complement each other; *Expanding* (EXP), where the images amplify the meaning of the text or vice versa; *Counterpoint* (COU), when the modes collaborate to offer a message that goes beyond their individual scope; *Contradictory* (CON), when they offer contradictory information. Yet, and in view of the examples analysed in this PB, we have found cases where there is a lack of relationship between text and image since one of the modes is not present. Consequently, another category has been added to Nikolajeva & Scott's (2001) classification to reflect this absence of a multimodal (text–image) relationship. This category has been named *Incomplete* (INC) (Martínez 2022) since the message is encoded in only one of the available modes.

Subsequent studies have expanded this typology to accommodate the complexity of contemporary PBs. Martínez (2022) proposed the INC category to describe cases where one mode (visual or verbal) is partially or entirely absent, an addition especially relevant to translation studies. This refinement acknowledges that translators often face situations where verbal transfer cannot fully replicate the multimodal density of the source text, requiring adaptive strategies to maintain coherence and meaning. The inclusion of the INC type thus allows for a more nuanced understanding of multimodal relationships in translation.

2.3. Translation studies and ideological mediation

As for translation and translation studies, it is a relatively new discipline, as Munday (2016) argues, since its founding manifesto (“The name and nature of translation studies”) was presented at the 3rd International Congress of Applied Linguistics held in Copenhagen in 1972. This caters to the fact that in its origins, translation studies has been nourished by other sibling areas of knowledge such as linguistics to outline its first theories. This heritage gave rise to the first postulates that posed the dichotomy between literal translation and free translation. Once these obsolete concepts and practices were overcome, in the 1980s, a paradigm shift in translation studies took place. The main proponent of this change was German functionalism led by Nord (1997), among other authors. Until 1980, the dominant models of translation assessment, as exemplified by Catford, Nida, and Newmark, were fundamentally based on a comparative analysis between the TT and the ST. The ST was the ultimate yardstick for measuring faithfulness, accuracy, and success. The subsequent revolution in translation studies, led by Toury and others, explicitly rejected this product-focused, ST-centric view, shifting attention to the function and reception of the translation within the target culture. This shift is what marks the transition from a primarily linguistic to a cultural and sociological discipline.

The functionalist paradigm in translation shifts the focus from the ST to the contextual and situational conditions of the TT. Instead of evaluating translations as correct or incorrect, functionalism judges them by their adequacy or appropriateness within their communicative context. This approach replaces the traditional notions of formal and dynamic equivalence with functional equivalence, emphasizing the translator’s role in achieving meaning adequacy that is both contextualized—relevant to a specific communicative act—and dynamic—sensitive to the evolving nature of cultures and meanings. Following Jakobson’s (2000) assertion that absolute equivalence is impossible, the translator’s goal becomes achieving functional adequacy by ensuring that the TT produces a suitable response in its audience while remaining faithful to the ST’s intended meaning.

For the study’s analytical purposes, the term *elements* refers to the translation units between which equivalences are drawn. Since scholars disagree on what constitutes a translation unit—ranging from morphemes and words to entire texts—the study adopts Nord’s (1988) practical definition. According to Nord, a translation unit is any segment of the source language or text that the translator treats as a unit during the translation process. This definition allows for flexibility in analysis without engaging in debates over the precise scope or hierarchy of translation units.

In translation studies, the shift from product-oriented to process-oriented approaches (Toury 1995; Nord 1997; Munday 2016) redefined translation as a socio-cultural and functional act rather than a mechanical linguistic operation. Functionalist frameworks such as Nord’s (1988, 2009) and Ketola’s (2017) models foreground adequacy and contextualisation, emphasising that translation must be assessed according to its communicative purpose within

the target culture. In the context of PBs, this perspective is essential, as the translator's role extends beyond linguistic equivalence to include semiotic interpretation and cultural negotiation.

Leonardi (2020) further articulates this view by describing translation as an ideological act that shapes and disseminates cultural values. Within children's literature, this process carries particular ethical weight because young audiences are especially susceptible to the ideological underpinnings of narratives. Consequently, translators act not only as mediators between languages but also as agents who influence the representation of gender, family, and identity.

2.4. Gender, diversity, and representation in picture books

Research in children's literature has increasingly turned toward the study of gender, sexuality, and inclusivity. Authors such as Evans (2015), Sunderland (2012), and Moya-Guijarro & Ventola (2022) have examined how PBs construct or challenge traditional gender roles through both linguistic and visual strategies. These studies underscore the didactic and ideological power of PBs in shaping young readers' perceptions of social norms. Within this broader context, the representation of non-traditional princesses and same-sex couples has emerged as a significant field of inquiry. Scholars such as Lester (2014) and Soler-Quílez (2016) highlight the transformative potential of such portrayals to disrupt heteronormative narratives and broaden the spectrum of acceptable identities in children's literature. Works like *King and King* exemplify this trend, positioning PBs as tools for promoting empathy, diversity, and critical literacy.

2.5. Multimodality and translation of ideologically sensitive content

The translation of ideologically charged PBs—those that address gender diversity, homosexuality, or non-traditional family models—demands heightened multimodal awareness. As Oittinen et al. (2018) argue, translating PBs requires attending to how visual and verbal modes mutually influence meaning. The translator's engagement with visual cues, compositional elements, and emotional tone ensures that the ideological intent of the original is not diluted or distorted in the target version.

Studies such as Moya-Guijarro & Martínez-Mateo (2022) show that translation decisions frequently correlate with visual prompts, particularly in the depiction of gendered actions and emotions. When dealing with unconventional characters—such as active princesses or same-sex partners—translators may employ linguistic strategies that align with or counterbalance the visual narrative. This responsiveness to visual input underscores translation as a multimodal and interpretive act rather than a one-dimensional transfer.

2.6. Theoretical integration

The present study builds on this interdisciplinary foundation, merging linguistic, translational, and multimodal perspectives to analyse *King and King* as a paradigmatic example of inclusive children's literature. It combines Halliday's (2004) model of transitivity for linguistic representation, Ketola's (2017) taxonomy of translation equivalence, and Nikolajeva & Scott's (2001) multimodal classification, expanded by Martínez (2022). By integrating these frameworks, the study seeks to trace how text-image relationships mediate

ideological meaning and how translation choices reshape the representation of gender and sexuality.

In sum, current scholarship supports the view that PB translation is an inherently multimodal and ideological process. Translators operate within overlapping systems of visual interpretation and cultural adaptation, and their decisions significantly affect how readers perceive non-traditional gender identities and same-sex relationships. This study contributes to this growing body of research by providing an empirically grounded, multimodal examination of how such representations are negotiated through the intersemiosis of text and image in *King and King*.

3. Methodology

The method employed in this study is a multimodal content analysis. According to Serafini & Reid (2019: 3), this is a modified version of qualitative content analysis. It is based on various interpretive research designs, also on deductive and inductive argumentation, and theories of multimodality used to study and analyse a given corpus of multimodal occurrences. However, assuming a contrastive multimodal analysis of content demands paying heed to the potentialities and limitations of the verbal and the visual mode of communication. As a result, we will carry out a qualitative contrastive multimodal analysis that constitutes a flexible method to cater for the different aspects of the linguistic and visual content and their relationship. The methodological design is grounded in the assumption that translation in multimodal texts must be interpreted as an intersemiotic and ideological act (Ketola 2017; Oittinen & Ketola 2014; Martínez 2022). Therefore, the analysis seeks not only equivalence at the linguistic level but also functional and ideological adequacy in relation to the visual narrative.

Given its exploratory nature and limited scope, this work constitutes a pilot study focused on the analysis of an illustrated album. The methodologies employed in this study are various, depending on the specific analysis of each section. In the following two sections (4.1 and 4.2), a descriptive-quantitative analysis is carried out; in 4.1, to describe how experience is epitomized through the representational metafunction in the ST and, jointly, to contrastively analyse the linguistic pairs between ST and TT and establish the equivalences between their elements according to the classification proposed by Ketola (2017); in 4.2, to describe the text-image relations according to a taxonomy based on the model of Nikolajeva & Scott (2001). Section 5 presents the outcomes of the analysis, and Section 6 draw up the findings of the paper.

The picture book *King and King*, written by Linda De Haan and Stern Nijland and translated into Spanish by Ediciones Serres (2004), challenges traditional gender stereotypes through the story of a prince urged by his mother to marry a princess and take over the throne. After meeting several princesses from different countries, none appeal to him until he meets Princess Magdalena's brother, Prince Charming, with whom he instantly falls in love and eventually marries. The book addresses themes of diversity, equality, and nontraditional relationships, offering a progressive view of love and gender roles that contrasts with the conventional portrayal of men as active and dominant and women as domestic and passive.

4. Analysis

The analytical process unfolds in the following steps:

1. Selection of representative instances from *King and King* that exemplify gender-related content and translation shifts.
2. Identification of transitivity structures in the ST and TT to determine participant roles and processes.
3. Categorisation of translation equivalences according to Ketola's (2017) model.
4. Cross-referencing with visual data to identify the type of text–image relationship following Nikolajeva & Scott (2001) and Martínez (2022).
5. Interpretive synthesis, where linguistic, visual, and ideological findings are integrated to explain how translation mediates multimodal meaning and ideological stance.

The foregoing sequence provides the methodological architecture for the paper. The analysis proceeds by applying the first four steps to each cluster of representative examples. Therefore, the subsequent sections (4.1 and 4.2) are structured not as separate applications of each step, but as integrated analyses where transitivity and equivalence (Section 4.1) and multimodal intersemiosis (Section 4.2) are examined in relation to the chosen instances. The final interpretive synthesis, detailed in Sections 5 and 6, emerges from these findings, offering a holistic explanation of the translation's ideological mediation.

4.1. Linguistic analysis

According to Halliday (2004), the ideational metafunction makes it possible to express on the linguistic level the Actors (person or thing), the actions performed (Processes), which attribute qualities (Attributes) and are framed in a context. For this purpose, a table has been drawn up in which the most salient instances of ST are listed (see Table 1). As for their translation, the fidelity and degree of linguistic equivalence of the analysed units is reviewed by means of a comparison between ST and TT, bearing in mind the context in which they appear. Thus, the contrastive linguistic study has used the categorisation of equivalent elements proposed by Ketola (2017: 52). This classification establishes six possible categories that correspond to the same number of equivalences to describe the relationship maintained between the linguistic components of ST and TT, i.e., their equivalences in a cross-linguistic translation. Each category has an alphabetical code to facilitate its identification.

Table 1: Textual relations of equivalence between ST and TT items

Code	Description
A	Item of the TT corresponds to its literal verbal equivalent of the ST
B	Item of the TT is more precise than its literal verbal equivalent of the ST
C	Item of the TT is more general than its literal verbal equivalent of the ST
D	Item of the TT does not correspond to its literal verbal equivalent of the ST
E	Item of the TT has no verbal equivalent in the ST
F	Item of the ST has no verbal equivalent in the TT

Due to the length and scope of this paper, a selection of the most representative examples appearing in *King and King* has been extracted for analysis and commentary. The following tables (Tables 2–10) compile these clauses broken down according to their representational function analysis in the ST and paired with their equivalents in the TT grounded in Ketola’s (2017) equivalence taxonomy.

Instance 1 (see Table 2), in which the ST is expressed by means of an existential process (*lived: vivían* ‘who lived’), is transferred to the TT broadening its scope by including the prototypical formula of the story (*Érase una vez* ‘Once upon a time’) which, however, does not find its natural equivalent in the ST (*Once upon a time*). The actors in this existential process have been given descriptive nuances in the TT about their age (*anciana* ‘elderly’, *joven* ‘young’) that do not appear in the ST and that contribute to establish with greater accuracy the range of their ages by expanding their description (linguistic relation code B). Besides, the translation of the circumstantial is codified as C since it is more general in the TT than in the ST.

Table 2: Instance 1. Existential process

	Representational metafunction				
	Actor	Process	Goal	Attribute	Circumstantial
ST	a queen, the young crown prince and the crown kitty	lived			On the tallest mountain above the town
TT	una anciana reina, un joven príncipe heredero y una gata con corona (‘an elderly queen, a young crown prince and a cat wearing a crown’)	Érase una vez (‘Once upon a time’) que vivían (‘who lived’)			en lo alto de una montaña (‘at the top of a mountain’)
Linguistic relation code	B	A			C

The queen is the actor of this material process (*had ruled: llevaba reinando* ‘had been ruling’, see Table 3). In its translation into the TT, the term undergoes a double modulation process. On the one hand, the translator has chosen the noun *dama* (‘lady’) which is a more general term (hence the linguistic code C) since it refers to a very broad collective, instead of choosing the ordinary equivalent which would have been *reina* (‘queen’), which would express in Spanish its more common meaning with greater neatness. On the other hand, the TT adds an age qualifier (*anciana* ‘elderly’) to this noun, which has no equivalent in the ST (linguistic code E). In the same way, the attribute of the relational process of the circumstantial character (*very tired*) incorporates the quality of *harta* (‘fed up’) which has no correspondence with any element of the ST (linguistic code E) and implies an extension of the information exclusively offered by the textual narrative about the mood of the old woman.

Table 3: Instance 2. Material process

	Representational metafunction				
	Actor	Process	Goal	Attribute	Circumstantial
ST	The queen	had ruled			for many long years
TT	La anciana dama (‘The elderly queen’)	llevaba reinando (‘had been reigning’)			ya muchos años ... (‘for many (long) years’)
Linguistic relation code	C / E	A			A
ST	and she	was		tired	
TT	y (ella) (‘and she’)	estaba (‘was’)		harta y muy cansada (‘fed up and very tired’)	
Linguistic relation code	A	A		B / E	

While the ST material process is expressed with the verb *to make* (see Table 4), whose semantic scope is rather ample, when it is transferred to the TT, its meaning is rendered much more precisely with the verb *ceder* ('give in') (linguistic code B) which the translator chose instead of its more common English equivalent, in similar contexts, which would be the verb *hacer que* ('make'). The ST actor is not manifested and appears as implicit when referring to *all that talking*. However, when translated into Spanish, the actor is made explicit when referring to *la reina* ('the queen') (linguistic code B). On the other hand, the translation of the attribute *dizzy* into Spanish turns the word category into a different one when the adverb of manner *completamente* ('completely') is used, which modulates the degree of the quality (linguistic code B) but lacks an equivalent in the ST (linguistic code E).

Table 4: Instance 3. Material process 2

	Representational metafunction				
	Actor	Process	Goal	Attribute	Circumstantial
ST	all that talking	had made	the Prince	dizzy	by the evening,
TT	La reina siguió hablando y hablando (‘The queen kept talking and talking’)	por fin, cedió (‘and she finally gave in’)	y el príncipe (‘and the prince’)	completamente mareado (‘completely dizzy’)	hasta la noche (‘until nightfall’)
Linguistic relation code	B	B	A	B / E	A

In Table 5, in the circumstantial, the adverbial phrase *No sooner* is used to indicate that one event happens immediately after another. It is frequently associated with a verb tense, the past perfect, and is followed by the preposition *than*. Therefore, since it is linked to the past perfect tense, the event to which it refers (event 1, *had finished*) occurred at an older time in the past in relation to the other event mentioned (event 2, *was shown*), which happens in a later past. In this case, event 1, *had finished*, should be prior to the 2nd event, *was shown (to the door)*. However, the translation of this temporal marker (*No sooner*) inverts the order of events in the TT and it is *Pero antes de que* ('But before it was finished') when *she had already been shown (to the door)*. This temporal inversion of events further emphasizes the fact that they did not even let her finish (linguistic code D) thus altering the given order of the ST.

Table 5: Instance 4. Circumstantial phrase

	Representational metafunction				
	Actor	Process	Goal	Attribute	Circumstantial
ST	she	had finished	she was shown to the door		No sooner
TT	(ella)	acabara (‘finished’)	ya la habían echado (‘they had already sent her out of the room’)		Pero antes de que (‘But before it was finished’)
Linguistic relation code	A	A	B		D

When transferring this material process (see Table 6, *had flown*) to the TT (*llegó haciendo* ‘arrived performing’), its meaning in the original has been made less concrete (linguistic code C). On the other hand, the object of this process, *with her magic act*, has acquired a greater degree of specificity than its ST equivalent by adding *malabarismos* (‘juggling’) (code B), which is not necessarily an inherent part of a magic act.

Table 6: Instance 5. Material process 3

	Representational metafunction				
	Actor	Process	Goal	Attribute	Circumstantial
ST	Princess Dolly	had flown	with her magic act		all the way from Texas
TT	La princesa Dolly (‘Princess Dolly’)	llegó... (‘arrived’) haciendo... (‘performing’)	malabarismos y magia (‘magic and juggling’)		desde Texas (‘from Texas’)
Linguistic relation code	A	C	B		A

In Table 7, what in the ST is a material process (*to come*) has been transferred to TT as a relational process of circumstantial character (*La siguiente fue una sonriente princesa* ‘Next **was** a smiling princess’). Moreover, in this instance 6, it is worth noting the translation into Spanish of the adjective *funny* by an unusual *sonriente* (‘smiling’). According to the Cambridge English-Spanish online dictionary, its first two entries are: 1. Making you smile or laugh; 2. Strange or unusual and not what you expect. Considering only the linguistic level, the more likely translation proposals for this term would be *graciosa* (‘funny, amusing’) or *rara* (‘weird, odd’), instead of the equivalent proposed here, *sonriente* (‘smiling’) (linguistic code D). As a result, this choice adopted by the translator hints at the possibility that something else was taken into consideration in the meaning construction process.

Table 7: Instance 6. Material process 4

	Representational metafunction				
	Actor	Process	Goal	Attribute	Circumstantial
ST	the funny princess	came		from Greenland	Next
TT	una sonriente princesa (‘a smiling princess’)	Fue (‘was’)		que llegó de Groenlandia (‘came from Greenland’)	La siguiente (‘Next’)
Linguistic relation code	D	A		A	A

The ST clause is expressed in an active voice sentence by means of a material process (*to hit it off*, see Table 8) which is usually associated with informal contexts and accompanied by the adverb *either* to deny something again after having done it previously. In this case, *either* refers to the fact that it did not impress the Prince. It is also noteworthy to remark that in Spanish, the original clause has been turned around to express it through an adversative subordinate clause, introduced by the conjunction *pero* (‘except’) (linguistic code D) where the material process *se enamoró perdidamente de ella* (‘fell madly in love with her’) (linguistic code B) is more precise than its ST equivalent. However, the object of that process which in the ST is limited to the two actors involved (the prince and the princess of Greenland), in the TT refers to a general, much broader addressee (namely by means of the indefinite pronoun *nadie* ‘nobody’).

On the other hand, the instance continues with a causal subordinate clause in the ST introduced by the conjunction *so* whose translation into Spanish does not correspond to the original (code D) since it is translated as *salvo* (‘except’), an adversative conjunction that in this context means *except* and which differs from the causal sense of the conjunction in the ST. Moreover, this phrase is expressed by means of a mental process (*enamorarse* ‘to fall in love’) whose scope and intensity (*perdidamente* ‘deeply/madly’) are expressed in its Spanish version,

although it lacks equivalent in the ST (code B). These instances point at the fact that other factors, information, must have been taken into account when translating the textual narrative.

Table 8: Instance 7. Material process 5

	Representational metafunction				
	Actor	Process	Goal	Attribute	Circumstantial
ST	The Prince	didn't hit... off with	her either		
TT	the prince	no impresionó (‘did not impress’)	a nadie (‘anyone’)		Pero (‘But’)
Linguistic relation code	A	B	D		E
ST	he	really didn't mind	when his page promptly	fell in love with her	so
TT	que (‘that’)		el paje del príncipe (‘the prince's page’)	se enamoró perdidamente de ella (‘fell madly in love with her’)	Salvo (‘except’)
Linguistic relation code	A		C	B	D

In Table 9, the ST instance is embodied by a material process (*to shed*) accompanied by the object *a tear* whose equivalent in English would have been *derramó una lágrima* (‘shed a tear’) instead of the option chosen, *lloraba* (‘was crying’). However, the TT in Spanish dispenses with the object of the ST to incorporate a circumstantial complement in its place to indicate that this process was carried out without interruption (*sin parar* ‘incessantly’), which lacks an equivalent in the ST (code E).

Table 9: Instance 8. Material process 6

	Representational metafunction				
	Actor	Process	Goal	Attribute	Circumstantial
ST	The queen	even shed	a tear		
TT	La reina (‘The queen’)	Lloraba (‘wept’)			sin parar (‘incessantly’)
Linguistic relation code	A	C	F		E

In Table 10, the first part of the ST instance takes the form of a mental verb (*to know*) in passive voice that is transferred to the TT with an existential verb (*vivir* ‘to live’) where the sensor (the two princesses) and the phenomenon (King and King) refer to the same people. In addition, the TT has a temporal circumstantial phrase (*Desde entonces* ‘Since then’, code E) that does not appear in the original. The second part of the instance presents a relational process with the verb *to have* that is translated into the TT by a material verb (*descansar* ‘to rest’) inserted in the verbal periphrasis *poder + infinitivo* (‘to be able to/can + infinitive’) to show the possibility of the semantics expressed by the infinitive, which does not coincide with the translation of the equivalent segment in the ST (code D). When comparing the ST and TT processes of this instance, we observe how their translation differs from some of the possible common equivalents expected for such segments. This lack of semantic agreement between syntactically equivalent elements leads us to think that there must be other reasons that motivate such choices and that we will delve into later.

Table 10: Instance 9. Existential process

	Representational metafunction				
	Actor	Process	Goal	Attribute	Circumstantial
ST	The two princes	are known as	King and King		
TT	los principes (‘the princes’)	viven juntos (‘had lived together’)	como Rey y Rey (‘as King and King’)		Desde entonces (‘Since then’)

Linguistic relation code	A	D	A		E
ST	the queen	has some time	for herself		finally
TT	y la reina (‘and the queen’)	puede descansar (‘could rest’)			por fin (‘finally’)
Linguistic relation code	A	D	B		A

In this section, we have analysed the representational metafunction in a selection of instances on the linguistic level where semantic discordances between comparable elements can be observed. These occurrences spark the curiosity to seek a plausible explanation that could be borne in the intersemiosis generated between the verbal and the visual narratives which is studied in the next section.

4.2. Text-image intersemiosis

After the linguistic analysis, the pairs of equivalences explored in the previous section are compared with the visual information of the ST. Now, following Nikolajeva & Scott’s (2001) typology of PB relationships between text and image expanded by Martínez’s (2022), this section deepens the multimodal analysis of *King and King* by focusing on how the interaction between verbal and visual narratives contributes to constructing non-traditional gender identities and same-sex relationships. These relationships are not merely aesthetic configurations; they function ideologically as semiotic mechanisms through which the translator mediates between the visual input and the target-culture expectations.

Symmetrical (SYM) relations—where both modes communicate essentially the same information—are rare in *King and King*, precisely because the album’s subversive ideology relies on multimodal tension rather than redundancy. Still, certain introductory scenes, such as the presentation of the royal family (“a queen, the young crown prince and the crown kitty”, De Haan & Nijland 2000: n.p.), display a near-symmetrical correspondence between text and image, providing narrative stability before the ideological disruption that follows.

More frequent are complementary (COM) relationships, in which each mode supplies information that completes the other, resulting in cohesive meaning. For instance, the depiction of *Princess Dolly* (see Image 1) performing a *magic act* in the ST, rendered as *malabarismos y magia* (‘juggling and magic’) in the TT, illustrates a case of complementary expansion. The translator’s lexical specification responds to the visual depiction of the princess juggling, aligning the textual element with the visual narrative. This synergy not only refines the depiction but also challenges the traditional passivity of princesses: Dolly’s self-presentation as an active performer signals agency, mobility, and occupational identity. The verbal precision in Spanish, motivated by the image, thus reinforces the ideological stance of the book towards empowered femininity.

Figure 1: Princess Dolly

Thus, the visual narrative presents us with an atypical princess whose visual representation is closer to that of a circus performer than that of a member of royalty. The following image (Figure 2) shows us again another princess who departs from the traditional canons usually associated to the members of the royal houses.

Figure 2: The Princess of Greenland

The most ideologically productive interactions are those of counterpoint (COU) and contradictory (CON) types, where verbal and visual cues diverge or collide to invite critical interpretation. A notable case is the portrayal of the Princess of Greenland. The analysis focuses on a segment classified as type D, which represents the actor in a material process and plays a key semantic role in the image's verbal conceptualization. The phrase *the funny princess* was translated as *princesa sonriente* ('a smiling princess'), a choice that diverges from expected equivalents given the visual context. The princess, depicted with childish attire, pigtails, large glasses, and imperfect teeth, conveys an image closer to *strange* or *peculiar* than simply *smiling*. By highlighting only her smile, the translator overlooks the overall visual cues and foregrounds a positive affect while toning down the visual strangeness, creating a COU relationship between the verbal and visual narratives. The dissonance between textual mildness

and visual peculiarity generates irony and stimulates interpretive agency, encouraging readers to reconsider what counts as beauty by presenting conflicting character portrayals.

A similar counterpoint arises in the closing scene doublespread (Figures 3 and 4) when the text and image jointly redefine masculinity through domestic tranquillity. The two princes' serene posture and gentle engagement in a leisure activity (EXP) visually undermine the hyperactive, heroic masculinity typical of fairy-tale princes. The ST's mental process *are known as King and King* is rendered as the existential *viven juntos como Rey y Rey* ('lived together as King and King'). This translation, prompted by the everyday scene depicted, shifts the focus from external recognition (social naming) to internal experience (shared life), thereby humanizing the homosexual couple and aligning with contemporary discourses of normalisation and inclusivity.

Figures 3 and 4: Playing chess

Along the same lines, the other ST process, a relational process (*to have*), is transferred to the TT as a material process in the form of a verbal periphrasis (*poder + descansar* 'to be able + rest'). Once again, we witness how it is plausible to consider the possibility that the image showing how the queen appears placidly lying in a hammock sunbathing would have led the translator to opt for the periphrasis *can rest* instead of what would be a translation equivalent more in line with the TO, such as *have time for her* (Table 10).

Martínez's (2022) addition of the INC category proves valuable in accounting for moments when one semiotic mode is absent or underrepresented. In *King and King*, these occur when the TT omits verbal reference to a visual cue, such as gestures or background elements. For example, the mountain landscape in the opening spread—visually emphasizing three hills of almost equal height—is simplified in the TT (*en lo alto de una montaña* 'on top of a mountain'), eliminating the superlative of the ST (*on the tallest mountain*). The translator's decision can be interpreted as visually motivated moderation: since the illustration minimizes height difference, the linguistic attenuation achieves coherence at the expense of verbal emphasis. Such incomplete correlations highlight the translator's interpretive agency and demonstrate how omissions can serve coherence rather than loss.

5. Results

This article examines how the interaction between visual and textual narratives in a PB influences the translator's treatment of gender stereotypes. An analysis of 39 translation instances revealed that while nearly half (19) used literal equivalents (code A), the rest showed varying degrees of modification: 9 made meanings more precise (code B), 5 generalised them (code C), and another 5 diverged completely from the source (code D). A few rare cases fell under codes E and F. Similar trends appeared in object and attribute translations, where literal equivalents were often replaced by generalized or imprecise alternatives. The study also highlights how images shaped translation choices—for example, translating *magic act* as *juggling* due to its visual depiction, and replacing *are known as* with *live together* to better reflect the visual portrayal of two kings enjoying a shared activity. Overall, the findings show that visual context significantly guided translation decisions, leading to shifts in meaning and characterization.

6. Discussion and conclusions

This study has examined how the verbal and visual narratives of *King and King* (De Haan & Nijland 2000) interact in translation to construct inclusive representations of gender and sexuality. Drawing upon Halliday's (2004) representational metafunction, Ketola's (2017) taxonomy of translation equivalence, and the multimodal typology of Nikolajeva & Scott (2001) extended by Martínez (2022), the research demonstrates that PB translation is a multimodal and ideological act. The translator emerges not merely as a linguistic intermediary but as a semiotic interpreter who negotiates between the source text's visual cues and the target culture's ideological expectations.

Across these relationship types, the translator emerges as a mediator between the semiotic resources of the PB and the ideological norms of the target culture. Complementary (COM) and expanding (EXP) relations tend to normalize inclusivity by aligning the verbal and visual modes towards coherence and empathy. Counterpoint (COU) and contradictory (CON) relations, by contrast, destabilize heteropatriarchal norms, compelling readers to negotiate meaning and recognize difference. Incomplete (INC) relations, finally, expose the translational negotiation itself—moments in which cultural adaptation or visual fidelity guide verbal attenuation.

The findings reveal that translation choices in *King and King* are significantly influenced by the visual narrative, which often guides linguistic modulation and re-interpretation. COM and EXP text–image relationships foster coherence between verbal and visual elements, promoting inclusivity through depictions of active female characters and normalised portrayals of same-sex love. Conversely, COU and CON relationships generate interpretive tension, inviting critical reflection on conventional notions of gender and beauty. INC relationships, in which one mode is absent or reduced, highlight the translator’s role in maintaining coherence and meaning when textual and visual information diverge.

Through these varied semiotic relations, the translator’s interventions subtly reshape the ideological fabric of the narrative. For instance, the amplification of the queen’s emotional state in the Spanish translation (*harta y muy cansada* ‘fed up and very tired’) aligns with visual cues to enrich character depth, while the shift from *are known as* to *viven juntos* (‘lived together’) transforms external social recognition into a portrayal of domestic intimacy. These examples illustrate how translation mediates not only language but also the ethical and cultural meanings embedded in multimodal storytelling.

From an ideological standpoint, the study underscores that translated PBs operate as dynamic spaces of negotiation where cultural, ethical, and aesthetic values intersect. Translators, as the first readers and mediators, engage in acts of ideological positioning through their interpretive responses to visual and verbal stimuli. In *King and King*, these responses contribute to the deconstruction of heteronormative and patriarchal narratives, encouraging empathy and inclusivity. The translation thus functions as a site of resistance, re-articulating familiar fairy-tale conventions to promote diversity and acceptance.

Pedagogically, these findings reinforce the potential of PBs as tools for fostering critical literacy and social awareness. By exposing young readers to alternative models of love, identity, and gender expression, PBs like *King and King* contribute to developing open-minded and ethically reflective audiences. As Cerrillo (2016) argues, children’s literature plays a foundational role in shaping the social imaginary, and when translated across cultures, it carries the additional responsibility of bridging ideological and linguistic boundaries.

The results of this study highlight the translator’s dual agency as both a linguistic artisan and a multimodal reader. Translation in PBs involves decoding visual messages, interpreting emotional tone, and reconstructing ideological nuances through language. This process often entails balancing faithfulness to the source with sensitivity to the target culture’s sociocultural context. The translator’s interpretive agency becomes especially visible in moments of multimodal dissonance—when text and image diverge—and in the deliberate modulations that enhance coherence or mitigate potential cultural friction.

In sum, this study provides a holistic understanding of *King and King* as a multimodal construct. It recognises the translator’s dual role as linguistic mediator and semiotic interpreter, highlighting how visual cues guide verbal decisions that ultimately shape the ideological and aesthetic identity of the translated PB.

As a pilot study, this research focuses on a single PB and therefore does not aim for statistical generalization. Its strength lies in its qualitative depth, offering detailed insights into multimodal translation processes. Future studies could expand the corpus to include multiple PBs addressing gender and sexuality across different linguistic and cultural contexts. Comparative analyses could further elucidate how translators from diverse backgrounds negotiate similar ideological tensions or employ distinct multimodal strategies.

Additionally, future research might explore reception-oriented perspectives, examining how young readers in different cultures interpret multimodal cues in translated PBs. Such studies would deepen our understanding of how translation mediates ideological meanings not only at the textual level but also at the level of reader response and cultural pedagogy.

Ultimately, this research confirms that the translation of PBs like *King and King* transcends the boundaries of linguistic transfer. It is a multimodal, interpretive, and ethical endeavour where text–image intersemiosis shapes new forms of cultural understanding. Through the interplay of COM, counterpoint, and EXP relationships, translators contribute to redefining gender roles, family models, and affective diversity in children’s literature.

The translated PB thus emerges as a transformative artefact—a space where the convergence of linguistic creativity, visual literacy, and ideological reflection opens pathways toward more inclusive representations. By bridging textual and cultural worlds, the translator affirms the ethical potential of translation as an act of social and artistic mediation, one that empowers readers to imagine and embrace plural and equitable forms of humanity.

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Roberto Martínez-Mateo
Universidad de Castilla La Mancha
Facultad de Educación. Campus de Cuenca
Avenida de los Alfares s/n. 16071
Cuenca, Spain
Email: roberto.martinez@uclm.es

Feminist Translation Strategies Revisited

Eivor Jordà Mathiasen, Universitat de València – IULMA

Abstract

The aim of this work is to present an overview of feminist translation strategies, to carry out a comparative analysis and to offer a unified proposal of classification. The existence of multiple proposals for feminist translation strategies seems to call for a comparative analysis and a unifying classification. The study will focus on the classical theories from the North American schools (Flotow 1991; Lotbinière-Harwood 1991; Levine 1991; Simon 1996; Massardier-Kenney 1997, and Maier 1998) which set the trend and are most frequently cited, but also on other later proposals that have tried to present some kind of systematic classification and that involve a type of innovative contribution (Flotow 2019; Wallmach 2007; Pas & Zaborowska 2017, and Lee 2023). What has been observed in the results is both a terminological confusion (with overlapping or partially synonymous terms) and also a confusion revolving around the different linguistic levels to be considered. This study can help translators obtain an overview of the different feminist translation strategies described in the past, as well as to understand the different moments throughout the translation process in which they can be applied.

Keywords: *gender and translation; feminist translation; translation strategies*

1. Introduction

Discussing feminist translation is inherently complex, as it should not be regarded as a singular, unified movement but rather as a field encompassing multiple perspectives and ongoing debate, paralleling the diverse ways in which feminism itself is understood. Nevertheless, certain common objectives can be identified, including the recovery and valorization of works authored by women, the critique of distorted translations of feminist texts, and the transformation of sexist language to contribute to the construction of a non-patriarchal society. In this regard, Castro's (2008: 288) definition remains particularly useful, characterizing feminist translation as a current of intellectual and practical work that advocates for the integration of feminist ideology into translation processes, arising from the necessity to articulate new modes of expression aimed at dismantling the patriarchal structures embedded within language and society.

To date, feminist translation theory has addressed a number of issues of great relevance for an understanding of the relationship between gender and translation, such as the *universal woman subject* (construct of a universal category of *woman*), *womanhandling* (active manipulation of a text by a woman translator) or *intersectionality* (particular experience of privilege/oppression of individuals by the confluence of their race, gender, class, etc.). However, the analysis of more practical issues, such as the possible strategies applicable to feminist translation, also seems indispensable, since the conversion from theory into practice is not always so evident. With a simple reading of the different proposals for feminist translation strategies drawn from the classical theories of the North American schools (Flotow 1991; Lotbinière-Harwood 1991; Levine 1991; Simon 1996; Massardier-Kenney 1997, or

Maier 1998), and from more recent proposals that aim at a certain systematisation (Wallmach 2007; Pas & Zaborowska 2017; Flotow 2019, or Lee 2023), we realize that there is a remarkable disparity of proposals and also a certain terminological dispersion. In our opinion, translators could benefit from a new proposal for the definition and classification of feminist translation strategies that brings together all the proposals mentioned above. In this respect we follow the work of Molina & Hurtado (2002: 506–07), who came to the same conclusion as regards general translation strategies.

Therefore, the aim of this paper is to review the main proposals for the classification of feminist translation strategies in order to establish a comparative analysis and offer a unified proposal that provides translators with an overview of feminist translation strategies; at the same time, it will allow them to obtain an overall idea and understand the different applications of these strategies depending on the linguistic level or the perspective from which the translation is approached. To this end, after an introduction to feminist translation, the paper is divided into two parts. In the first part, each proposal is outlined, including the corresponding denomination, definition and examples of the strategies proposed. In the second part, a comparative analysis of the proposals is carried out, and a unified classification proposal is presented in which the strategies have been grouped into four general categories: *intratextual strategies*, *peritextual strategies*, *procedural strategies* and *publishing strategies*.

2. Feminist translation

European history has provided us with remarkable examples of translators who, in some way, rebelled against the misogyny present in patriarchal language and who contributed towards developing a literary culture with a feminist touch. In this regard, Simon (1996) offers a comprehensive account of experiences of women from different periods who managed to enter the literary world through translation, due to the secondary role traditionally assigned both to women and translation, which led to the assumption that these two terms were somehow synergic. On the one hand, women were not allowed to be authors but were “confined to a subordinate writing role” (39). On the other hand, translation could work as a “strong mode of expression for women” (3). In the English of the 16th and 17th centuries, Robinson (1995) sees a process of “feminisation” of translation, as women used translation to obtain a public voice. Here we find figures such as Mary Sidney or Margaret Tyler, who stated “it is all one for a woman to pen a storie, as for a man to addresse his storie to a woman” (Tyler 1578: Aii). Aphra Behn stood out among the 17th century English women translators for her sophisticated work and comments on the right of women to be part of literature as *translatresses*. In the 18th and 19th centuries, women translators used translation in the service of political causes, as was the case of Madame de Staël, Margaret Fuller or Eleanor Marx, who also demonstrated their commitment to equality for women. The passage from the 19th to the 20th century leaves us with the names of women translators such as Constance Garnett and Jean Starr Untermeyer. So, although translation has traditionally been seen as a marginal activity, women have often perceived it as a means of self-expression since their access to original authorship was limited at best.

Feminist translation as a different way of understanding writing and translation owes its inspiration to the patriarchal and phallogocentric perspective that has shaped the concept of translation, mainly in the Western world. Gender-based power relations have always occupied a central place in the imagery of translation theory, where the reproductive work of women/translators has been seen as an undervalued activity. This has been the case from the very first mention of the notion of fidelity by Horace (18 B.C.); through Drant (1567), who justified the hijacking and penetration of the original text; via Florio (1603: A2), who stated that all translations are defective, since they are *reputed femalls, delivered at second hand*, to Gilles Ménage's recurring expression *les belles infidèles*, coined in the 17th century, to Schleiermacher (1813: 8) and his plea to honour *der Muttersprache* ('the mother tongue'). This tradition continues with Steiner (1975: 298), who identifies the translator with a man who has to "penetrate" the translation (obviously a woman) violently. Most of these metaphors have been excellently discussed by Chamberlain (1988). Fortunately, in response to all this, a new rhetoric of translation has been developed, one with new metaphors that displace all those that are based on a patriarchal perspective of translation (Castro 2009: 6).

Meanwhile, an interdisciplinary movement emerged in Quebec at the end of the 1970s which, as part of the cultural turn in translation studies, sought to link ideology studies in translation with those focusing on gender and translation, with a clear holistic intention in search of justice and equality. As Castro & Ergun (2017: 15) explain, this movement started with "women writers whose experimental texts attempted to reinscribe femininity in language and deconstruct hegemonic male-centric discourses through conscious manipulation of language". More specifically, Simon (1996: vii) establishes the moment in 1986 when the idea of feminist translation first emerged in the context of the Canadian cultural dialogue during a panel discussion on "feminist poetics" organised in 1986. It was then that something that had been brewing from the late 1970s and the 1980s onwards in Quebec had come into existence, namely a practice we could call Canadian feminist translation. This happened at a time when a strong movement of English to French experimental feminist translation was taking place.

Since then, feminist translation has been written about prolifically, many of the discussions focusing on the concepts of particularity and universality. As Tissot (2017: 27) points out, transnational feminist movements have questioned the so-called "universal woman subject", as well as the numerous attempts of women of the First World "to talk on behalf of every woman". So, instead of constructing a theory of hegemonic oppression under a unified category of gender, Crenshaw (1991), for instance, coined the term *intersectionality* to denote multiple systems of domination in which other factors such as race, social class, religion, sexual identity and so on play important roles as well. Others, such as Grewal & Kaplan (1994: 17), have argued for the need to unmask the multiple, overlapping and discrete oppressions. Therefore, Tissot (2017: 34) highlights that "the meaning of 'the universal' proves to be culturally variable and the specific cultural articulations of 'the universal' work against its claim to a transcultural status".

The main trend in feminist translation theories has been to stand up for a kind of hospitality (a concept from deconstruction meaning that translators embrace the other) far from the classical sense of authorship (where authors impose the meaning), taking the perspective of the subject/object of the translation (when feminist translators assume an active role), and defending the diversity of sexual orientation and gender in the face of the antithetical identities of "man" and "woman" (Flotow 2007: 93). On the other hand, there are also other conceptions of the translation process, as the one that understands it as an "enabler of multi-directional communication" (Reimóndez 2017: 51), both as a means of connecting us "in ways that do not

pursue homogeneity, assimilation or annihilation” (Lugones 2010: 750) and as a means of “understanding and explaining the unfamiliar but also refamiliarizing the familiar in more productive and enriching ways” (Nnaemeka 2004: 381).

There has been criticism of these feminist translation movements. Arrojo (1994, 1995), for instance, focuses on feminist translation theories, particularly those that refer to deconstruction as the basis of their work to defend their visibility of women translators and their right to transform the original text based on notions such as the Derridean *différance*. This notion underlines the provisional nature of the linguistic sign, as regards both signifier and signified, inasmuch as any element which is present is always connected to what is absent, to everything it defers or everything from which it differs (see Derrida [1972] 1982). Arrojo (1994: 158) argues that accepting that no meaning can ever be stable or “original” does not entitle feminist translators to be “unfaithful” or to “abuse” the original. Thus, the impossibility of capturing the essence of the original is not a right but “every translator’s and every reader’s inevitable fate”. In this regard, Arrojo (1994: 157) wonders why intervention, or “hijacking”, is fair in the case of Levine or Lotbinière-Harwood, but not for Drant, and she asks “on what grounds can one justify that ‘womanhandling’ texts is objectively positive while ‘manhandling’ them is to be despised”. One important aspect of so-called feminist translation theories of the 1990s that Arrojo conveniently disregards is the importance that feminist translators ascribe to their drawing attention to and explaining the changes they make in the texts. Conventional/traditional translators conceal such changes; feminist translators celebrate them as a sign of the power they wield.

3. Feminist translation strategies

The history of Anglo-American and European feminist translation shows that it was the translators and translation theorists of the 1980s and 1990s from the North American schools who laid the foundations both for the theory and the practice of feminist translation. That was the context which gave rise to the first descriptions of feminist translation strategies, which set the standard for later proposals. The following comparative analysis will focus on the classical theories of the North American schools (Flotow 1991; Lotbinière-Harwood 1991; Levine 1991; Simon 1996; Massardier-Kenney 1997, and Maier 1998) which are most frequently cited, but it will also present other, later proposals that have tried to create a systematic classification and also constitute an innovative contribution (Wallmach 2007; Pas & Zaborowska 2017; Flotow 2019, and Lee 2023). Prior to the comparative analysis, the proposals will be presented in chronological order and grouped into schools. It is important to highlight that, we will use the terminology, definitions and examples deployed by the respective authors for subsequent comparison. For this very reason (using the terminology employed by the authors mentioned), we will preferably use the term *translation strategies* rather than *translation techniques* in this paper, even though we agree with Molina & Hurtado (2002: 508) that translation strategies are procedures to solve general problems when undertaking a translation and translation techniques are referred to particular problems that arise during the translation process.

3.1. Canadian school

From the Canadian school, Luise von Flotow was the first to describe strategies for feminist translation by reviewing the theory and practice of the recent feminist translation movement in Canada developed by Barbara Godard, Marlene Wildeman, Fiona Strachan, Howard Scott and Susanne de Lotbinière-Harwood. Based on the analysis of the work of these translators, Flotow (1991: 74–80) established a first classification of three strategies.

1. **Supplementing** is defined as a “voluntarist action” (75) on the text by which the translator compensates for the differences between languages, so when the target language invisibilises women, the translator transforms the text to let them emerge. The example Flotow provides in this case is Scott’s translation of Bersianik’s *L’Euguélonne*, where *Le ou la coupable doit être punie* (‘The guilty party must be punished’) transforms into *The guilty one must be punished, whether she is a man or a woman*. By adding the expression *whether she is a man or a woman*, the focus in English is on gender as it is in the French participial agreement of *punie* (‘punished’), which would otherwise have been neutralised.
2. **Prefacing and footnoting** are strategies through which the translator visibilises herself to communicate what is “lost in translation” (76) and thus manage to overcome the barriers that the target language might impose, something that would otherwise be insurmountable. An example is the preface to Nicole Brossard’s *These Our Mothers* by Barbara Godard, in which she explains the wordgames that could not be translated. Translator footnotes also serve to demonstrate how and when the translator deliberately intervenes to change some aspect of the text.
3. **Hijacking** implies some kind of “correction” (79) or feminisation of the target text such as, for instance, converting the generic masculine grammar of the original into feminine form or putting the female element first. Susanne de Lotbinière-Harwood’s avoidance of male generic terms in her English translation of *Letters from Another* by Lise Gauvin, despite the fact that they appear in French, e.g. *la victoire de l’homme* (‘the victory of man’) becomes *our victory [...] over the elements*, can be labelled hijacking.

Susanne de Lotbinière-Harwood (1991: 113–19) focused her study of feminist translations into English and into French on examining the differences between both languages. In conclusion, she set out the following strategies.

1. **Neutralisation**, replacing a gender-marked expression with a seemingly neutral one (e.g. replacing *stewardess* by *flight attendant*).
2. **Desexisation**, replacing a generic expression with another one marked by the feminine or masculine gender (e.g. using *he* or *she* instead of the generic *he*).
3. **Feminisation or gender-marking**, a strategy that goes beyond neutralisation and desexisation as it includes strategies such as putting the feminine first, avoiding derogatory words to designate women, encoding new meaning in existing words and coining new words which empower women (e.g. replacing *incest victim* by *incest survivor*).

Within this group of pioneers of feminist translation theory, it is also worth mentioning Sherry Simon (1996), who provided an exhaustive review of feminist translation strategies used throughout the ages (as mentioned in section 2). However, the aim of her study is not so much to elaborate a classification of translation strategies as to highlight the relevance of gender in translation from the perspective of cultural studies. In her study, she alludes to the strategies defined by authors, such as Luise von Flotow, Howard Scott, Susanne de Lotbinière-Harwood, Nicole Brossard, Barbara Godard and Carol Maier, along with a long list of feminist translators and translation theorists. But her exposition is unsystematic and, therefore, cannot be reproduced here. However, all the strategies that Simon (1996) mentions are already part of the classifications of the other authors presented here.

3.2. USA school

In the USA, Suzanne Jill Levine (1991) reflects deeply on the decision-making process involved in her own translation of Guillermo Cabrera Infante's novel *Tres Tristes Tigres*, focusing on the relationship between author and translator. Levine calls herself a "subversive scribe" (7) for the subversive character with which she approaches the translation of a text whose misogynistic character she clearly does not share. In her book, Levine describes the translation challenges she had to face, such as paranomasia, alliteration, intertextuality, onomastics, partial inequivalences of meaning, as well as the techniques she used to overcome those difficulties; of these techniques, she mentions (albeit again in an unsystematic way) *compensation, substitution (free play), linguistic variation, addition, supplementation, "rhetorical displacements" or "cultural metamorphoses"* (176). Although the strategies she discusses are not new, her examples and accompanying analysis are of great value for feminist translation.

Françoise Massardier-Kenney (1997) initiates a critique of the earlier theories of feminist translation strategies based on two main arguments. Firstly, she questions the Eurocentric and imperialistic view of the feminine subject visible in texts that come from a cultural context in which "feminism is not a viable strategy" (57). Secondly, she points to the need to change the perspective by highlighting that "it is not the strategies themselves that are feminist, assuming the notion of feminist itself is clear and non-controversial, but rather the use to which these strategies are put" (57). Her argument is based on the finding that these translation strategies themselves have already been used before for other purposes (e.g. she points out that "supplementing" is the old "compensation"). Thus, Massardier-Kenney's (1997: 58) critique of the different proposals for a classification of feminist translation strategies, such as Flotow's (1991), seeks to redefine the term *feminist*. She offers an alternative categorisation of feminist translation strategies, distinguishing between *author-centred* and *translator-centred* strategies.

Author-centred strategies seek to make the reader understand the source text and highlight the importance of women as producers of texts (be it as authors or translators). In this regard, Massardier-Kenney (1997: 59–61) mentions the following three strategies:

1. **Recovery** consists of widening and reshaping the canon, an archaeological task of finding, publishing and translating texts by women authors who were previously excluded. As an example, Massardier-Kenney offers up the rediscovery of Germaine de Staël and George Sand, as well as that of many other women authors previously excluded from the canon.

2. **Commentary** involves using the metadiscourse accompanying the translation to clarify the importance of the feminine (or of woman/women) in order to counteract the immediacy of the translated text and the danger of a false sense of familiarity with a foreign text or author (as Spivak (1992) has also pointed out). In this case, the example could be the afterword to Carol Maier's (1994) translation of Rosa Chacel's *Memoirs of Leticia Valle* which served to introduce Chacel to the contemporary reader and to establish her position by discussing her views on gender.
3. **Resistancy** entails the visibility of the translation through linguistic means that have a defamiliarising effect and that work against easy fluency (e.g. through a reworking of grammar). Massardier-Kenney considers resistancy as an appropriate strategy for the translation of experimental feminist writers like Monique Wittig, who reworks French grammatical gender, for example, in subject pronouns and male/female endings of substantives. This effect could also be achieved by reworking the English language in the translation.

Among the translator-centred strategies, Massardier-Kenney (1997: 63–5) mentions:

1. **Commentary**, when the feminist translator must describe her/his motives and the way they affect the translated text so as to avoid reproducing a male textual power structure (the original text as primary and the translation as secondary); this is a way of including the feminist questioning of universal categories in the translation project and examining how the factor of gender affects her/his decisions. An example of this could be Chamberlain's (1988) demonstration of how the metaphors of translation are deeply marked by gender differences.
2. **Use of parallel texts**, when the feminist translator is inspired by texts in the target language with a feminine voice that were produced in a similar situation, or that belong to the same genre as that of the source text. This is the case, for example, in Richard's preface to *Crossing the Mangrove*, where he explains that he found Virginia Woolf rather than Faulkner, Naipaul and Garcia Márquez to be the most parallel to Maryse Condé.
3. **Collaboration**, when the feminist translator works with one or more translators and/or with the author on a given text, thus connecting the interest in understanding how the discourse constructs/deconstructs gender and the idea of negotiation, and avoiding a strict separation between author/translator, writer/reader, translator/scholar and source text/target text. Diaz-Diocaretz (1985) and Levine (1991) provide good examples of the kind of collaboration the translator and the author can share.

Carol Maier (1998) starts from her own experience in translating María Zambrano's *Delirio y destino* to maintain that there is a continuum of strategies when translating in terms of gender, and, in this sense, she establishes two extremes. At one end of the continuum would be what she calls literal translation, i.e. a “no deliberate approach” or “null strategy” of the translator that implies “the absence of a deliberately formulated method” (98). The second would be the “feminist approach”, the interventionist one, which would imply both the translation of only explicitly feminist texts and the application of all kinds of strategies, both at the lexical level of a text and in terms of the text as a whole, where feminist strategies concern footnotes and commentary, inserting translator's remarks in the text itself or even eliminating passages the translator considers non-feminist (99).

3.3. Further contributions

Both the Canadian and USA schools have played an important role in defining feminist translation strategies. Nevertheless, other proposals for the classification of feminist translation strategies have been put forward. For the present research we are interested in highlighting those of Kim Wallmach (2007), Justine Pas and Magdalena Zaborowska (2017), the redefinition of Luise von Flotow's (2019) own first approach and the most recent work by Sang-Bin Lee (2023), because these are proposals which are innovative or add something to those of the Canadian and USA schools of the 1990s.

An interesting contribution is that of Kim Wallmach (2007), who uses Delabastita's (1993) categories of translation strategies (*substitution, repetition, deletion, addition and permutation*) as umbrella strategies that could be further subdivided into more detailed subcategories by a combination with Vinay & Darbelnet's (1995) categories (*literal translation, transposition, modulation, equivalence and adaptation, borrowing and calque, compensation, addition and deletion*). Furthermore, Wallmach (2007) carries out a comparative study of four translations by Patricia Claxton and Barbara Goddard to verify whether feminist translation uses different translation strategies or just the classical ones in a different way. Her conclusion is that, apart from metatextual comments, the differences between translations are not due to a feminist approach, but to different ways of using "the most conservative of existing translation strategies" (23). As a result of her research, Wallmach (2007: 15–19) establishes the following classification of translation strategies.

1. **Substitution**, by which a relevant source text item is replaced by a relevant target text item, i.e. translation in its strictest sense without any transformation or adaptation (e.g. *dans les bras de ma mère* translated into *in my mother's arms*).
2. **Repetition** (borrowing and calque), by which a relevant source text item is replaced or transferred directly from the source text into the translation (e.g. *kleenex* translated into *kleenex*).
3. **Deletion**, by which a source text item is not rendered in the target text at all (e.g. *nous dansons très collées* ('we dance very close together'), where the silent *e* indicates that the subjects are women, translated into *we dance very close together*).
4. **Addition**, by which the target text contains linguistic, cultural or textual component features which have no apparent antecedent in the source text (e.g. the use of a wordplay like *histoire* ['history'] translated into *history*).
5. **Permutation** (compensation), by which the target text does not reflect the relative position of its source text counterpart (by means of the use of footnotes, parentheses, italics, prefaces and so on).

Justine Pas and Magdalena Zaborowska (2017) conduct research in which they synthesise the strategies used in the English translations from Polish, Mandarin, Chinese, Hindi and Tamil for a translational oral history project initiated in 2001 at the University of Michigan. The aim of the research was "to demonstrate the value of specific feminist translation strategies in making visible the differently situated participants' voices and narratives, as well as acknowledging the creative and political agency of the translators" (140). As a result, the strategies found useful for feminist translation were:

1. The rendering of source language phrases literally or use of unidiomatic phrases in the target language.
2. The addition of in-text parenthetical explanations when transferring local idioms disrupting the transcript's narrative flow and visually signalling the translator's presence.
3. The use of grammatical gender structures in order to make women or gender relationships visible.
4. The transfer of non-English words and phrases and the offering of an explanation instead.
5. Footnoting to add explanations of gender issues that cannot be expressed in the text itself.

Pas & Zaborowska (2017: 149) conclude that putting into practice the findings of the Canadian school of feminist translation “helps create a praxis of resistance to transparent equivalence, fluid readability and translatability that works against assimilationist and homogenising Anglo-American publishing market trends”. In their view, the feminist translation strategies of supplementing and footnoting are particularly helpful in revealing the complexities of translation.

After receiving copious commentary, Luise von Flotow (2019) retraces the early developments of feminist translation, redefines the feminist translation strategies as observed and described in 1991 and classifies these strategies into two categories: *Macro-strategies* and *micro-strategies*.

1. **Macro-strategies** would be translator's notes, prefaces, explanations (which provide the space for a discussion of feminist principles, histories and ideas as well as specific translation problems), but also non-translation, re-translation and strategic text selection, as well as feminist publishing, reviewing, gratis translation or critiquing.
2. **Micro-strategies** would be stylistic and grammatical adjustments (making the feminine visible in language by using only feminine plural forms or devising odd juxtapositions of masculine/feminine forms, such as women and men), but also creative and neologistic translation, as well as omission, addition, supplementing and the development of various stylistic, grammatical or neologistic innovations that work on the details of the text itself.

One of the most recent contributions to the classification of feminist translation strategies is by Sang-Bin Lee (2023), who analyses the strategies used by the translators of Yeolda Books, a Korean independent publishing house. Lee asserts the need to decentre from the Anglo-European structure of thought. He starts by distinguishing between “translation peritexts” (106) (commentary, preface/postface) and translation strategies, which he calls “radical feminist translation strategies (techniques)” (107) and lists the following from among these strategies.

1. *Fanning*: Using words (especially pronouns) on a “female-as-norm” (108) (FAN) basis. As an example, Lee gives the use of feminine pronouns instead of the gender-neutral which are more common in Korean.
2. *Mirroring*: Creating female or male words that have countervailing effects on conventional words. Lee offers the example of using words signifying ‘wife’ or ‘married

woman' in Korean and not the usual ones signifying 'home person' or 'the person in the house', as correspondence for 'husband' or 'married man'.

3. *Tagging*: Adding lexical and/or grammatical markers to conventional words to show that the words are, in effect, misogynistic. For example, the use of quotation marks for the names of places where women are denigrated as "geisha venues" (110).
4. *Reversing*: Reversing the order of two successive words or characters to increase women's visibility and/or degrade men's sexuality, as when we say *women and men*.
5. *Normalising*: Replacing a misogynistic element of a word with a women-friendly one. The example Lee provides is the translation of *uterus* into an expression in Korean meaning 'the palace for cells' instead of the frequently used expression *the palace for sons* (as if daughters were excluded from there, he adds).
6. *Unpacking*: Explaining terms in a way that emphasises the dire conditions of women's lives, as when translating the English expression *prostitution buyers* for an expression meaning 'men who sexually exploit women' in Korean.
7. *Footnoting*: Providing explanatory notes for readers.

4. Comparison of feminist translation strategies

Given the diversity of the proposals for feminist translation strategies that we have just presented here, it seems necessary both to carry out a comparative analysis and to put forward a proposal for their synthesis. What first catches the eye are the different perspectives from which the various authors approach their proposals. Thus, while many of them only consider the classification of grammatical or lexical strategies applicable to the text itself (such as changing the gender of words or creating neologisms), others comment on strategies that go beyond the text (such as adding prefaces or notes to the translation) or even editorial policy (such as the deliberate selection of texts by unrecognised or forgotten women writers). In addition, a certain disorder may be observed within the proposals themselves, as they do not distinguish between different linguistic levels, since writing a preface is not the same as creating a neologism. For example, Flotow (1991) structures her article in three sections: supplementing, prefacing and footnoting and hijacking; or Massardier-Kenney (1997), who groups resistancy (which is an intervention of the translator in the text at the lexical or grammatical level) or recovery (which is an editorial decision) under the same umbrella of author-centred strategies. Finally, although some authors use the terminology of previous proposals, very often they baptise the same strategy with another name, as is the case of supplementing (Flotow 1991), addition (Wallmach 2007), in-text parenthetical explanations (Pas & Zaborowska 2017) and unpacking (Lee 2023), which come to the same thing.

Thus, the first step in the analysis of the different proposals for feminist translation strategies should be to establish different categories in correspondence to the different linguistic levels. The revision that Flotow (2019) carried out of her first proposal from 1991 points in this direction, thereby establishing a classification between macro-strategies and micro-strategies. However, a more detailed classification could still be established, which is the one proposed here. We distinguish between intratextual strategies, peritextual strategies, procedural strategies and publishing strategies. Intratextual strategies are those techniques applicable to specific problems that arise during the translation process at the grammatical or lexical level. By

peritextual strategies, we refer to all the information that surrounds the text itself in order to express everything that could not be conveyed in the translation itself. Procedural strategies are those actions of the translator that are not visible in the translation itself but have helped in the decision-making process. Finally, publishing strategies are all those decisions external to the text regarding which works to translate and which not to translate, or regarding the actual edition of the texts (such as the elimination or addition of fragments or the choice of the cover).

For a better visualisation of the analysis of the different feminist translation proposals, we have created a comparative table (see Table 1). First of all, it should be noted that the proposals we will analyse in greater depth are those that present a certain degree of systematisation. For this reason, proposals such as those of Levine (1991) or Maier (1998) are not included. In the first case, this is because although Levine discusses many of the strategies used in her translations (such as compensation, substitution, linguistic variation, addition or supplementation) and explains them with very illustrative examples, they are well-known strategies. Furthermore, her explanations are subordinated to a deep reflection on the translation process, decision-making and the relationship with the author, leaving systematisation aside. In the second case, the reason is that Maier focuses on the question of the general approach that every translator takes when faced with a new translation as to whether she/he should take into account the precepts of feminist translation and under what conditions to apply it, but the author does not provide further specification. The last proposal by Flotow (2019) is only implicitly included in the table, since the distinction between macro-strategies and micro-strategies that she puts forward has been taken into account.

If we look at Table 1, the first thing that strikes us is the number of empty symbols (Ø) that have been included to show all those cases in which the strategy proposed by an author is not included in other classifications. Some of these authors focus on intratextual strategies, ignoring many other moments that are also part of a translation. As mentioned above, Table 1 clearly shows a certain confusion caused by the diversity in nomenclature. Although some terms have been quite successful in the literature on feminist translation (such as Flotow's hijacking), almost all of the authors choose to rename the strategies. In some cases, such as Massardier-Kenney's, the same term (*commentary*) is used for two strategies that are part of different sections (author-centred and translator-centred). Furthermore, it has been observed that on many occasions the equivalence is not complete, but rather that the different definitions offered for what is supposedly the same strategy, include more assumptions than in others. It can also be seen in Table 1 that some authors are more precise or detailed in their classification and subcategorise some strategies (as is the case in Lee, who considers four different assumptions for hijacking or feminisation: fanning, mirroring, reversing and normalising).

We will begin the comparative analysis with the macro-strategies (those that exceed the text itself). In the case of the publishing strategies, few are the authors who take them into account, while Flotow (2019) mentions them as feminist translation strategies of great relevance: non-translation, strategic text selection, feminist publishing, reviewing, critiquing, re-translation and gratis translation. Editorial issues are often at the centre of the feminist translation debate, but except in the case of Flotow (and Massardier-Kenney (1997), in which recovery is also included) they are not usually part of the classifications of feminist translation strategies. However, publishing strategies are clearly a fundamental starting point for feminist translation and should be included in any classification in order to complete an overall picture of the whole translation process beyond the text itself.

As can be seen in Table 1, procedural strategies, which we have defined as those actions of the translator that are not visible in the translation itself but that help in the decision-making

process, are hardly taken into account when reflecting on the possible translation strategies applicable to feminist translation. The exception in this case is Massardier-Kenney (1997), who highlights two strategies among those she calls translator-centred strategies: use of parallel texts and collaboration both with the author of the text and with other translators. It should be recalled that women translators, such as Levine (1991), have used this type of strategy widely and have commented on them in their works. Due to the great influence they can exert on the final result of a feminist translation, it seems appropriate to consider these two strategies as a separate category of feminist translation strategies.

Table 1: Comparison of translation strategies

Flotow (1991, 2019)	Lotbinière-Harwood (1991)	Massardier-Kenney (1997)	Wallmach (2007)	Pas & Zaborowska (2017)	Lee (2023)
Intratextual Strategies					
Supplementing	∅	∅	Addition	In-text parenthetical explanations	Unpacking
∅	Neutralisation	∅	Deletion		∅
Hijacking	Desexisation	∅	∅	Use of grammatical gender	∅
	Feminisation	∅	∅	∅	Fanning
					Mirroring
					Reversing
Normalising					
∅	∅	Resistancy	Repetition	Literalness / unidiomatic phrases	∅
				Non-English expressions	
Peritextual Strategies					
Prefacing	∅	∅	Permutation	∅	∅
Footnoting / explanations	∅	∅		∅	Footnoting
∅	∅	Comments about author / translator	∅	∅	∅
∅	∅	Comments about translator's motivation	∅	∅	∅
Procedural Strategies					
∅	∅	Collaboration with author / translator	∅	∅	∅
∅	∅	Use of parallel texts		∅	∅
Publishing Strategies					
Text selection	∅	Recovery	∅	∅	∅
Re-translation	∅	∅	∅	∅	∅
Non-translation	∅	∅	∅	∅	∅
Critiquing	∅	∅	∅	∅	∅

The last category of macro-strategies is the one we have called peritextual strategies. These strategies, although they do not apply to the text itself, do accompany it and are part of it in some way. In general, as we have defined them, they are strategies whose objective is to explain issues related to genre that could not be included in the text itself during the translation process, in many cases due to the linguistic characteristics of the target language. Flotow (1991) was the first to highlight the importance of these strategies and, since then, this has been a very important resource in feminist translation. Within this category, Flotow (1991) discusses the strategies of prefacing, footnoting and explanations, to which two other authors add some more strategies. Firstly, Massardier-Kenney (1997) points out the importance of comments, both on the author/translator and on the translator's motivations. This is, in fact, a strategy that is often part of prefacing or footnoting, but which points to issues that are sometimes overlooked. Wallmach (2007), on the other hand, introduces the term *permutation* into this category; this is actually Delabastita's (1993) compensation but is defined as the strategy by which the translator compensates for gaps in her/his translation by means of comments in prefaces or footnotes.

The category considered most often is that of intratextual strategies. These strategies address both grammatical and lexical translation problems. However, it does not seem practical to make a distinction between these two linguistic levels, nor do the authors do so with the examples they provide in their explanations. When comparing the strategies of the different proposals, it is clear that (although known by different names) the authors consider four fundamental strategies. Given the diversity of nomenclature with which these authors refer to these categories, we believe some kind of unification to be appropriate. In this sense, we propose the use of terms that are most commonly used or that make most references to feminist translation. Thus, four fundamental intratextual strategies for feminist translation would be: supplementing, neutralisation, hijacking and resistancy.

The first intratextual strategy would be what Flotow (1991) called supplementing, which she defined as the strategy by which some type of grammatical or lexical information is added to a translation in order to make women more visible. It is a strategy that seeks above all to compensate for linguistic differences, in many cases due to their sexist nature, and with which the translator shows that she/he is aware of her/his role as mediator. This same strategy is called addition by Wallmach (2007), who offers a definition and some examples that are very similar to those of Flotow's (1991) supplementing. For this strategy, other proposals present more specific contributions. Pas & Zaborowska (2017) speak of in-text parenthetical explanations, which in reality would be one of the many possible applications of supplementing. Lee (2023) contemplates unpacking, with a definition similar to supplementing, but adds tagging, as a specific addition of grammatical or lexical markers to conventional words to highlight their misogynistic character. In short, supplementing can be applied whenever the grammar or lexicon of languages make women invisible.

As a counterpart strategy to supplementing there is deletion, contributed by Wallmach (2007); this consists of eliminating or deleting a lexical or grammatical element that is part of the original text so that it does not appear in the translated text when a masculinised original text makes women invisible or denigrates women in some way. In Table 1, we have included the neutralisation strategy provided by Lotbinière-Harwood (1991) as being equivalent to deletion, although in her case it has a much narrower meaning, since it refers exclusively to the replacement of a gender-marked expression by one that is not gender-marked. However, for a unified approach to translation strategies, it would be preferable to call this strategy neutralisation and use Wallmach's (2007) definition of deletion, since it is more evident

in the context of feminist translation (as opposed to *deletion*, which is the classic term in translation studies).

Hijacking is undoubtedly the feminist translation strategy par excellence since Flotow (1991) defined it as an intentional feminisation of the translation that corrects the original. However, if we compare the definition and the examples proposed for this strategy, we will see that they are easily confused with those of the supplementing strategy, for which, Flotow (1991: 75) herself employs the much-used example of the translation of *Ce soir j'entre dans l'histoire sans relever ma jupe* ('This evening I'm entering history without lifting my skirt') into *This evening I'm entering history without opening my legs*, which would fit the concept of hijacking perfectly. Wallmach (2007) also uses the example of the translation of *solidarité* ('solidarity') as *sisterhood* for the strategy of addition (her equivalent of supplementing), although it could equally well be understood as hijacking. On her part, Lotbinière-Harwood (1991) establishes a distinction between feminisation (placing the feminine first, avoiding derogatory words for women, or creating neologisms) and desexisation (substituting a generic word for another marked by gender) within the framework of hijacking. On the other hand, Lee (2023) offers a more detailed classification of this strategy by subdividing it into four possible cases: fanning (preferential use of the feminine), mirroring (creation of compensatory feminine or masculine equivalents), reversing (reversal of the usual masculine/feminine order) and normalising (substitution of a misogynistic term).

The last fundamental intratextual feminist strategy is resistancy, contributed by Massardier-Kenney (1997); this consists of maintaining traces of the original text in the translation, traces that surprise in order to call attention to some sexist aspect of the content of the original text or of the source language. Wallmach (2007) calls the same strategy repetition and relates it to the classic strategies of borrowing and calque. For their part, Pas & Zaborowska (2017) raise several assumptions within the spectrum of this strategy: literalness, use of unidiomatic phrases or transfer of non-English words and phrases. In general, this strategy is useful when the aim of the translation is to transfer a specific misogynistic or patriarchal expression from the original text.

5. Final considerations

We have been able to observe that the proposals for the classification of feminist translation strategies are rather disparate in nature; some focus on more general aspects, such as the selection of texts in the editorial field (Flotow 2019), others on everything that surrounds the translation itself, such as collaboration with the author or other translators, or comments on the translation process in prefaces and notes (Massardier-Kenney 1997), and others target very specific translation techniques at the grammatical and lexical level (Lee 2023). We have also observed a certain hesitation both in the terminology used to name the strategies (with overlapping or partially synonymous terms), and in the definitions and examples used. Finally, it seems that the difference between the translation process and the resulting translated text is sometimes confused as well as the fact that different linguistic levels require different strategies. In this sense, the conclusions we reach are similar to those of Molina & Hurtado (2002: 506–7) as regards general translation strategies. These authors concluded that there are terminological, conceptual and classification confusions in the existing definitions and classifications of translation techniques (mainly because of (1) terminological confusion and over-lapping terms, (2) confusion between translation process and translation result, and (3)

confusion between issues related to language pairs and text pairs), and therefore a new classification of translation techniques was needed. However, it should not be forgotten that the aim of many of the proposals discussed above was not to establish a strict classification but to explore possibilities within feminist translation.

For all these reasons, this paper has attempted to provide a comparison of the different proposals for the classification of feminist translation strategies in order to offer an overall view. It is clear from this comparison that the grouping of strategies according to the different linguistic levels or perspectives from which feminist translation is undertaken or analysed is appropriate because it allows us to deal more comprehensively with the strategies available in each case. Furthermore, the comparative approach allows us to rule out multiplicities in the nomenclature and to complement the different proposals. On this basis, a new unified classification proposal of a more exhaustive nature could be created, choosing the most appropriate name for each strategy when it refers specifically to feminist translation. This could have the following structure:

1. **Intratextual strategies:** Supplementing, neutralisation, hijacking and resistancy
2. **Peritextual strategies:** Prefacing, footnoting and explanation
3. **Procedural strategies:** Collaboration (with the author or other translators) and use of parallel texts
4. **Publishing strategies:** Text selection, editing and critiquing

In view of the comparative analysis we have undertaken in this paper, it might seem that Wallmach's (2007) conclusion that feminist translation makes use of the same strategies as general translation is correct. However, establishing a classification exclusively oriented towards feminist translation, including only those strategies useful for this purpose and where the examples refer to gender-related aspects will undoubtedly serve to improve feminist translation practice. Many of us believe that translation has been under patriarchal sway for a long time and to achieve new levels of equality in terms of gender, a neutral positioning is not possible (in fact, it is never possible). Everybody "abuses" the original text (as Arrojo states (1994: 157)), precisely because we cannot capture the essence of the original and we are obliged to intervene. The question is: "What is the purpose of our strategy?" and "Are we being honest and consistent in our approach?"

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Eivor Jordà Mathiasen
Universitat de València
Department of English and German
Av. Blasco Ibáñez 32
46010 Valencia, Spain
Email: eivor@uv.es

Exploring Curricular Aspects of Dialogue Interpreter Training: A Report on Two Surveys

Rachel E. Herring, Century College
Anne Catherine Gieshoff, Zurich University of Applied Sciences

Abstract

The last few decades have seen considerable growth in the availability of formal training opportunities for dialogue interpreters. These training opportunities range from post-graduate university courses to undergraduate certificates to short courses and workshops offered by non-governmental or community organizations. Although many publications have reported on training opportunities and courses, they generally provide high-level overviews of programs. There is little available information provided by individual instructors on the theoretical frameworks informing their work as trainers and the didactic materials that students are exposed to. This paper reports on two exploratory surveys of teachers of dialogue interpreting, encompassing both academic and non-academic training contexts, aimed at increasing our knowledge of these aspects of interpreter training. The results illustrate commonalities and differences in teachers' backgrounds, the didactic materials they employ, and the theoretical frameworks that inform teaching and are encountered by learners. The authors argue for strengthening of collaboration among those involved in teaching dialogue interpreters and for continued research efforts focused on teaching and learning of dialogue interpreting.

Keywords: *public service interpreting, interpreter training, survey, theory in interpreter training, materials in interpreter training*

1. Introduction

Training¹ opportunities for dialogue interpreters² have become more prevalent during the last several decades. Such opportunities are often offered outside tertiary-level institutions (Bao 2015; Kim 2017; Mikkelson 2017; Angelelli 2020), although the number of tertiary-level programs available has increased during the first decades of the twenty-first century. There is also a growing body of pedagogically focused research related to dialogue interpreting and overviews of training programs in a range of contexts (see, for example, Delgado Luchner 2019; Šveda 2021; Wakabayashi & O'Hagan 2022; and Napier et al. 2024). The majority of such reports describe the general outlines of curricula, offering relatively few specifics about aspects such as the materials used with learners and the theoretical frameworks informing teaching and learning.

¹ Discussion of the distinction between training and education and the question of which label should be used in what contexts is outside the scope of this paper. Interested readers are referred to Sawyer (2004), Angelelli (2017), and Amato & Mack (2022). For the purposes of this paper, the labels are used interchangeably.

² There are multiple labels used to describe the type of interpreting that is the focus of this paper, principally community interpreting, public service interpreting, and dialogue interpreting (e.g. Hale 2007, 2011; Merlini 2015; Tipton & Furmanek 2016). In this paper, we use dialogue interpreting, following Tipton & Furmanek (2016) and Niemants & Cirillo (2017).

Much discourse around dialogue interpreting has focused on the question of professionalization (Gentile 2016; Tiselius 2021). Among the hallmarks of professional status that appear in discussions of professionalization is the existence of a shared body of knowledge that is specific to the profession and the existence of professional education regulated by members of the profession (Weiss-Gal & Welbourne 2008). Perusal of the interpreting studies literature related to teaching and learning of dialogue interpreting suggests that there is some level of consensus around key aspects that should be addressed in training (e.g. Hale 2007; Corsellis 2008; Angelelli 2017; Ozolins 2017; Orlando 2019), as further discussed in Section 2. To date, however, there is relatively little information available about the extent to which dialogue interpreter training programs rest on and disseminate a shared body of knowledge and theory. There is also a lack of information about the professional and educational profiles of the people carrying out such training. Moreover, there has been little systematic comparison between formal academic settings and non-academic settings (e.g. courses offered through NGOs, interpreting agencies, government programs) with regard to such aspects.

As a first step toward addressing the paucity of available information regarding a range of aspects of teaching of dialogue interpreting and potential differences between academic and non-academic training contexts, two surveys were developed, one aimed at teachers of dialogue interpreting working in institutions of higher education (formal academic settings, or FAS) and the other aimed at teachers of dialogue interpreting working in non-academic settings (NAS). The study was exploratory in nature, with a broad aim of gathering information directly from teachers of dialogue interpreting about their backgrounds, the programs they teach in, the didactic materials they use, strengths and weaknesses of such materials, and the theoretical frameworks informing teaching and learning, and subsequently making the results available to researchers as an impetus for further research and a baseline for comparison. The two groups (FAS and NAS) were surveyed separately due to the need to tailor the survey content to specific aspects of the experience of each group. This paper focuses on the data related to respondents' backgrounds (Section 5.1), the didactic materials they employ (Section 5.2), and theoretical frameworks informing teaching and learning (Section 5.3), and discusses the implications of the findings for training of public service interpreters.

2. Existing publications on dialogue interpreter training

Among the main sources of information about dialogue interpreter training worldwide are overviews of the situation in a specific geographical area or overviews of specific programs or projects. Three recent examples are the volumes edited by Šveda (2021) and Wakabayashi & O'Hagan (2022), which focus on Central Europe (the former) and Australia and New Zealand (the latter), and the volume edited by Napier et al. (2024), which discusses training of interpreters of signed language in a number of countries. In addition to edited volumes such as these, there are a number of papers that report on training efforts in places such as Sweden (Gustafsson et al. 2012), the United Kingdom (de Pedro Ricoy 2010; D'Hayer 2012), Spain (Foulquié-Rubio 2018), Kenya (Delgado Luchner 2019), and Argentina (Manfredi & Lázaro Gutiérrez 2021), among others.

Another source of information about the landscape of dialogue interpreter training consists of publications that discuss the subject more generally, rather than with a focus on a specific program or region. These works highlight issues such as the importance of empirically-grounded teaching that embraces pedagogical knowledge, principles, and theory

(Angelelli 2017) and the need to strike a balance in training programs between translation competence, setting-related content, and social and interactional aspects (Ozolins 2017). Other papers focus on specific challenges confronting dialogue interpreting trainers, such as the diversity of student profiles and the need to transcend traditional notions of interpreting and translation (Valero Garcés 2019). Pedagogical and didactic aspects of dialogue interpreting have also been addressed in edited volumes dedicated to the subject (e.g. Cirillo & Niemants 2017), monographs (e.g. Mazzei & Jay-Rayon Ibrahim Aibo 2022; Tipton 2024), and chapters within more broadly focused handbooks (e.g. several chapters in Gavioli & Wadensjö 2023).

Information about dialogue interpreter training can also be found in monographs and manuals that are intended as introductions to the field and in textbooks (e.g. Hale 2007; Rudvin & Tomassini 2011; Tipton & Furmanek 2016). These and other authors address skills and knowledge needed by dialogue interpreters, including the following:

- Knowledge of context and subject matter (Corsellis 2008; Hale 2007; Tipton & Furmanek 2016; Gentile et al. 1996)
- Language competence (Corsellis 2008; Hale 2007; Gentile et al. 1996; Tipton & Furmanek 2016)
- Cross-cultural awareness (Hale 2007; Tipton & Furmanek 2016; Rudvin & Tomassini 2011)
- Knowledge of ethics, role behavior, and professional issues (Corsellis 2008; Hale 2007; Tipton & Furmanek 2016)
- Interpreting theory (Tipton & Furmanek 2016; Hale 2007; Ozolins 2017)
- Practical and business-related aspects (Tipton & Furmanek 2016; Gentile et al. 1996)

The publications mentioned in the preceding paragraphs tend to address dialogue interpreter training from a macro perspective, providing overviews of specific programs, regional situations, or high-level recommendations for teaching and learning. The micro-level perspective is also represented in the literature, often in the form of classroom-based studies reported on by teachers who have carried out action research with their students (see Nicodemus & Swabey 2015; Crezee & Burns 2019). Such reports give glimpses of the interpreting classroom, but in a necessarily limited fashion, given their scope and aims. One source of a comprehensive micro-level view of a training program is Maximous' (2017) dissertation-length case study. Drawing on observations, interviews, and questionnaires, reflecting both faculty and student perspectives, she paints an exhaustive picture of an academic year in a university-level program in Australia. She reports on evidence of variability and lack of uniformity in teaching approaches and methods and a lack of awareness and uptake of research and theory, with many respondents (both faculty and students) viewing them as of low value or relevance. Her findings point to possible gaps and inconsistencies between the macro-level perspectives contained in overviews and manuals and on-the-ground realities. This raises the question of whether similar patterns would be detected in other training contexts, or whether they are unique to the context that Maximous reports on. The survey data reported on in this paper may serve as a point of reference for development of more in-depth studies similar to that carried out by Maximous, leading to a fuller picture of concepts and frameworks taught of dialogue interpreting

3. Theory in interpreter training

The relationship between theory and practice in interpreter training has been addressed by a number of scholars, who are generally united in emphasizing the fundamental importance of theory and research for both teachers and learners. In relation to this discussion, it is important to distinguish between two aspects of theory (following Setton 2010): on the one hand, theory related to teaching and learning, both in general and in connection with interpreting, which is primarily related to the instructor and how they conceptualize and approach instructional activities; and, on the other, student-facing theory, which is the domain-related theory to which students are exposed through instructional materials (e.g. textbooks, articles) and classroom activities (e.g. lectures, presentations).

In connection with the need for instructors to have a balanced knowledge of both the vocational–practical and the academic aspects of interpreting, Orlando (2019: 221) notes that “knowing the profession but nothing of the academic discipline and the findings from the research carried out in T&I Studies will be an impediment to the sound theoretical education of future professionals.” The benefit of theory to student interpreters is clearly explicated by Arumí Ribas (2020: 73), who states that “trainee interpreters need a number of concepts that enable them to put names to the description of the process they go through while interpreting and to analyse the challenges they encounter in their training.” Similar arguments have been made with respect to the need for interpreter training itself, from curricula down to individual class activities, to be rooted in a clear theoretical model or conceptualization of interpreting (e.g. Setton 2010, Angelelli 2017, 2020). In her chapter on training of community interpreters, Hale (2007: 176) describes the connection between theory-informed teaching and learning outcomes:

[K]nowledge and skills are crucial elements in any Community Interpreting course. However, teaching these areas will not be effective if it is not underpinned by a theory of interpreting or informed by the results of research [...] Applying theoretical principles in the teaching of the practical skills is essential if students are to understand the reasons why their choices are being assessed as appropriate or inappropriate.

The theoretical frameworks informing trainers’ approaches to teaching and the frameworks and constructs encountered by students in the course of their studies are thus highly relevant objects of research, inasmuch as they provide insight into the conceptualizations and representations of interpreting that learners are being exposed to during this process of learning and socialization (see Angelelli 2020; see also Washbourne & Liu 2023, on an ontological turn in translator and interpreter training).

The macro-level information about dialogue interpreter training that is contained in publications providing high-level descriptions of programs and in manuals and textbooks does not provide detailed insight into the theoretical frameworks and conceptualizations of interpreting and of pedagogy that inform trainers’ work with learners nor into the aspects of theory and research that interpreter trainees are exposed to (that is, student-facing theory). Maximous’ (2017: 242) case study of teaching and learning of community interpreting reports “considerable” variation in teaching practices and approaches within a single program, as well as a lack of awareness and appreciation for research and theory and their relevance to teaching and learning of interpreting. To date, a clear picture of how research and theory inform interpreting training worldwide is lacking.

4. Method

This paper reports on two surveys of trainers of dialogue interpreters. The first survey (late July to mid-September 2021) was aimed at trainers working in formal academic settings (FAS). The second survey (mid-March to late June 2022) was aimed at trainers working in non-academic settings (NAS). Ethics approval for both surveys was sought and obtained through the institutional review process at Century College (Minnesota, USA). Both surveys were built in a secure institutional Microsoft Forms account and were set up to gather responses anonymously.

The FAS survey was developed in light of the scope and aims for the project (see Section 1) and on the basis of a review of relevant literature, discussed in part in Sections 2 and 3. It was piloted and revised in response to feedback from colleague interpreter trainers and scholars. The survey was a mix of closed-ended and open-ended questions and consisted of the following sections:

- Acknowledgement and consent—1 question, closed-ended
- Eligibility to participate in the study—2 questions, closed-ended (see below)
- Questions related to the program you teach in—8 questions, mix of open-ended, closed-ended, and Likert scale
- Questions about the courses you teach—9 questions, mix of open-ended, closed-ended, and Likert scale
- Demographic information—7 questions, mix of open-ended and closed-ended questions

The NAS survey was largely the same as the FAS survey. Introductory segments at the beginning of each set of questions were modified to reflect the intended audience. The wording of closed-ended response choices was slightly modified in some cases to better fit the NAS setting; these changes were made in consultation with colleagues training in NAS (for example, the question in the FAS survey about the type of program in which the respondent taught was converted into two questions about the teaching situations in which NAS respondents work). The full text of both surveys is available upon request to the corresponding author.

Invitations to participate in the surveys were disseminated via professional associations, emails to professional contacts, and social media. Prospective participants were identified through the first author's professional networks as well as through internet searches of publicly available listings of faculty (for the FAS survey) and of interpreter training organizations (for the NAS survey).

Upon entering the survey tool, participants were asked to confirm that they had read the study description and information (including information about anonymity of responses) and that they consented to participating in the study. The second and third questions of each survey served as screen-in/screen-out questions for respondents, confirming their status as (recently) active trainers of dialogue interpreters in the indicated setting for each survey. Respondents were required to answer all questions, with the exception of two open-ended questions. The FAS survey received 41 complete responses; 13 potential respondents were screened out. The NAS survey received 21 complete responses; 5 potential respondents were screened out.

5. Results

5.1. Demographic information

Responses to the FAS survey come from teachers working in 15 countries: Australia (N=3), Austria (N=4), Belgium (N=2), Canada (N=2), Finland (N=1), Germany (N=2), Haiti (N=1), Ireland (N=1), New Zealand (N=1), Norway (N=5), Spain (N=2), Sweden (N=4), Turkey (N=1), the United Kingdom (N=3), and the United States (N=11)³. More than half of FAS respondents teach in Europe (56%, N=23⁴), and 32% (N=13) teach in North America.

Respondents to the NAS survey teach in Australia (N=1), Austria (N=1), Canada (N=2), Japan (N=1), Mexico (N=1), Turkey (N=1), and the United States (N=16). The NAS respondents teaching in the United States make up 76% of the respondents to this survey.

As detailed in Table 1, respondents teaching in formal academic settings tend to have higher levels of formal education, are more likely to have received more formal training in interpreting, and are more likely to have completed some type of formal training as teachers in comparison with the respondents from non-academic settings, whereas respondents from non-academic settings are more likely to be working as interpreters in addition to working as trainers.

Respondents were asked to describe what, if any, formal training in teaching they had taken part in. FAS respondents mention experiences ranging from attendance at conferences to undergraduate coursework to graduate degrees in teaching. The majority describe training related to teaching in higher education, in general, although some also mention training in teaching for compulsory primary and secondary schooling, including completion of teacher certification courses. Of thirty-one respondents to this question, nine (29%) mention completing workshops, courses, or degrees specifically related to interpreting pedagogy.

The NAS respondents describe formal training in teaching ranging from continuing education offerings, workshops, summer schools, training aimed at employees in the private sector, training-of-trainers programs aimed at licensees of private short courses, teacher training for compulsory primary and secondary schooling, and postgraduate degrees or certificates in education, including higher education. With the exception of train-the-trainers sessions for private short courses offered by the organizations that license the courses, the respondents do not mention trainings specifically related to interpreting pedagogy.

³ Note that the total number of responses is higher than the total number of respondents, as two FAS respondents and one NAS respondent report teaching in multiple countries.

⁴ The respondent from Turkey is included in this count.

Table 1: Respondents' demographic information

		NAS	FAS
Highest level of formal education <i>(not necessarily interpreting-specific):</i>	Bachelor's degree	3 (14.3%)	2 (4.9%)
	Some graduate coursework	2 (9.5%)	0 (0.0%)
	Graduate certificate	0 (0.0%)	1 (2.4%)
	Master's degree	12 (57.1%)	14 (34.1%)
	PhD	4 (19.0%)	24 (58.5%)
Formal training in interpreting <i>(NB: respondents were asked to select all that applied to them)</i>	None.....	1 (4.8%)	1 (4.8%)
	Private short course.....	11 (52.4%)	5 (12.2%)
	Continuing education/ professional development.....	11 (52.4%)	9 (22.0%)
	College/university-based short course, undergraduate level...	2 (9.5%)	11 (26.8%)
	College/university-based degree (BA or equivalent).....	1 (4.8%)	6 (14.6%)
	College/university-based short course, postgraduate level.....	2 (9.5%)	4 (9.8%)
	Postgraduate degree (MA or equivalent).....	5 (23.8%)	18 (43.9%)
	Other.....	0 (0.0%)	4 (9.8%)
Experience training interpreters (in years)⁵	< 5	5 (23.8%)	5 (12.2%)
	5–10	6 (28.6%)	10 (24.4%)
	11–15	0 (0.0%)	6 (14.6%)
	16–20	2 (9.5%)	9 (22.0%)
	21–25	5 (23.8%)	6 (14.6%)
	26–30	0 (0.0%)	2 (4.9%)
	> 30	3 (14.3%)	3 (7.3%)
Formal training in teaching	Yes	11 (52.4%)	31 (75.6%)
	No	10 (47.6%)	10 (24.4%)

⁵ Respondents who teach in both settings were asked to consider only their time spent training in the setting applicable to the survey they were responding to.

5.2. Didactic and instructional materials⁶

Respondents were asked a question aimed at better understanding the extent to which the curriculum they use is institutionally mandated or otherwise fixed (that is, consisting of structure and content provided to the trainer, with little room for individual modification), draws on materials made available to them by an institution on a voluntary basis, or is self-created. Within the FAS group, 35% (N=14) of respondents report having access to program-provided syllabi, materials, and activities, but having the freedom to adapt them as they see fit, while 39% (N=16) report that course goals and learning objectives are set by the institutions and they create their own syllabi, materials, activities, and so forth. Only 17% (N=7) of FAS respondents report that they must create everything, including learning objectives and curricula, on their own. In contrast, 43% (N=9) of the NAS respondents report creating their own curricula and finding or creating all of their own materials, 29% (N=6) have some curriculum and materials provided for them but also create some materials on their own, and 24% (N=5) use curricula and materials that are created and provided by someone else (e.g. private training programs). In both groups, most trainers are responsible for creating at least some of the didactic materials they use with learners, with the proportion being higher in the FAS group.

As noted above, the existing literature provides little information about the types of didactic materials (that is, excluding those used as stimuli for interpreting exercises and practice) that are used in dialogue interpreting classrooms. In order to take a first step toward gathering such information, respondents were provided with a list of types of didactic materials and asked to state how frequently they use each type of material with learners. Details of these results appear in Figures 1–3.

Figure 1: Types of instructional materials used with learners, #1

⁶ Throughout the survey and this paper, “didactic and instructional materials” refers to materials used to teach content and skill, rather than to material used as stimuli for interpreting practice (e.g. speeches, role plays). This definition was provided to survey respondents in narrative text preceding these questions.

Figure 2: Types of instructional materials used with learners, #2

Figure 3: Types of instructional materials used with learners, #3

We conducted chi-square tests to compare the FAS and NAS responses for each of the types of material listed. A statistically significant relationship between type of material and FAS/NAS responses was only found for articles published in academic journals ($X^2=18.853$, $p=0.001$). Binomial testing revealed that FAS respondents significantly more often reported that they use academic articles frequently or very frequently (FAS: 34%, NAS: 0%, $p < 0.000$), while the proportion was significantly lower for the answer option “never” (FAS: 5%, NAS: 38%, $p < 0.000$). No statistically significant difference was found for the answer options

“rarely” (FAS: 7%, NAS: 14%, $p=0.267$) and “occasionally” (FAS: 20%, NAS: 24%, $p=0.59$) (see Appendix for detailed statistics).

Respondents also had the opportunity to list types of didactic materials that they use that had not been included in the Likert scale survey item. Among the types of materials listed by the FAS respondents are self-created lectures, slideshow presentations, and videos; program-created course compendia or packets; textbooks and research articles from other disciplines; and resources created and disseminated by governmental and non-governmental entities (e.g. the European Commission, foundations or professional organizations related to specific diseases or conditions). NAS respondents mention materials such as patient-directed educational materials, medical books or curricula, self-prepared slideshow presentations, case studies and scenarios drawing on real-life situations, and government documents and policies.

In addition to gathering information on the different types of materials being employed in dialogue interpreter training, the survey contained items aimed at gaining information about various aspects of trainers’ perspectives on the materials they use, including their satisfaction with the materials, the extent to which the materials are appropriate for students or need to be adapted for students’ use, and the extent to which cost is a factor in choosing materials. Respondents were then asked to read a number of statements related to the didactic materials they use and to indicate their level of (dis)agreement with each statement (Figures 4–6).

Figure 4: Aspects of instructional and didactic material, #1

Figure 5: Aspects of instructional and didactic material, #2

Figure 6: Aspects of instructional and didactic material, #3

For each of the statements regarding instructional materials (see Figures 4–6), the association between respondents' agreement and their teaching setting was investigated with a chi-square test. For most statements, no relationship was found between the responses of FAS and NAS respondents. A statistically significant relationship was found for the statement “interpreting theory is not relevant for my students” ($X^2=11.606$, $p=0.021$) and a marginally significant association for the statement “considerations of cost for students play a role in my choice of instructional/didactic material” ($X^2=9.297$, $p=0.054$). In order to investigate the differences more closely, a binomial test was performed on each of the answer options. This test revealed in the first case that trainers from formal academic settings tended to disagree more strongly with the statement that interpreting theory is irrelevant than trainers from non-academic settings (FAS: 32%, NAS: 1%, $p < 0.001$). Trainers from non-academic settings, in contrast, agreed more strongly with the statement on cost considerations (FAS: 5%, NAS: 29%, $p < 0.001$) (see Appendix for detailed statistics).

In order to gain insight into barriers, gaps, and areas of need related to available instructional materials, respondents were asked an open-ended question about what they see as the greatest weaknesses of the materials they use. In the FAS survey, four respondents did not answer this question and two respondents indicated that they do not perceive any particular weaknesses in the materials they use. In the NAS survey, one respondent did not answer the question, and two respondents indicated no weaknesses. Thus, 35 FAS respondents and 19 NAS respondents described weaknesses in materials. The two sets of responses were analyzed separately to identify recurring themes. Similar themes were identified in both sets of responses: the focus or content of available materials, the approachability of materials for learners, the language(s) in which materials are written, and the need to create or adapt materials for use in the classroom. In the representative examples below, we have employed bold typeface to highlight particularly salient elements of the responses.

- Focus or content of available materials
 - (1) *Not flexible in use for deaf interpreters. Most materials are **focused on the auditory features** of speech.—NAS*
 - (2) ***Limited reference to different country contexts.** We teach from the perspective of institutional interactions in [Country], but students come from all over the world and are unlikely to stay to work in [Country]. Having **access to materials of use across the board is challenging.**—FAS*
- Approachability of materials for learners
 - (3) *Some are **complex and difficult to quickly understand**, so I have to do a lot of the thinking for students, **which puts them at a disadvantage** as they are learning my interpretation of the materials and not analyzing them for themselves.—NAS*
 - (4) *The available materials are often outdated or fall to one extreme or the other (**too simplistic or too unapproachable**; below college level or above undergraduate reading level). Many materials **do not come with an applied component** to easily tie theory into practice.—FAS*

- Language(s) in which materials are written
 - (5) *The weakness of instructional materials (e.g. books and journal articles) is that they **may be in a language not accessible to the students** whose working languages/bilingual competency does not include e.g. English. **Central curricular texts must adapted to the students' common language** (in our case, [Language]) by the course organizer.—FAS*
 - (6) *Not a lot of information for signed languages. We borrow a lot from spoken languages. **We have to generate the [Language] content we use**, which is time consuming.—FAS*
- Need to create or adapt materials for use in the classroom
 - (7) *Re: interpreting theory, I use it a lot but it **has to be adapted to plain speech** to be relevant - and **very often I have to adapt materials** that take a broad swipe at the fields I work in but aren't really targeted well.—NAS*
 - (8) *I mostly **create my own instructional materials**, so as to be able to tailor the materials to the students and their particular needs. In that sense, I guess the **greatest weakness is the time it takes to prepare classes**.—NAS*

5.3. Theoretical frameworks and constructs informing teaching & learning

The survey contained several open-ended questions aimed at gathering information related to the theoretical frameworks and constructs informing respondents' work as trainers and to which learners are exposed in classroom and homework activities.

Respondents were invited to identify the five scholars or theoretical frameworks that have most influenced their work as interpreter educators, first with reference to interpreting and translation and then with reference to teaching and learning. With regard to theoretical frameworks and constructs related to translation and interpreting, FAS respondents mention forty-nine separate scholars or scholarly teams.⁷ Of these, thirty-four are mentioned once, ten are mentioned between two and four times, and five are mentioned five or more times, as detailed in Table 2. In addition, FAS respondents mention a number of constructs and frameworks that are not strongly associated with a specific scholar or scholarly team (e.g. discourse and conversation analysis; relevance theory; theories of politeness, face, and agency). NAS respondents mention twenty scholars or scholarly teams in response to this survey item. Of these, thirteen are mentioned once, three are mentioned twice, one is mentioned four times, and three are mentioned five times, as detailed in Table 3. NAS respondents mention fewer theoretical constructs not associated with specific authors, but do mention a few, including deliberate practice models and functional effect and communicative intent (i.e. skopos theory).

⁷ "Scholarly team" refers to two or more authors who have jointly developed a framework or approach, or published a joint volume, which is thus strongly associated with both or all of them, rather than with one of them.

Table 1: Most frequently referenced T&I scholars influencing FAS respondents' work as interpreter educators

Name(s)	Number of Mentions
Cecilia Wadensjö	14
Daniel Gile	12
Robyn Dean & Robert Pollard	7
Peter Llewellyn-Jones & Robert G. Lee	6
Sandra Hale	5

Table 2: Most frequently referenced T&I scholars influencing NAS respondents' work as interpreter educators

Name(s)	Number of Mentions
Cross-Cultural Healthcare Program / Cynthia Roat	5
Robyn Dean & Robert Pollard	5
Holly Mikkelson	5

With respect to the question about scholars and theoretical constructs and frameworks related to teaching and learning, 27 FAS respondents (66%) responded to this question, with responses falling into two broad categories: scholars and frameworks that can be categorized as being within translation and interpreting studies (TIS), and those from outside TIS. In the first group, twenty-one scholars are mentioned, some of whose work is pedagogically oriented and some of whose work is not. The second category of responses to this question includes scholars and frameworks related to teaching and learning from outside TIS. Among the theoretical frameworks mentioned are constructivism, situated learning, experiential learning, critical pedagogy, and reflective practice. All of the NAS respondents answered this item in the survey, although 29% (N=6) of them answered “not applicable,” “none,” or “as above.” As with the FAS respondents, NAS respondents mention some TIS scholars in response to this question. Respondents also mention packaged curricula licensed by private interpreter training companies. Several responses mention specific frameworks from the field of teaching and learning, including principles of adult education (andragogy), deliberate practice, reflective practice, experiential learning, and competency-based learning. Responses from both groups provide evidence of current trends in interpreting pedagogy and didactics as discussed by authors such as Orlando (2016), Li (2018), Orlando (2019), and Tiselius & Herring (2023).

In order to get a sense of the range of theoretical perspectives that learners are exposed to and the extent to which learners may or may not be exposed to a shared body of theory and knowledge, respondents were asked to list the names of up to five scholars whose work their students are exposed to in some way as part of their studies. FAS respondents listed 90 scholars or scholarly teams in response to this prompt, with five names being mentioned more than five times and nineteen names mentioned three or more times (Table 4). Thus, 71 out of 90 names (79%) mentioned by FAS respondents appeared only one or two times. NAS respondents mentioned 35 scholars or scholarly teams in response to this question. Of these, 7 are mentioned two or more times, with the most-frequently appearing name mentioned four times (Table 5). In the NAS survey, 28 out of 35 names (80%) appear only once.

Table 3: Names mentioned more than five times in response to query about scholars whose work students are exposed to in FAS

Name	Number of Times Mentioned
Franz Pöchhacker	14
Cecilia Wadensjö	13
Daniel Gile	12
Sandra Hale	10
Jemina Napier	9

Table 4: Names mentioned two or more times in response to query about scholars whose work students are exposed to in NAS

Name	Number of Times Mentioned
Holly Mikkelson	4
Cross Cultural Health Care Program / Cynthia Roat (Bridging the Gap training course)	3
Robyn Dean & Robert Pollard	3
Marjory Bancroft	2
Daniel Gile	2
Sandra Hale	2
Jean-François Rozan	2

The number of separate names mentioned and the tendency for names to be mentioned only once illustrate the heterogeneity of the discipline and the range of scholars whose work is encountered by learners. The names mentioned by the two groups (FAS and NAS) do overlap; for example, four of the five names most frequently mentioned by the FAS group are also mentioned by the NAS group. NAS responses to this question include curricula produced especially for short training courses, such as *Bridging the Gap* and *The Community Interpreter*, while the FAS responses do not mention such materials.

Respondents were also asked to share information (i.e. author, title) for up to five didactic materials (e.g. journal articles, book chapters, textbooks, recorded webinars or presentations) that are assigned to students. The majority of the publications listed by FAS respondents are in English (or are identified or listed in English); however, publications in a number of other languages are also mentioned, including Danish, Galician, German, Norwegian, Spanish, and Swedish. No NAS respondents specifically mentioned items written in languages other than English. The prevalence of English-language texts mentioned in the responses is perhaps not surprising in light of the fact that the survey was administered in English; at the same time, it also may reflect the tendency noted by the respondents quoted in Section 5.2 who mention lack of texts in languages other than English as a weakness of the didactic materials they use.

The responses that included sufficient information to allow for further analysis were categorized by type of (re)source.⁸ FAS responses included videos, documents produced by governmental or non-governmental organizations and institutions (e.g. Departments of

⁸ Both sets of responses included items that could not be categorized due to insufficient information (e.g. listing an author but not specifying a work by that author).

Education of individual US states, professional organizations, United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees), textbooks or other didactically oriented volumes, academically oriented volumes (e.g. monographs, edited volumes), and papers from scholarly journals. Many of the textbooks mentioned by FAS respondents are aimed at students training to go into a specific setting, such as courts or healthcare. However, textbooks are mentioned less frequently than academically oriented books (whether monographs or edited volumes) and peer-reviewed journal articles, which is in line with the responses to the question about frequency of use of various types of materials (see Figures 1–3 above). Publications listed by the NAS respondents include textbooks and didactically oriented books, peer-reviewed articles, academically oriented monographs, curricula for specific private training programs, codes of ethics and standards of practice, news articles, videos and podcasts, and government policies. Fewer materials were mentioned by NAS respondents than by FAS respondents; indeed, some NAS respondents stated that they do not generally assign homework to trainees, but, if they do, it is likely to be practice-oriented, rather than involve consumption of didactic material.

6. Discussion

6.1. Geographic coverage and respondent profiles

The majority of the responses to both surveys are from trainers working in Europe and North America. The limited geographical coverage may be in part due to the existence of fewer training programs for dialogue interpreters outside these regions; it may also, however, reflect insufficient dissemination of the survey, despite efforts to reach a wide audience. The survey was also only available in English, which may have influenced the geographical range reached.

Within this sample, respondents from FAS tend to have higher levels of formal education, are more likely to have completed some type of formal training as teachers and are more likely to have received more formal training in interpreting, in comparison with the respondents from NAS. The fact that 95% (N=39) of FAS respondents have completed at least some graduate study and that more than half (59%, N=24) have completed a PhD may be a reflection of the fact that tertiary-level institutions generally require such qualifications in order to teach; it may also reflect the possibility that FAS trainers with PhDs were more likely to respond to a request to participate in a research study. That said, the percentage of NAS respondents reporting having completed some type of graduate-level studies is also quite high, at 76% (N=16).

With regard to formal training in interpreting, 24% (N=5) of the NAS respondents report having completed a post-graduate level program (MA degree or equivalent), in comparison with 44% (N=18) of the FAS respondents. Given the paucity of graduate-level training specifically focused on dialogue interpreting before the last couple of decades, it might be seen as noteworthy that so many of the participants in both groups have graduate-level training in interpreting. However, it is possible that the graduate-level study of interpreting undertaken by many of these respondents was focused on conference interpreting or on interpreting and translation in general, rather than on dialogue interpreting in particular.

FAS respondents are also more likely to have received formal training in teaching (FAS respondents: 76%, N=31; NAS respondents, 52%, N=11) and to have participated in training specifically related to interpreting pedagogy. Only 29% (N=9) of the 31 FAS respondents who report having received formal training related to teaching specifically

mention training related to teaching interpreting, while the only type of interpreting-pedagogy-specific training mentioned by the NAS group is training-of-trainers (TOT) sessions intended to prepare trainers to teach specific private curricula. The need for teaching staff to have training in pedagogy, both in general and specific to interpreting, has been addressed by scholars such as Angelelli (2017), Orlando (2019), and Kadrić & Pöllabauer (2023). Availability of TOT courses and materials is a highly relevant topic for trainers in both FAS and NAS. Although the data gathered in these surveys provides only limited information about trainers' access to and participation in TOT activities, these findings resonate strongly with the discussions found in the just-cited literature of the need for teacher training for trainers of dialogue interpreters. In our view, efforts to respond to this need should take trainers in NAS into account, rather than focusing solely on trainers in FAS, inasmuch as NAS trainers may have received less formal training in interpreting (and thus may have less grounding in theory) and, by virtue of their training context, may not have institutional affiliations that would allow them the same access to academic publications enjoyed by their FAS colleagues.

6.2. Didactic materials

The section of the survey focused on curriculum began with a question aimed at understanding the extent to which respondents create their own curricula and teaching materials versus teach from a fixed curriculum and set of materials. The great majority of respondents in both groups report that they create and/or adapt materials for use with their students (NAS: 71%, N=15; FAS: 98%, N=40). This suggests a landscape that allows for significant individual variation among trainers. This can be a strength of training programs, inasmuch as it allows for flexibility and tailoring of instruction to learner needs and profiles. At the same time, it can potentially be a weakness, since developing one's own curricula and teaching materials requires a significant amount of time and effort, the need for which may or may not be reflected in remuneration rates. Additionally, lack of shared understandings and frameworks (both of interpreting and of teaching and learning) within a program or across programs in a geographical area can lead to inconsistencies and confusion for both service users and interpreters in relation to issues such as standard practices, understanding of role boundaries and decision-making latitude, and conceptualizations of what constitutes (un)ethical behavior.

The range of types of didactic materials encountered by students in both FAS and NAS settings reinforces the impression of a heterogeneous landscape. While some materials and authors are mentioned by multiple respondents, learners are likely to encounter a wide range of materials by a wide range of authors. Many of the materials that respondents mention assigning to learners are focused broadly on dialogue interpreting, often addressing multiple settings rather than one single setting (e.g. medical, legal). This may be evidence of a curricular tendency toward what Taibi et al. (2022: 97) describe as a "generic skills education," with a primary focus on developing interpreting skills in general, rather than on preparation for a specific work setting. The fact that FAS respondents are significantly more likely than NAS respondents to assign academic, peer-reviewed publications as reading material for their students is indicative of some differences in the type of materials that learners in the two settings encounter. It is perhaps not surprising that credit-granting institutions of higher learning would require more engagement with academically oriented texts. Additionally, as noted above, FAS respondents are also more likely to have higher levels of education, in general, and may therefore be more likely to be acquainted with research- and theory-focused texts. The frequent use of academic, peer-reviewed publications as texts in the interpreting classroom merits further

investigation, given that such texts are by nature not intended for an audience of learners and may present a number of challenges for use in the dialogue interpreting classroom (Tiselius & Herring 2023).

Most respondents in both groups report being happy with the didactic materials they use (NAS: 90%, N=18 strongly agree or agree;⁹ FAS: 85%, N=35 strongly agree or agree) and feeling that the materials they use are approachable for learners (NAS: 80%, N=16 strongly agree or agree; FAS: 90%, N=37 strongly agree or agree). At the same time, a majority of both groups reports having to do a lot of work to adapt materials to meet learners' needs (NAS: 55%, N=11 strongly agree or agree; FAS: 68%, N=28 strongly agree or agree), and half (NAS) or close to half (FAS) report not having materials available in their students' primary language (NAS: 50%, N=10 strongly disagree or disagree; FAS: 46%, N=19 strongly disagree or disagree). The need to create and adapt materials, the approachability of materials, and the languages in which materials are available are common themes in the responses to the open-ended question about weaknesses of available instructional and didactic materials, as discussed in Section 5.2. These responses resonate with Orlando's (2016: 65) call for "more and more accessible, journal articles and [...] books or textbooks on the didactics of T&I." Similar themes are also highlighted by Hale (2007: 17), who reports on focus groups in which community interpreter trainers identified "lack of teaching materials and textbooks to guide them, time limitations and the students' mixed bilingual and bicultural competence" as the main challenges facing them. The same group of trainers reported needing to create their own teaching materials, although in Hale's case the comments regarding materials appear to be largely focused on practice materials rather than didactic materials.

6.3. Theory in teaching and learning

Several survey questions elicited information from respondents related to theory in teaching and learning. As noted in Section 5.2, a significant difference emerged between the two groups with regard to the Likert scale item "interpreting theory and research are not very relevant for my students," with FAS respondents disagreeing more strongly with the statement than NAS respondents. In contrast, the majority of both groups were in agreement with the statement "my course(s) are informed by interpreting theory and research" (NAS: 85%, N=17 strongly agree or agree; FAS: 90%, N=37 strongly agree or agree), with no statistically significant difference found between the two groups. The fact that some NAS respondents endorse the role of theory in informing their courses while others endorse the statement that theory is irrelevant for their students is an interesting contrast worthy of further investigation, potentially via observation, interview, case studies or other methods that allow for a qualitative analysis of classroom practices.

Responses regarding the theoretical constructs and frameworks that inform respondents' work as trainers suggest a landscape characterized by some commonalities, but also much diversity and variation. Similarly, responses to the question focused on student-facing theory (that is, materials assigned to students) demonstrate a notable heterogeneity in terms of the types of materials assigned and the theoretical content to which learners are exposed during their studies. Within the responses to these questions we see abundant evidence of the influence of dialogue interpreting-focused scholarship (e.g. Claudia Angelelli, Sandra Hale,

⁹ NAS total N=20 for the questions about specific materials because one respondent stated that they do not use didactic materials.

Holly Mikkelson, Hanne Skaaden, Cecilia Wadensjö) and of theoretical frameworks developed by scholars of signed language interpreting (e.g. Robyn Dean & Robert Pollard, Peter Llewellyn-Jones & Robert G. Lee), as well as of the continued influence of scholarly work arising from simultaneous conference interpreting (e.g. Daniel Gile) or encompassing a broad view of interpreting studies (e.g. Franz Pöchhacker). There is also evidence of the influence of translation studies, narrowly defined, on our respondents' work as educators, particularly with respect to pedagogy of translation (e.g. Mona Baker, María González Davies, Donald Kiraly, Kelly Washbourne).

The method (i.e. survey) and exploratory nature of this study provide only limited information regarding this topic. Although the results provide some evidence of trends and of points in common (e.g. socioconstructivist approaches to teaching and learning; see also Orlando 2016 and Tiselius & Herring 2023) and points of difference in terms of the theoretical frameworks informing teaching and to which learners are exposed, the exploratory nature of the study did not allow for in-depth investigation of the ways and extent to which the constructs and frameworks mentioned by respondents are integrated into training programs. Further in-depth exploration is needed in order to get a better understanding of the specifics of teaching and learning theory in the dialogue interpreting classroom. Additionally, further research is needed to explore trainers' teaching beliefs and practices and learners' and program graduates' perspectives on curricula and teaching practices. In this we join other scholars who have argued for increased research into the effectiveness of teaching approaches and practices (e.g. Pöchhacker 2010; Winston 2013; Orlando 2016). In addition, given evidence of differences in learners' and instructors' perceptions and beliefs regarding issues such as beliefs and practices related to teaching & learning and the relevance of theory in interpreter education (see Takeda 2010; Li 2018; Liu 2019; Arumí Ribas 2020), this investigatory angle is highly relevant.

7. Conclusion

The survey results discussed in these pages offer an initial, wide-angle view of several aspects of dialogue interpreter training and draw our attention to a number of aspects that need closer examination. The overall impression given by the data is of a landscape that has a number of points of commonality but also a great deal of heterogeneity. Heterogeneity is not necessarily problematic, and is to some extent necessary, given the variety of possible training situations, cultural contexts, and work settings in which dialogue interpreters are trained and carry out their professional responsibilities. At the same time, ongoing efforts to professionalize dialogue interpreting—and, indeed, its established status as a (semi-)profession in some areas—might be expected to imply a corresponding trajectory of professionalization or regularization of the body of knowledge and the theoretical frameworks employed in the teaching of dialogue interpreting. While recognizing the need for training to be adapted to context and situation, we also echo Arumí Ribas' (2020: 77) assertion that there is a need to work toward a “shared collective decision” regarding theory and concepts to be included in interpreter training. We join Kadrić & Pöllabauer (2023: 424) in their call for a “global exchange between interpreter educators,” in the hopes that such collaborative efforts will lead to intentional, collaborative efforts to develop relevant materials and curricula and make them available to teachers in all types of situations and settings.

Authorship statement

Rachel E. Herring designed the study, collected the data, led the qualitative data analysis, and wrote the initial draft of the literature review, method, and results sections. Anne Catherine Gieshoff carried out and wrote up the quantitative data analysis. Both authors collaborated on drafting the discussion and conclusions sections and preparing the paper for publication.

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Appendix: Detailed Statistical Analyses

Table 5: Descriptive statistics and test statistics (chi-square-test) for didactic material

Variable	N	Percent	N_1	Percent_2	Test
Survey	FAS		NAS		
Textbook	41		20		$X^2=8.9, p=0.064^*$
... Never	5	0.122	8	0.4	
... Rarely	5	0.122	3	0.15	
... Occasionally	12	0.293	4	0.2	
... Frequently	7	0.171	0	0	
... Very Frequently	12	0.293	5	0.25	
acaJournal	41		20		$X^2=18.853, p=0.001^{***}$
... Never	2	0.049	8	0.4	
... Rarely	3	0.073	3	0.15	
... Occasionally	8	0.195	5	0.25	
... Frequently	14	0.341	4	0.2	
... Very Frequently	14	0.341	0	0	
profJournal	41		20		$X^2=3.399, p=0.493$
... Never	5	0.122	5	0.25	
... Rarely	3	0.073	3	0.15	
... Occasionally	17	0.415	6	0.3	
... Frequently	13	0.317	4	0.2	
... Very Frequently	3	0.073	2	0.1	
Blog	41		20		$X^2=5.626, p=0.131$
... Never	11	0.268	10	0.5	
... Rarely	15	0.366	2	0.1	
... Occasionally	12	0.293	6	0.3	
... Frequently	3	0.073	2	0.1	
... Very Frequently	0	0	0	0	
publicVideos	41		20		$X^2=5.475, p=0.242$
... Never	0	0	2	0.1	
... Rarely	2	0.049	0	0	
... Occasionally	12	0.293	7	0.35	

... Frequently	15	0.366	6	0.3
... Very Frequently	12	0.293	5	0.25
subscribedVideos	41		20	$X^2=5.568, p=0.234$
... Never	14	0.341	9	0.45
... Rarely	7	0.171	2	0.1
... Occasionally	12	0.293	4	0.2
... Frequently	8	0.195	3	0.15
... Very Frequently	0	0	2	0.1
podcast	41		20	$X^2=5.59, p=0.133$
... Never	17	0.415	14	0.7
... Rarely	13	0.317	2	0.1
... Occasionally	8	0.195	2	0.1
... Frequently	3	0.073	2	0.1
... Very Frequently	0	0	0	0
codesConduct	41		20	$X^2=6.983, p=0.137$
... Never	1	0.024	3	0.15
... Rarely	1	0.024	0	0
... Occasionally	7	0.171	1	0.05
... Frequently	12	0.293	3	0.15
... Very Frequently	20	0.488	13	0.65

Table 6: Descriptive statistics and test statistics (chi-square-test) for didactic material

Variable	N	Percent	N_1	Percent_2	Test
survey	FAS		NAS		
I'm happy with the materials	41		20		$X^2=1.086, p=0.896$
... Strongly disagree	1	0.024	0	0	
... Disagree	1	0.024	0	0	
... Unsure	4	0.098	2	0.1	
... Agree	24	0.585	13	0.65	
... Strongly agree	11	0.268	5	0.25	
cost considerations play a role in my choice	41		20		$X^2=9.297, p=0.054^*$
... Strongly disagree	4	0.098	0	0	
... Disagree	13	0.317	2	0.1	
... Unsure	5	0.122	6	0.3	
... Agree	11	0.268	4	0.2	
... Strongly agree	8	0.195	8	0.4	
interpreting theory is not very relevant for my students	41		20		$X^2=11.606, p=0.021^{**}$
... Strongly disagree	21	0.512	3	0.15	
... Disagree	16	0.39	9	0.45	
... Unsure	1	0.024	1	0.05	
... Agree	2	0.049	6	0.3	
... Strongly agree	1	0.024	1	0.05	
the materials are not as in-depth as I would like	41		20		$X^2=2.305, p=0.68$
... Strongly disagree	8	0.195	4	0.2	
... Disagree	15	0.366	6	0.3	
... Unsure	7	0.171	3	0.15	
... Agree	11	0.268	6	0.3	
... Strongly agree	0	0	1	0.05	

the materials are available in my students' L1	41		20		$X^2=1.324, p=0.857$
... Strongly disagree	6	0.146	5	0.25	
... Disagree	13	0.317	5	0.25	
... Unsure	6	0.146	2	0.1	
... Agree	11	0.268	5	0.25	
... Strongly agree	5	0.122	3	0.15	
I have a lot of work to adopt the materials	41		20		$X^2=2.528, p=0.64$
... Strongly disagree	2	0.049	3	0.15	
... Disagree	6	0.146	3	0.15	
... Unsure	5	0.122	3	0.15	
... Agree	23	0.561	8	0.4	
... Strongly agree	5	0.122	3	0.15	
my course is informed by interpreting theory	41		20		$X^2=5.752, p=0.124$
... Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	
... Disagree	3	0.073	1	0.05	
... Unsure	1	0.024	2	0.1	
... Agree	13	0.317	11	0.55	
... Strongly agree	24	0.585	6	0.3	
the materials are approachable	41		20		$X^2=4.652, p=0.199$
... Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	
... Disagree	0	0	2	0.1	
... Unsure	4	0.098	2	0.1	
... Agree	22	0.537	8	0.4	
... Strongly agree	15	0.366	8	0.4	

Table 7: Proportions and binomial test statistics

statement	answer option	number of successes	number of trials	proportion of successes (FAS)	estimated probability (based on NAS)	p-value
cost considerations play a role for my choice of didactic materials	Strongly disagree	4	41	0.1	0	0
	Disagree	13	41	0.32	0.1	0
	Unsure	5	41	0.12	0.29	0.023
	Agree	11	41	0.27	0.19	0.23
	Strongly agree	8	41	0.2	0.38	0.015
interpreting theory is not very relevant	Strongly disagree	21	41	0.51	0.14	0
	Disagree	16	41	0.39	0.43	0.64
	Unsure	1	41	0.02	0.05	1
	Agree	2	41	0.05	0.29	0
	Strongly agree	1	41	0.02	0.05	1

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*Rachel E. Herring
Century College
3300 Century Ave N
White Bear Lake MN 55110 USA
Email: rachel.herring@century.edu*

*Anne Catherine Gieshoff
ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences
School of Applied Linguistics
Theaterstr. 15
8401 Winterthur
Switzerland
Email: annecatherine.gieshoff@zhaw.ch*

Aspects of creativity in AI-powered Polish-to-English literary translation

Małgorzata Kodura, University of the National Education Commission

Abstract

This research paper explores the capabilities and limitations of various AI models in translating Polish literary texts into English. The study examines the impact of different prompt settings on translation output, focusing on the creativity, accuracy, and correctness of AI-generated texts. The aspect of creativity in the generated texts is analysed through the application of creative shifts as proposed by Bayer-Hohenwarter. By evaluating translations generated by diverse AI models with varied prompts, this research aims to provide insights into the role of AI in literary translation and its potential to bridge linguistic and cultural gaps. The paper highlights the potential challenges and considerations associated with augmented creativity, reviews the current state of research, and offers recommendations for further studies in this domain.

Keywords: *translation creativity, artificial intelligence, creative shifts, machine translation, literary translation*

1. Introduction

The advent of advanced artificial intelligence (AI) models, particularly large language models (LLMs), has led to significant advancements in the field of machine translation. However, the translation of literary texts – rich in stylistic nuances, cultural references, and subtle meanings – presents a unique challenge. This research aims to explore the capabilities and limitations of various AI models in translating Polish literary texts into English, with a particular focus on the impact of different prompt settings on the translations produced, their creative solutions, translation accuracy, and the preservation of source text imagery. Through this investigation, the study seeks to deepen our understanding of AI's role in literary translation and assess its potential to bridge linguistic and cultural divides.

Artificial intelligence is increasingly being utilised across various fields, including translation. While AI translation tools, particularly those based on machine translation (MT), have made considerable progress, concerns remain about their ability to capture the subtleties and intricacies of literary language. Nevertheless, translators are actively exploring and incorporating AI tools into their workflows, seeking innovative ways to leverage these technologies. Recent developments in AI-powered translation systems, notably neural machine translation (NMT), have ignited discussions within translation studies about the concept of creativity in machine-generated translations. Although AI models have shown remarkable proficiency in producing fluent and accurate translations, their ability to generate truly creative output remains a subject of ongoing research and debate.

2. Literature review

Early investigations by Guerberof Arenas & Toral (2020) explored the notion of creativity in machine-generated translations of the story *Murder in the Mall*. The study defined creativity as a blend of novelty and acceptability, comparing the outcomes of machine translation, post-editing of machine translations, and human translations. The results consistently showed that human translations attained the highest creativity scores, while raw MT scored the lowest. This suggests that NMT systems, even when trained on literary data, lack the ability to produce creative translations and tend to favour literal solutions. Moreover, the study revealed that using MT as a foundation for post-editing can potentially constrain the creativity of human translators. Post-edited translations, compared to those produced solely by humans, consistently exhibited a lower degree of creativity. This was evident in a reduced tendency to deviate from literal renderings and a diminished ability to handle units of creative potential effectively. While these distinctions may seem minor, they are nonetheless significant, as subtle elements such as voice, rhythm, and style are precisely what elevate a translation from merely functional to truly distinctive.

Toral & Way (2018: 263) investigated the quality of NMT on literary text, which they claim is “the greatest challenge for MT”. They compared the performance of NMT with the previous dominant paradigm, phrase-based statistical machine translation (PBSMT), using English-to-Catalan translations of novels. The researchers first trained both NMT and PBSMT systems with over 100 million words of literary texts and evaluated the resulting translation with both automatic evaluation metric (BLEU) and using human evaluation. They concluded that NMT provided a viable solution for literary translation and proposed that future work should focus on integrating NMT into professional literary translation through post-editing. Toral and Way also observed that the difficulty of training MT systems on a vast amount of bilingual parallel literary text was a challenge before the advent of e-books. The wide availability of e-books in digital format created an opportunity to build MT systems specifically for novels, which in turn resulted in better performance.

Subsequent research by Guerberof Arenas & Toral (2022) further corroborated the finding that human translation generally exhibits greater creativity than MT or post-editing. This study highlighted the crucial role of human intervention in navigating cultural contexts and making subjective choices, both vital components of creative translation. More recently, Jiménez-Crespo (2024) explored the influence of AI and large language models on the translation landscape. While AI can generate novel content, Jiménez-Crespo (2024: 319) emphasised that human-generated texts are perceived as more creative, since creativity in translation involves processes richer than just creating “never-before-seen content”. This highlights the continued importance of human expertise in creative endeavours such as translation, advocating for a human-centred AI approach that augments human capabilities rather than replacing them, particularly in creative fields.

In contrast, a study carried out by Hu & Li (2023) showcased the creative potential of the AI-powered translation system DeepL in translating Shakespearean plays into Chinese. DeepL achieved over 80% accuracy and fluency, demonstrating its capability to handle complex texts across languages. Furthermore, it exhibited creativity through techniques such as adding words for clarity, shifting perspectives, and employing specific Chinese grammatical structures. However, identified accuracy and fluency errors, including overly literal translations, indicated that AI is not yet ready to fully replace human translators. It

should also be noted that the researchers did not include the analysis of the Shakespearean verse in their study.

At the same time, Wang (2023) investigated the increasing application of AI-powered machine translation, highlighting the unique characteristics, complexity, and cultural significance of literary translation – often overlooked amidst the advancements in MT. Employing sociological theories, Wang identifies three key challenges in applying MT to literary texts: the deeply ingrained habits and skills translators develop over time, a complex network of human and non-human actors, and the cultural and ethical implications of MT in literary contexts. Wang argues that current MT systems merely simulate human translation, potentially undermining the processes of meaning generation and cultural knowledge production inherent in literary translation. The study concludes that until MT can be proven both effective and safe for literary texts, human translators remain indispensable for managing the complexities and nuances in those texts.

Łoboda & Mastela (2023) observed in their study that although it is believed that in some areas, e.g. translating for EU institutions, neural machine translation engines can reach surprisingly high-quality scores, their use in literary texts is a controversial subject. Łoboda and Mastela suggest introducing post-editing exercises into translator education to enhance students' cultural sensitivity and to make them aware of the limitations of machine translation. The authors propose that such exercises, particularly with culture-bound texts, can serve as an innovative way to develop students' technological, linguistic, and cultural competencies. By working with texts rich in cultural elements, students learn to identify when a machine is likely to fail. The study found that students with prior training were more critical of machine translation output and better at detecting and correcting errors, demonstrating the value of this pedagogical approach.

Recent research offers diverging perspectives on the role of AI in creative translation. For example, Gao et al. (2024) explored the creative potential of artificial intelligence in translating Chinese poetry into English. They observed that ChatGPT could generate novel combinations of words and phrases, capturing the essence of the original poems while offering fresh interpretations. However, fidelity issues persisted, and ChatGPT struggled to apply its understanding of specific phrases consistently during translations. Conversely, Runco (2023) presents a contrasting viewpoint, contending that AI cannot exhibit true creativity. He argues that while AI outputs may appear original and effective, they lack key characteristics of human creativity, such as self-actualisation and emergent thought. Runco proposes viewing AI output as a form of pseudo-creativity. Bridging these perspectives, Škobo (2023) examined the integration of AI in literary translation, finding that while AI offers benefits such as time-saving and improved consistency, it struggles with the nuances, metaphors, and figurative language intrinsic to literary works. The study highlights that human expertise, creativity, and critical thinking are essential for capturing the artistic value of the original text.

The impact of AI on translation, particularly in the literary domain, is a complex and multifaceted issue. While AI demonstrates impressive capabilities in generating fluent and accurate translations, its capacity for true creativity remains a subject of debate. Human expertise, with its nuanced understanding of language and culture, continues to play a vital role in preserving the artistic value and essence of literary works in translation. However, the increasing prevalence of inexpensive and easily accessible machine translations is increasing its share of the market, with publishers offering low rates to translators for post-editing machine-translated texts, raising ethical concerns regarding transparency and fair

compensation. As Li (2023) notes, the increasing use of AI in translation challenges the professional identity of translators, downplaying the human contribution to a supporting role. Li highlights that this trend directly impacts translation quality, as AI systems are prone to biases derived from their training data, which is based on statistics rather than personal understanding. These biases include issues related to gender, race and nationality. While some companies like Nuanxed and China Literature openly embrace AI in translation, using human collaborators to edit machine-translated books, ethical questions persist. Under international intellectual property law, a translation is considered a derivative work, but an ethical question emerges whether an AI translation can have authorship. Li (2023: 537) refers to the US Supreme Court case *Naruto v. Slater*, which established that a non-human individual cannot claim copyright ownership, thus an AI translator is merely a tool. Another issue mentioned by Li (2023: 538) in the context of ethics is the AI retranslations of existing works, as they integrate the language expressions of previous human translations. Those issues, not properly managed by translators' associations so far, need to be addressed more systematically, especially in translator education. Fortunately, the use of AI translation is not commonly encouraged, for instance platforms like Amazon KDP advise against the use of AI for literary content, emphasizing its potential to damage an author's reputation (Albarino 2023).

In the realm of machine translation, LLMs like ChatGPT-4 – while not specifically designed for translation – are increasingly being utilised for this purpose due to their extensive training data encompassing various languages. Although specialised machine translation systems still outperform LLMs in terms of translation quality, particularly for specialised texts, LLMs offer a valuable complementary role, providing faster initial translations or suggestions for professional translators. In the context of literary translation, LLMs face challenges in capturing the nuances and complexities inherent in literary language. While AI excels at translating everyday language, the subtle wordplay and deeper meanings often found in literature can be lost in AI-generated translations. Advancements in NMT, which utilises artificial neural networks to make contextual connections between words and phrases, offer promising avenues for improvement, initiating a growing trend of employing AI in the domain of literary translation. These experiments serve not only to demonstrate the evolving capabilities of machines, but also to actively challenge the perceived boundaries of AI's potential in handling complex literary forms.

A notable example of AI's expanding role in literary translation is a recent initiative undertaken by a publishing house from Kraków, which launched the "Conceptual Line" series with a unique translation of Alfred Jarry's play *Ubu Roi*, generated entirely by Google Translate. This attempt, led by Aleksandra Małecka and Piotr Marecki (2018), was not aimed at creating a flawless translation but rather at conducting an experiment in conceptual art. They intentionally selected *Ubu Roi*, a play renowned for its absurdity and its goal of creating theatre without theatre. By employing machine translation, they sought a "translation without translation", embracing the awkwardness, nonsensical phrases, and errors produced by the algorithm as an extension of Jarry's spirit of absurdity. Another project employed Chat GPT-4 to translate the play from French to Polish, with prompts engineered by Jan K. Argasiński (Argasiński & Marecki 2024). The goal was to produce a simplified translation, followed by a summary, a dramatic retelling, and a prosaic adaptation infused with modern youth slang and profanity. The project, showcasing both the potential and limitations of AI in capturing the essence of the play while creatively adapting its language, reached its apex with the publication of *UBU GPT* (Jarry 2024), a physical book presenting these AI-generated interpretations. This experiment followed the concept of uncreative

writing, challenging traditional notions of creativity and authorship, where text is treated as data to be manipulated and transformed. It highlighted AI's potential in literary studies and creative practices by generating new insights and interpretations of classic works, positioning translation within the realm of conceptual art. The idea was not to replace human translators but to broaden the creative possibilities of translation and encourage reflection on technology's role in artistic expression, with AI's transformative potential used to generate new forms of literary expression.

In a similar vein, the experiment described in this paper aims to examine the possibilities and limitations of the most advanced technology when applied to a specific literary genre, and to verify whether and to what extent currently available AI tools are capable of replicating the nuanced understanding and resourcefulness of contemporary literary texts. Using the framework of creative shifts proposed by Bayer-Hohenwarter (2009, 2010, 2011), the study poses the question whether the output produced by modern large language models can be regarded as creative and comparable to human creative translations.

3. The source material

The source material selected for this study is a fragment from *Love Song*, a book by Karolina Krasny – a young writer, poet, and designer from Kraków – published in 2024 by Ha!Art, the same publishing house that released the ChatGPT-generated *UBU GPT*. According to the publisher's description, *Love Song* is a narrative that explores the transformative power of love on its surroundings. The two protagonists exist in a state of correspondence with nature, their community, and the urban fabric they inhabit. Reviewers have compared Krasny's poetic text to cubist paintings, with characters as letters and relationships as impossible figures.

The fragment selected for the study, titled "Field Wedding", describes a wedding ceremony where the main characters, Zet and XY (the bride and groom) feel alienated and overwhelmed by the formality and expectations of the event. The text features a distinctive style characterised by a skilful blending of vivid imagery and a sense of detachment, creating a unique, surreal atmosphere. The author frequently uses figurative language, unconventional metaphors and similes, enriching the text and adding layers of meaning and emotional depths. The couple is likened to metal, their vows to steel, and their shrinking bodies to fabric folding in on itself. Sensory details and visual and tactile imagery immerse the reader in the scene, with the hard and tense surroundings, cold or hot metal, and the scent of perfume mingling with the buzzing of flies.

Apart from figurative language and sensory descriptions, other challenges awaiting the translator of this text include the blending of formal and informal language, as well as the occasional use of fragmented sentences and ellipses, all of which contribute to the dreamlike atmosphere of the text. The text is characterised by a distinctive contrast between mundane elements and surreal imagery. This juxtaposition is evident in the author's lexical choices, blending colloquialisms with poetic language and creating tension between the ordinary and the extraordinary. Sudden shifts in perspective, particularly the transition to first-person narration in *cudzy oddech był tym samym, co mój* (lit. 'someone else's breath was the same as mine'), present a challenge in maintaining coherence and narrative flow in the target language. The translator must decide whether to preserve this shift or to normalise it for the sake of consistency in English.

4. AI tools and methods

The study, conducted in December 2024, used three selected AI models (ChatGPT 4o created by OpenAI, Claude 3.5 Sonet built by Anthropic, and Gemini Advanced 1.5 Pro offered by Google AI) and three different prompts to generate multiple English translations of this text. The prompts were designed specifically to obtain responses corresponding to three levels of the temperature parameter settings. In AI-generated texts, temperature settings play a pivotal role in controlling the balance between creativity and coherence. The temperature parameter in LLMs is intrinsically linked to their capacity for creative output, particularly in the realm of narrative generation. By controlling the randomness of the LLM's output, temperature influences the diversity and unpredictability of the generated text (Bhupen 2024). Higher temperature values encourage the model to explore less probable options, leading to more diverse and imaginative outputs. Conversely, lower temperature values constrain the model to favour the most likely tokens, resulting in more focused and predictable text. The choice of temperature setting depends on the specific application and the desired outcome. While higher temperatures stimulate novelty and creative expression, they also increase the risk of generating incoherent or nonsensical responses. Therefore, it is crucial to evaluate the generated text for inaccuracies or AI hallucinations, as strategic adjustment of the temperature parameter allows users to control the behaviour of LLMs and achieve desired levels of creativity. However, as it proved infeasible in this study to directly manipulate the temperature in all three AI tools, an intermediate solution was applied to modify the temperature within the prompt itself (Ramlochan 2024).

Each model generated three translations based on three distinct prompts designed to simulate varying levels of the temperature parameter: low, medium, and high. The low-temperature prompt was: "Translate the following text conservatively into English, focusing on literal meaning rather than idiomatic expressions". The medium-temperature prompt instructed the tool to: "Translate the following text while maintaining a balanced tone – clear and informative but also engaging and natural. Ensure the translation captures the essence of the original text without being too rigid or too free". Lastly, the high-temperature prompt asked the AI model to:

Provide a vivid, expressive translation of the following text. Feel free to use colourful language, idiomatic expressions, and creative phrasing to capture the spirit and mood of the original in a way that resonates strongly in the target language. While preserving the core meaning, prioritise the sound of the target language and follow the melody of the original, do not focus on rhyme in English, do not create a poem, but try to reconstruct the rhythm from the Polish language.

These prompts were finalised after preliminary testing on a short sample, which revealed the need to instruct the models explicitly to avoid generating poetry or rhymes, as they were being produced in response to the prompt asking for prioritising the language. All translations were produced using a new chat each time to avoid any references to previous prompts and contexts. The resulting outputs were labelled as Ch1, Ch2, Ch3 (for ChatGPT), C11, C12, C13 (for Claude), G1, G2, G3 (for Gemini), according to the applied prompt. These labels are utilised throughout the subsequent analysis presented in this paper and a literal translation of the Polish text is provided in brackets with each reference to the source text.

This study employs a mix of quantitative and qualitative methods to analyse the translation data generated by different AI models and prompt settings. The objective is to assess the impact of these variables on translation quality, identify patterns and trends, and draw conclusions regarding the strengths and weaknesses of AI in literary translation. To ensure a comprehensive evaluation, the output translations were assessed based on a set of predefined criteria. First, their correctness was determined by examining grammatical accuracy, appropriateness of vocabulary, and adherence to English language conventions. Second, accuracy was evaluated by assessing the faithfulness of the translation to the original meaning and intent of the Polish source text. Lastly, to evaluate creativity, the study utilised the approach proposed by Bayer-Hohenwarter (2009, 2010, 2011), focusing on the identification of creative shifts such as abstractions, concretisations, and modifications, and their frequency in the analysed texts as indicators of the creative features of the translated text. Furthermore, the study investigated the processing of figurative language, metaphors, and stylistic choices to effectively capture the aesthetic qualities of the original text. This multi-faceted approach was designed to provide valuable insights into the capabilities and limitations of AI in the domain of literary translation.

5. Results

To be creative, translation must first and foremost be fit for purpose, i.e. linguistically correct and accurate. Therefore, the initial phase of the analysis involved a careful examination of the generated translations, focusing on their linguistic correctness. Each translation was evaluated independently for the presence of any linguistic errors. The most common issue identified was the use of punctuation, such as the overuse of dashes instead of semicolons or some commas that could have been used differently to ensure better flow. However, this unconventional use of punctuation in some places corresponded to the rhythm of the original text and did not depend on any specific prompt. Major errors were not common in the AI-generated translations; the only grammar problems concerned the past tense. For example, in two translations generated by Claude (C11 and C12), the use of tenses followed the unconventional but correct structure of the Polish language, as shown in (1).

- (1) ST: Naraz zrzucili każdą z możliwych warstw, chwycili się i stoją.
 (lit. ‘At once they have shed every possible layer, grasped each other and are standing’)
- C11, C12: At once, they shed each possible layer, grasped each other and stand.

In another fragment, as in (2), instead of applying the expected sequence of tenses, the translation mirrored the form of the source text.

- (2) ST: Chciał krzyknąć o udach, na których dziś zaśnie.
 (lit. ‘He wanted to shout about the thighs on which he would fall asleep today’)
- C11: He wanted to shout about the thighs he’ll sleep on today.

Translation versions 1 and 2 generated by Claude were characterised by calques, with several instances of literary translation of individual words that failed to produce correct collocations in the target language or distorted the meaning. For example, *sweat spots* (meaning ‘heat rash’) was used as a translation of *plamki potu* (lit. ‘little spots of sweat’) or *give slaps* was a literal translation of *dawać klapsy* in C11 and C12. In most responses generated for prompts 1 and 2, the target sentences followed the structure of the source language, resulting in awkward and unnatural phrasing. For instance: *In the field they chose, a circle was mowed and an approach to this circle two meters wide* (as a direct equivalent of *Na polu, które wybrali, wykoszono koło i dojście do tego koła o szerokości dwóch metrów*). This tendency was also evident in the translation of the phrase *młoda para* (lit. ‘young couple’, meaning ‘the bride and the groom’) in several translations (C11, C12, Ge2). In this particular context, the translation contradicted the source text, as the bride was an older woman. However, only ChatGPT consistently used the correct phrase *the bride and groom* in all three translations, at least in the first part of the text. Later in the text, ChatGPT reverted to employing the calque *the young couple* for subsequent occurrences of *młoda para*.

Regarding the aspect of accuracy, ChatGPT also showed a tendency to alter the name of the character Zet. In two outputs (Ch1 and Ch3), the form *Zeta* was used, despite the fact that nothing in the source text suggested this variation, as the name consistently appeared in its uninflected form.

A grammar issue related to accuracy was observed in the use of tenses in example (3), which refers to the internal monologue of the main character XY.

- (3) ST: XY nie działa, pomyślał, no tak, to byłoby chore, gdyby XY działał.
(lit. ‘XY doesn’t work, he thought, well yes, it would be sick if XY worked’)

Individual translations rendered this fragment using the following different structures:

- Ch1: XY doesn’t work, he thought. Well, of course, it would be insane if XY worked.
- Ch2, Ch3: XY is malfunctioning, he thought. Of course, it would be twisted if XY worked properly.
- C11: XY doesn’t work, he thought, well, it would be sick if XY worked.
- C12: XY doesn’t work, he thought, well, it would be sick if XY did work.
- C13: XY’s on the fritz, he mused, yeah, it’d be messed up if XY actually worked right.
- G1, G3: XY doesn’t work, he thought, well, yeah, it would be sick if XY worked.
- G2: XY doesn’t work, he thought, yeah, it would be sick if XY worked.

The choice between the present continuous and present simple in this case does not result in significant changes to the story but reflects the internal state of the main character, who is described using the imagery of a machine (e.g. *sweat-like smear*, *vows of steel*, *metal surrounding*). Using the continuous form (which was surprisingly rare in the AI-generated output) would better correspond to XY’s present condition, emphasising that he is not functioning as he should at that specific moment.

The creativity of the AI-generated texts was examined through the analysis of creative shifts and non-standard renderings of poetic imagery. The task of measuring creativity has long been considered challenging due to the perceived difficulty of quantifying the inherently subjective quality of a text. Nonetheless, Bayer-Hohenwarter (2009: 45) has proposed criteria for measuring and promoting translational creativity, focusing on the concept of creative shifts. In this approach, creative shifts are cognitive categories contrasting with traditional shift concepts such as addition, change, or omission, which are primarily form-oriented categories. Bayer-Hohenwarter argues that creative shifts involve semantic changes at the level of abstraction, where a translator employs abstraction, modification, or concretisation to achieve novelty. This demonstrates flexibility, a key indicator of creativity in translation. To produce a translation that effectively fulfils its intended purpose, translators often need to move beyond simple word-for-word translations that require less cognitive effort. Instead, they may need to employ more complex strategies involving understanding the deeper meaning of the source text beyond its literal wording. These strategies require significantly more cognitive effort than reproduction, the term used for non-creative translation. It might be expected that AI-generated texts would tend to adhere closely to the source text, resulting in a machine-like quality often described as translationese. However, unlike machine translation tools that typically provide one single version of the translation – albeit with some modifiable elements, as suggested in changes offered by tools like DeepL – AI tools can follow a series of instructions, adapt to the context, and comply with the imposed style as specified in the prompt. Additionally, the nature of the response generated by the tool can be determined by adjusting the temperature setting. Given the inability to use all three tools via an IT interface that allows parameter adjustments, the prompts were carefully structured to ensure responses corresponding to three temperature levels: low, medium, and high.

The analysed texts demonstrated the presence of all three types of creative shifts identified by Bayer-Hohenwarter: abstractions, concretisations, and modifications. These shifts are summarised in Table 1, categorised by specific AI models and prompts.

Table 1: Creative shifts identified in AI-generated translations

	Ch1	Ch2	Ch3	C11	C12	C13	G1	G2	G3
Abstractions		1	1				1		
Concretisations	3	13	14			43	5	6	6
Modifications	2	6	4		1	16	1	1	2
Total number of creative shifts	5	20	19	0	1	59	7	7	8

The analysis of nine texts generated by three AI tools demonstrated that, although all three types of creative shifts were present in the translations, abstractions – referring to cases where translators resort to solutions that are more general or abstract than the source text meaning – were clearly the least frequent. Abstractions were identified in only two cases: *the couple* as a translation of *mloda para* (‘the bride and groom’, lit. ‘young couple’) in Ch 3 and G1; *In the chosen area* is used as a translation of *Na polu, które wybrali* (lit. ‘In the field they selected’).

The high frequency of concretisations is consistent with a general feature of translated texts, which “tend to be simpler, more standardised, and more explicit, retaining some characteristics that pertain to the source language” (Zhang & Toral 2019: 73). Apart from representing a creative shift and thus a sign of flexibility, concretisations can be associated with “depth of analysis”, i.e., going beyond the mere surface of the apparent and obvious to provide details of what is assumed to be the core meaning (Bayer-Hohenwarter 2009: 46). Concretisations can be identified in cases where the translation evokes a more explicit and precise idea or image than the source text, sometimes by adding an element that changes the tone of the utterance. For example, the rendering of the phrase *dawać klapsy* (‘spank’, lit. ‘give slaps’) as *to playfully slap* (G2) demonstrates this shift.

Concretisations were clearly more frequent in texts generated in response to prompts 2 and 3 (corresponding to medium and high temperature settings in the AI tools), although they were also present in texts generated in response to the first prompt. These shifts typically involved specific words and phrases, e.g., *Each of the guests’ foreheads tilted* as a translation of the phrase *Każdy z gościnnych łbów pochylił się* (lit. ‘Each of the guest heads bowed’) in G1. They also affected entire sentences, e.g., *The horizon line crept closer to that big sky dome* as an equivalent of the fragment *Linii horyzontu było bliżej do kopuły* (lit. ‘The horizon line was closer to the dome’). This version provided a specific interpretation of the phrase, clearly altering the tone of the source text.

The term *modification* refers to the shifts that occur at the same level of abstraction, such as expressing a source text metaphor with a different target text metaphor, without making the image more abstract or concrete (Bayer-Hohenwarter 2010: 88). An interesting example of modification can be found in the Ch1 translation of the following fragment: *baldachimy, kable i krawaty nie poddawały się wiatrowi ani słońcu* (lit. ‘canopies, cables and ties did not yield to the wind or the sun’), which was rendered as *canopies, cables, and ties resisted both the wind and the sun*. Here, the negative construction in the source text was replaced with a positive form in the translation.

Another noteworthy example concerns the translation of the sentence *Zapletli włosy w warkocze i przykryli twarze białym pudrem* (lit. ‘They braided their hair and covered their faces with white powder’), rendered by ChatGPT (Ch2) as *Their hair was woven into braids, and their faces dusted with white powder*. This translation replaced the dynamic, action-oriented image highlighted by the active voice in the source text with a more descriptive and static image employing a passive voice. While the source texts emphasised the agency and actions of the couple, the target text focused on the results of their actions, creating a sense of observation. It should also be noted that, while the source text used a more direct and literal description (*covered with white powder*), AI-generated text employed more figurative language with the phrase *dusted with white powder*, where *dusted* creates a more visual and perhaps delicate image. The choice of active or passive voice, along with subtle differences in wording, shifts the emphasis and creates different effects for the reader. The source text emphasises the actions while the AI-generated translation focuses on the visual result.

The AI tools used in this experiment responded very differently to the same prompts, as evidenced by the number of creative shifts. While the output generated by ChatGPT and Gemini differed only in terms of specific translation solutions applied, the difference with Claude was much more pronounced. Prompts 1 and 2 resulted in more or less literal translations of the source text, preserving the sentence structure and imagery of the original, thus producing a machine-translationese effect. However, prompt 3, intended to elicit a response with a high-temperature setting, produced a text with strong emotional meaning.

This was achieved through the abundant use of emotionally charged vocabulary, e.g., *Most guests sported flip-flops, 'cause for some damn reason, blisters were all the rage that summer* as a translation of the more neutral Polish sentence *Większość gości przyszła w japonkach, bo — z nieznanym powodów — tego lata było łatwo o otarcia* (lit. ‘Most of the guests came in flip-flops because – for reasons unknown – it was easy to get chafed this summer’), or *The guests were too busy melting in the heat to notice a damn thing* as a translation of the direct, clear, and simple *Goście byli zbyt zajęci upałem, żeby zauważyć jakąkolwiek zmianę* (lit. ‘Guests were too busy in the heat to notice any change’). Interestingly, this translation included plenty of metaphors and similes that were absent from the source text, e.g., *canopies, cables, and neckties all giving the finger to wind and sun alike* as a rendering of the Polish *baldachimy, kable i krawaty nie poddawały się wiatrowi ani słońcu* (lit. ‘canopies, cables and ties did not yield to the wind or the sun’), or *times were tough as nails* as a translation of *czasy były ciężkie* (lit. ‘times were tough’). This version of the translation also employed changes in imagery, such as rendering the Polish phrase *Garnitur ściągał go na dół jak woda* (lit. ‘The suit was pulling him down like water’) as *His monkey suit dragged him down like a lead weight*. Remarkably, the poetic imagery was consistent with the overall context of the source text. For instance, C13 used the phrase *As they took centre stage in that grassy arena* as an equivalent of *Kiedy stanęli po środku koła* (lit. ‘When they stood in the middle of the circle’). Although the image of grass was not explicitly present in this sentence, the entire scene was set up in a field, making the use of the adjective *grassy* seem justified. Contrary to the common opinion of machine-translated or AI-generated translations, this version did not merely reproduce the source text without additional elements or modifications. Instead, it displayed a tendency to impose a particular point of view on the emotional state of the characters through the use of emotionally charged vocabulary, e.g., *He parroted words that might as well have been gibberish* as a rendering of the original *Powtarzał słowa, których nie rozumiał* (lit. ‘He repeated words he did not understand’).

The analysis of the number of individual translation solutions provided for a single problem by the AI tools yielded interesting results. This capacity to produce multiple solutions corresponded to the concept of fluency in Bayer-Hohenwarter’s (2009: 41) framework of translation creativity. In this regard, AI was particularly helpful in finding translations for unconventional phrases. For that reason, it was considered useful to compare how different tools rendered specific sentences that set the tone of the text. Krasny’s text involves imagery of metal, machinery, and a robotic setting, juxtaposed with a wedding ceremony. This same idea was rendered by the AI tools using a varied selection of vocabulary, as shown in (4).

- (4) ST: A XY nie chciał przysiąc ze stali.
 (lit. ‘And XY did not want oaths of steel’)
- Ch1: But XY didn’t want oaths of steel.
- Ch2/3: And XY didn’t want vows forged in steel.
- C11: And XY didn’t want steel vows.
- C12: But XY didn’t want steel vows.
- C13: But XY wasn’t after iron-clad vows.
- G1/2/3: And XY didn’t want vows made of steel.

The AI suggestions differ in the level of formality and the imagery they create. For instance, *vows* is slightly less formal than *oaths* in Ch1, and the use of the conjunction *but* instead of *and* might imply a contrast that is not present in the original. The addition of *forged* enhances the imagery, which is absent in the original, potentially altering the emphasis of the text and risking over-translation. On the one hand, not all options sound natural in English (e.g. *steel vows*), although this literal word order and awkwardness can be used to retain the concept of the source text. On the other hand, the option that adds unnecessary words (*made of*) makes the sentence less concise.

Another example of figurative language applied by the author to create a surrealistic imagery of machinery is the sentence describing the groom's emotional state under intense pressure in the analysed scene: *Spocił się smarem* (lit. 'He sweated with grease'). The AI solutions provided several options combining the image of sweat and grease, although in one case *smear* was replaced with *oil*, as shown below.

- Ch1: He sweated oil
- Ch2/3: Sweat slicked his skin like grease
- C11/2, G1/3: He sweated grease
- C13: Sweat slicked him like grease
- G2: He was sweating grease.

Those examples show the wide range of solutions generated by AI, starting with a simple word-for-word translation (*he sweated grease*), using a term that typically applies to machines, not human beings (*sweated oil*), to focusing on the physical sensation and appearance (*sweat slicked him like grease*). Notably, the translations differ not only in the choice of lexical elements, but also the grammatical form: The version produced by Gemini, for instance, uses the past continuous, emphasising the groom's state at a particular moment. As can be seen from these examples, the versions generated by Claude in response to prompt 3 are consistently the furthest from the literal translation, representing the boldest approach. However, such intervention in the text, which enhances imagery and imposes a particular perspective, carries the risk of over-translation. Moreover, it alters the author's original style, which relies on simple words and phrases, inviting the reader to imagine the story between the spoken words and to experience emotion through the imagery evoked in the reader's mind rather than through overtly emotive language.

6. Conclusions

The AI-generated translations analysed in this paper demonstrated the presence of all three procedures (abstraction, modification, and concretisation) recognised as creativity shifts – measures of the creative features of the translated text. In her original paper, Bayer-Hohenwarter (2009: 46) claimed that if such shifts result in an adequate product, the application of these procedures is considered a creative process in itself. Interestingly, Bayer-Hohenwarter contrasted creative translation produced by experienced translators and translation trainers with the superficial reproduction accomplished by machines. As seen in the analysis of specific translation solutions, current translation tools are capable of processing much more than the surface level of language, taking into account the overall context, imagery, and imposed style.

Paul Kussmaul (2000: 118), a pioneer in research on creativity and translation, argued that creative translation requires a balance between originality and appropriateness. While the translation should exhibit novelty and an element of surprise, it must also remain suitable for the intended audience and context. The translations generated by all three AI models demonstrated appropriateness, as they were, overall, accurate and linguistically correct texts that complied with the translation brief, presented here in the form of a structured prompt. Individual rare errors were easy to correct. The translations also contained elements of surprise in the form of unique translation solutions or specific choices of vocabulary. However, as is evident from the quantitative analysis of creative shifts, especially in the output produced by the Claude AI model, the balance between originality and accuracy proved problematic. The texts tended to be either too literal or too complicated, with creative additions and changes introduced in almost every sentence of the translation. These changes imposed certain imagery and heavily affected the authorial voice of the Polish author. This proves that the mere identification of creative shifts is a problematic measure of creativity in the context of AI-generated texts. Further research should focus on emotional intelligence in AI, exploring the subtle balance underlying creative expressions, which sometimes sacrifice accuracy to capture the emotional impact of the original.

However, the variety of solutions provided by different prompts in different tools might be particularly useful for translators brainstorming ideas. In this sense, the resourcefulness of the tools might contribute to the creative process, embodying the idea of augmented creativity, where artificial intelligence develops a large number of possible solutions, thus supporting translators in idea generation and contributing to human culture (Griebel et al. 2020). AI models excel at quickly and accurately translating large volumes of text, handling different language structures and identifying the most likely meaning of words based on context. In this regard, they can also be useful in the field of literary translation – not to mimic human creativity or to replace professional translators, but by offering options for human editors to choose from. AI tools are constantly evolving, and over time, they could be trained on larger datasets with richer contextual information, providing better output and new tools for specific languages (e.g. the Polish Large Language Model Bielik). Based on the experiment described in this paper, it can be concluded that, at the current stage of development, AI can assist human translators by providing initial drafts, suggesting alternative translations, and handling the technical aspects of translation. However, AI still lacks balance and a sensitivity to nuance. It is probable that the future of translation will involve collaboration between humans and AI models, leveraging the unique strengths of each. At the same time, it should not be forgotten that the rise of AI in translation also presents significant ethical questions. When an AI system is trained on vast amounts of existing literary works, it blurs the line between human and machine creativity. The output generated by AI can be seen as an appropriation of the skills and creations of human translators, as it synthesises their work without credit or compensation. AI-generated translations also risk perpetuating biases present in their training data, leading to translations that may lack cultural sensitivity and nuance, which can result in the loss of cultural content. As AI is based on data and statistics and not personal understanding, it is less capable of capturing the subtleties of human language. While AI offers opportunities for efficiency and can assist in handling the technical aspects of translation, providing an unparalleled opportunity to investigate new tools, the future of the field seems to lie in collaboration between human translators and AI, but this requires a careful re-examination of concepts like originality, novelty and creativity, as well as fair compensation.

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Małgorzata Kodura
Instytut Filologii Angielskiej UKEN
Karmelicka 41, 31-128 Kraków, Poland
Email: malgorzata.kodura@uken.krakow.pl